

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures in Germany – The case of the federal state of North Rhine- Westphalia

Country Dossier (WP3)

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Table of Contents

List of Abbreviations.....	2
List of Figures	3
List of Tables.....	3
Summary.....	4
The GAPs Project	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Brief introduction of the wider GAPs project and WP3	7
1.2 Introduction of the case study.....	7
2. Methods	8
2.1 General methodological framework of WP3	8
2.2 Specific conditions of data collection and analysis of the case study	8
3. Context.....	11
3.1 Context of migration	11
3.2 Historical overview: The evolution of Return Migration Infrastructures in Germany and NRW.....	12
3.3 Return migration in Germany and NRW: Trends and figures	17
4. Return Migration Infrastructures in NRW.....	20
4.1 Assisted return	24
4.2 Forced removals.....	32
5. Case study: Forced Removal Migration Infrastructure in NRW, Germany	34
5.1 Actors involved in the forced removal infrastructure and their role/intention/mandate.....	34
5.2 Implementation/ “doings” of RMI connected to places of forced pick-up for removal	42
5.2.1 Actions by different actors.....	42
5.2.2 How do they facilitate or contest returns (How effective are they?)	51
5.3 Materials and technologies used in the forced removal infrastructure.....	56
5.4 Relationships of actors, materials and technologies in NRW’s forced return migration infrastructure.....	61
5.4.1 Collaborations/ networks of facilitating and contesting actors	61
5.4.2 Tensions/ oppositions of actors	66
5.4.3 Financial flows between institutions, actors and networks.....	73
5.4.4 Implementation gaps between different actors’ agendas and actions.....	76
6. Conclusion	80
7. References.....	85
8. Annex: Glossary.....	101

List of Abbreviations

ABH	Foreigners Authority (<i>Ausländerbehörde</i>)
AfD	Alternative für Deutschland
AHaftVollzG	Forced Removal Detention Act (<i>Abschiebungshaftvollzugsgesetz</i>)
AMIF	Asylum, migration and integration fund (<i>Asyl-, Migrations- und Integrationsfonds</i>)
AnkER	“Arrival, decision and return” facilities
APS	Departure Planning Statistics
AsylG	German Asylum Act (<i>Asylgesetz</i>)
AufenthG	German Residence Act (<i>Aufenthaltsgesetz</i>)
AufenthV	German Residence Ordinance (<i>Aufenthaltsverordnung</i>)
AZR	Central Registry of Foreigners (<i>Ausländerzentralregister</i>)
BAMF	German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees
bicc	Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies
BMI	German Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community
CDU	Christian-Democratic Union
CSU	Christian Social Union
EU	European Union
EURP	European Reintegration Programme
FAR	Frontex Application for Return
FDP	Liberal Democratic Party
FFiNW	Forum Airports in NRW (<i>Forum Flughäfen in NRW</i>)
GG	German Basic Law (<i>Grundgesetz</i>)
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
IRMA	Integrated Return Management Application
MKFFI	NRW Ministry for Children, Family, Refugees and Integration (2017-22)
MKJFGFI	NRW Ministry for Children, Youth, Family, Equality, Refugees and Integration (since 2022)
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation
NRW	North Rhine-Westphalia
OAM	Online Application Module
OSINT	Open Source Intelligence
PBL	Air escorts (<i>Personenbegleiter:innen Luft</i>)
PEP	Passport replacement paper/s (<i>Passersatzpapier/e</i>)
RCMS	Readmission Case Management System
REAG/GARP	Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum-Seekers in Germany/Government Assisted Repatriation Programme

RIAT	Reintegration Assistance Tool
RKK	Regional Return Coordination Offices (<i>Regionale Rückkehrkoordinationsstellen</i>)
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructures
RT	Round Table (<i>Runder Tisch</i>)
SEK	Police Special Unit (<i>Sondereinsatzkommando</i>)
SIS	Schengen Information System
VG	Administrative Court (<i>Verwaltungsgericht</i>)
WP	Working Paper
ZAB	Central Foreigners Authority (<i>Zentrale Ausländerbehörde</i>)
ZFA	Central Directory for Deportations by Air (<i>Zentralstelle Flugabschiebungen</i>)
ZIRF	Zentralstelle für Informationsvermittlung zur Rückkehrförderung (Central office for the provision of information on return assistance)
ZRK	Zentrale Rückkehrkoordination (Central return coordination [agency])
ZUE	Central accommodation facility (<i>Zentrale Unterbringungseinrichtung</i>)
ZUR	Repatriation support centre (<i>Gemeinsames Zentrum zur Unterstützung der Rückkehr</i>)
ZustAVO	Ordinance on Responsibilities for Foreigners (<i>Verordnung über Zuständigkeiten im Ausländerwesen</i>)

List of Figures

Figure 1: Asylum applications

Figure 2: Decisions on Asylum

Figure 3: Forced removals, incl. Dublin cases

Figure 4: Assisted return (REAG/GARP)

Figure 5: RMI flow map NRW/ Germany

Figure 6: Overview of institutions and actors in forced removals from NRW

Figure 7: Continuum of attitudinal practices in forced removals – from facilitation to resistance

Figure 8: Information-sharing

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of conducted interviews for GAPs WP3

Table 2: Types of obligation to leave and suspension of the obligations as of 31 October 2023

Table 3: Usage of materials and technologies

Table 4: Bridging collaborations between state institutions and forced removal-consenting actor

Summary

This Country Dossier on Germany presents an overview of the assisted and forced return migration infrastructures (RMIs) in Germany, focusing on the most populous federal state of Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), as a case study. It examines how return migration governance is put into practice through the concept of RMIs. Federalism in Germany grants autonomy to local governments, and federal law assigns responsibility for return policies to municipal authorities. This leads to complex coordination among institutions that decide independently on procedures and technologies. Consequently, the staff of the foreigners authorities (*Ausländerbehörden*, ABHs) are often isolated when implementing decisions they did not make and are faced with the conflicting demands of overseeing integration and return.

The extended case study on NRW highlights how the RMIs and forced returns in particular, are implemented by describing the actors involved, their practices (“doings”), the materials and technologies used, the relationships between them and several perceived tensions and ‘gaps’. A broad network of actors involved at different levels emerges, such as those who either facilitate or contest return, others who maintain a dual role, actors with an entrepreneurial approach to the operation of (forced) return, and individuals.

Assisted and forced return procedures are institutionally designed to follow a linear logic; however, non-linearity is very common depending, for example, on the dispositions of migrants, the attitudinal ‘cultures’ in foreigners offices and the strength of local civil society. Moreover, there is a considerable overlap between forced and assisted return in terms of actors/ institutions, activities and technologies, which suggests that the distinction between so-called voluntary assisted return and forced removals is not a strict one but rather a continuum connecting the two. Several practices emerge in grey areas. With the efforts to streamline service providers and the centralisation of institutional support through newly created institutions in NRW, overlaps, including in funding structures, are becoming more pronounced. In both RMIs there is an increasing reliance on Frontex for organisational and procedural tasks but also for funding.

For the forced removal infrastructure, the study revealed a continuum of attitudinal practices among actors, which dilutes the binary between facilitating and contesting actors, as the latter may not oppose forced removals but simply advocate for their enforcement in a more humane manner. Those who categorically reject and oppose forced return usually have no institutionalised support and minimal financial resources. Similarly, within the assisted return migration infrastructure, attitudes towards forced return range from opposition to scepticism to pragmatic acceptance, but contestation tends to be more about the means rather than the ends of RMIs. State technologies of control include opacity and the diffusion of responsibility through the regular issuance of new legal restrictions on foreigners and an increase in bureaucracy.

The implementation gaps in NRW’s return infrastructure are numerous. They can be categorised into three pillars. First, in the field of practical enforcement of returns there are challenges due to limited monitoring and the structural overburdening of foreigners authorities. The second is about the preconditions in the NRW context in terms of lack of minimum standards versus overly restrictive regulations, a lack of sincerity, impartiality and transparency, as well as the outsourcing of responsibility. The third are federal-level

frameworks as a norm-setting context where we see legislative hyperactivity in Germany that remains without effect, and the autonomy of local government. The gaps seem to result from the search for solutions in ever more institutional innovations and legal adaptations with endless exceptions and new detailing of case possibilities, leading to an administrative–bureaucratic deadlock and inefficiency. Gaps in monitoring, and the outsourcing of responsibility for returnees by handing them over at departure/ arrival in the destination country, pose high risks in terms of the protection of rights but are largely ignored. The reasons for this are speculative, but it is likely that a mixture – consisting at least of a lack of political will and a lack of capacity in the face of bureaucratic and decision-making deadlocks on the one hand and an overload of staff and mandates on the other – accounts for the current situation.

The focus on the perceived need for quicker and ‘more effective’ returns in German political debates has rendered assisted return largely invisible. While some providers seek to promote its benefits, others fear that increased publicity will lead to increased scrutiny and controversy. The landscape of assisted return has developed into a patchwork of practices without a solid legal foundation, while the current discourse favours harsh measures despite their financial and human costs. Recent federal calls for more forced removals, and increasing pressure, especially financial insecurity, on non-state actors in NRW, have left stakeholders sceptical about the future of assisted return in general or the role of non-state providers in it. Moreover, there is a clear trend towards state institutions taking more control of the process in forced removals and assisted return at the federal level and in NRW, e.g., through the establishment and increased role of interface institutions, centralisation efforts and shifts in return counselling.

Keywords: return, forced removals, assisted returns, governance of returns, Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia, return migration infrastructure

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- A trajectory approach, which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026), coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Brief introduction of the wider GAPs project and WP3

Return migration has become a policy priority across the world, and especially in Europe. The GAPs project is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies, and the potential disconnects between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a de-centring approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Euro-centric understanding of return policymaking. The consortium consists of 17 partners in 12 countries across four different continents¹.

This Country Dossier on Germany is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPs project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is *put in practice* through the concept of “return migration infrastructures (RMIs)”, by focusing on the so-called “crucial meso-level” (Faist 2021). Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g. Xiang & Lindquist 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (“doings”), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape – i.e. facilitate *or* undermine and contest – the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the aforementioned work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground through a range of practices (Koinova et al. 2021).

1.2 Introduction of the case study

Given the complexity of Germany’s return governance framework by default – i.e., with a three-tier administration and highly heterogeneous actor constellations and practices at the local (community-) level (Mielke et al. 2024) – the case study zooms in on one of the 16 federal states, North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). With a population of 18.2 million, it is the largest and one of the most diverse in population (Germany: 84.7 million)² and governance architecture. It has been the state where most of the documented facilitated (including forced) returns to EU member states and countries of origin occur (cf. section 3.3). NRW shares a border with the EU member states the Netherlands and Belgium; it has several airports, the most relevant for return migration infrastructures being Düsseldorf and Bonn/ Cologne. In contrast to all other federal states, NRW has maintained a highly devolved governance architecture, resulting in a parallel existence of centralizing agencies (e.g. the Central Foreigners Authorities, ZAB) and 81 decentralized foreigners authorities (Ausländerbehörde/n, ABH/s) that bear the responsibility to enforce the return of persons who are obliged to leave the country according to the provisions of the Residence Act and Asylum Act. Thereby, the ABH personnel has a considerable margin of discretion through which they ‘put return migration governance into practice’. Moreover, NRW has the highest number of return counselling providers, mainly consisting of ABHs/ZABs on the one and non-state organisations on the other hand. This governance structure already encapsulates an inherent tension between legal provisions and decisions based on them versus the implementation level, where actors are challenged in several dimensions to enforce the decisions (made somewhere else). The case study focuses on foreign nationals without a ‘right to remain’ and who are obliged to leave the country;

¹ For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>

² <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bevoelkerung/Bevoelkerungsstand/Tabellen/bevoelkerung-nichtdeutsch-laender.html>

assuming that no reasons apply for them to tolerate their stay, thus with the obligation to leave considered enforceable ('vollziehbar ausreisepflichtig') according to Art. 58.1 AufenthG. Following this assessment, the supposed returnees are exposed to an axis of coercion that includes assisted returns and forced removals, thereby going beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness versus forced returns (Şahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou 2024).

2. Methods

2.1 General methodological framework of WP3

The empirical research for this *Working Paper* lasted from June 2023 to November 2024 and included two main tasks. The first was to create an overview of return migration infrastructures (RMIs) in each partner country by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their 'doings', and iii) the materials and technologies used.

Second, the WP3 research on NRW focused on the selection of a particular type of RMI, in this case forced removal. The research started from a variety of specific 'entry points' on the ground related to the everyday workings of the forced removal infrastructure. It included conducting 22 interviews (and partly written responses to questions) with actors involved at the meso level of the everyday operation of the return procedure that may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees were given an Information Letter and signed the Consent Form for participation in the research. These, as well as the interview transcripts in German and an English translation, are stored on the servers of Uppsala University.

2.2 Specific conditions of data collection and analysis of the case study

For the current case study, the interviews the researchers had conducted built on the semi-structured guideline provided by the WP but significantly extended beyond that, with a narrative component in many cases depending on the background and positionality of the interview partner/s. In addition, previously conducted 23 interviews (2019-2022) by the authors in the framework of another research project on return and reintegration (2019-23)³ were used as these had covered several aspects of assisted returns from Germany. Given the complexity of the situation in Germany in terms of a highly heterogeneous actors' landscape, the discretionary power and scope of actions and agency of local / subnational actors in the federal system of multiple tiers – which results in several parallel and often dissimilar practices – the practice dimension covered by the interviews could only test and scrutinize insights from secondary literature research. Or, to put it the other way around, the researchers felt the need to position and contextualize the situated views and detailed insights about practices that were shared in some interviews with the available insights from other studies

³ Research project titled "Trajectories of Reintegration, The Impact of Displacement, Migration and Return on Social Change", <https://www.bicc.de/Projects/Trajectories-of-reintegration>.

and reports about the topic. The paper subsequently reflects a partial insight of the complexity of the NRW return migration infrastructure. Important to note is that all information given below refers to the period of data collection, as of 31 December 2024, if not noted otherwise.

Moreover, there were challenges in accessing interview partners in the NRW regulatory authorities where only lower-tiered foreigners offices and some of those working on assisted return (including in one of the five Central Foreigners Authorities (*Zentrale Ausländerbehörde/n*, ZABs) agreed to participate in the research. The Federal Police and state police remained inaccessible and denied all requests for interviews or background talks.⁴ Likewise, in the institutions hosting those who are obliged to return, the administration (care, security and institutional service providers in central and decentralized accommodation facilities) and medical service providers that play a role in various stages of returns, remained largely inaccessible.

Non-governmental actors of the so-called meso-level were more open to share their insights, while interviews about assisted return – despite relatively better access - had to be mainly conducted online. NRW comprises of a rich landscape of civil society organizations and other actors such as communal volunteers. Rather contrary to the initial assumption of the WP logic – that there would be a binary division of actors along the division of those who facilitate and those who oppose forced returns – the actual situation is not clearcut and the overall political developments, financial dependencies and current polarizations have a bearing on the (non)engagement of those who oppose forced returns in meso-level institutions and organizations. Some non-governmental actors, such as charities, are torn about whether or not to engage in assisted return and return counselling. Some have formulated high internal standards before engaging with it, the larger ones may run advocacy sections that contest the legal and political means introduced to enhance deportability at a different level. Among the interviewees, those who scrutinise the existing return infrastructure in NRW are taking care not to be(come) part of it – especially in the operational dimension.

The authors employed two strategies to compensate for these challenging conditions: First, we focused on interview partners with a broad range of insights, some occupying several positions in crucial interfaces of the RMI between government and civil society institutions. In this way, the authors were able to tap the knowledge about the practices of inaccessible actors and complement/ square them with insights from secondary written sources. As a rule, these actors and representatives of institutional bodies who are part of the RMI had a good overview of the larger context and structures in their purview, given their own efforts to document, resolve and report return cases and respective procedures. To give but three examples of interviewees: (1) actors involved in the Forum Flughäfen [airports] in NRW which also includes departure monitoring and an annual publication (Diakonie 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024); (2) Abschiebungsreporting (Deportation Reporting) NRW – an initiative funded by several institutions in NRW together with the Berlin-based Institute for Human Rights which tracks and publishes on individual cases and practices on their website and published a state of the art compilation in 2024 (Rose & Schießl 2024); (3) to gain further insights into the whole aspect of forced removal detention – NRW has one such facility within the municipality

⁴The denial of access by all types of German police forces was not expected and is thus telling as such, after Borrelli had been able to conduct participant observation with state police and conduct interviews with Federal Police representatives between 2015 and 2016, cf. Borrelli (2021, p. 3476).

of Büren with space for up to 175 people (2023, cf. Bundestag 2024, p. 21) – insights from previous published research of volunteers in the Association ‘Hilf für Menschen in Abschiebehaft Büren e.V.’ (Assistance for People in Deportation Detention (Droste and Nitschke 2022) were complemented and cross-checked for updates in an additional interview.

To enrich collecting insights about actual practices and actors and varying data sources, the authors took a quasi-ethnographic approach by attending several specialised training courses, workshops and conferences dealing with or closely related to the issue of return migration infrastructure. This included (1) a training course for staff of ABHs on the topic of return enforcement challenges (2024), (2) a two-day meeting organised for return counsellors from across Germany to exchange and receive updates by state authorities and Frontex on the latest developments regarding assisted return procedures (IntegPlan Fachtagung, 2024), (3) the annual Berliner Symposium zum Flüchtlingsschutz (refugee rights symposium) which are conducted by the Evangelische Akademie Berlin (2022, 2023, 2024), attended by a vast range of civil society actors and various stakeholders; (4) an activist academia workshop organised by the kritnet network of critical migration scholars (2024); (5) an NRW-focused convention on return counselling (2025). These events brought new contacts, insights and opportunities for cross-checking, raising questions with the practitioners and validating empirical data throughout data collection and analysis.

Table 1: Overview of conducted interviews for GAPs WP3

Category/ type of interviewee	Number of interviews
State government bodies	3
Foreigners Authority	3
Central Foreigners Authority	1
Medical service providers	1
Counsellors	3
Migrant self-organization	1
Organised civil society	2
Church representatives	3
Informed observers from within the RMI (other than the above but overlapping with organised civil society institutions)	4
Written interview questions and response (Frontex)	1
SUM	22

All primary and secondary source materials (except hardcover books) were analysed with the help of MAXQDA, a qualitative data analysis software. Interviews were completely coded; besides, secondary materials were coded based on utility.

3. Context

This section summarises basic information about asylum and return migration trends in Germany and the state of North-Rhine Westphalia (NRW), as well as the underlying developments that led to the evolution of today's return migration infrastructures. Most notable but not subjected to (asylum and) return migration (infrastructures) is the immigration of Ukrainians since 2022. Their number increased from 155,000 in 2021 to 1,239,705 at the end of 2023; they currently constitute the second-largest group of foreign nationals in Germany.⁵

3.1 Context of migration

Over the last 25 years, asylum immigration and protection rates in Germany correlated strongly (cf. Figures 1⁶, 2⁷). While the number of asylum applications was at around 80,000 applications per year at the turn of the century, a steady decline set in from 2003 onwards, reaching its lowest point in 2007 with only a quarter (19,164) of the earlier application numbers. The most significant increase in asylum applications occurred in 2015-16 with a

⁵ The EU reacted to the massive influx of Ukrainians fleeing to EU Member states by activating the Temporary Protection Directive in 2022, based on which Ukrainians move freely within the EU and do not have to submit individual asylum applications (SVR 2024). Refugees from Ukraine without papers – such as 20 per cent of those belonging to the Roma community residing in Ukraine – were excluded from the benefits of the Directive and subjected to discrimination (Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 25.). Third country nationals based in Ukraine at the start of the war, such as international students, also did not qualify for protection. Many had no other option than to return to their origin countries, including through assisted return.

⁶ Sources for Figure 1: BMI (2023, p. 85), BAMF (2007, p. 13; 2008, p. 23; 2009, p. 15; p. 13; 2010; 2011, p. 16; 2012, p. 16; 2013, p. 16; 2014, p. 16; 2015, p. 16; 2016a, p. 5; 2016b, p. 16; 2017, p. 7; 2018, p. 7; 2019, p. 8; 2020, p. 8; 2021, p. 8; 2022, p. 8; 2023, p. 3, 8; 2024a, p. 3, 8).

⁷ Sources for Figure 2: BMI (2016, p. 78), BAMF (2024a, p. 11).

record high of 722,370 applications in 2016. Ever since, asylum applications have been higher than before 2013. With 329,120 applications it reached another peak in 2023.

The national trend of asylum applications is also mirrored in NRW – the largest of the German federal states in terms of population and territory. Over the years, NRW received the largest number of asylum applications, around 20-27 percent of the German total. Since 2012, Syrians have been in the lead with 32.8 per cent of the applications from 2014-2018 (BMI 2020, p. 91), followed by Afghans as second largest group (BMI 2023, p. 86), and Iraqis as third largest (BMI 2022, p. 78) until in 2022 they were replaced in the ranking by Turks (23,938 applications in 2022) (BMI 2022, p. 87). Protection rates⁸ at federal level have been steadily on the rise until 2023, from around five per cent (2003) to 27 per cent in 2007, 37.7 per cent in 2008 and 56 per cent in 2022 (52 percent in 2023) – with the NRW figures even being slightly higher with 58 per cent in 2022 (MKJFGFI 2023a, p. 1) and 54 per cent in 2023 (MKJFGFI 2024a, p. 1).

3.2 Historical overview: The evolution of Return Migration Infrastructures in Germany and NRW

In the 1950s and 1960s, Germany signed several bilateral agreements on the recruitment of so-called guest workers (*Gastarbeiter:innen*) from selected partner countries, e.g. with Spain, Greece, Turkey and others (Oltmer and Hanewinkel, 2021). Until the end of recruitment with the so-called recruitment stop (*Anwerbestopp*) in 1973, 14 million workers came to Germany, from which 11 million went back to their country of origin (Oltmer and Hanewinkel 2021). A Return Assistance Act (*Rückkehrhilfegesetz*) was passed in 1983, introducing temporary return assistance for returns before 30 September 1984 (Akçit 2023). In hindsight, this Act

⁸ The protection rate is the sum of asylum recognitions according to Art. 16a German Basic Law and Family Asylum, recognition as a refugee in line with Sec. 3 (1) Asylum Act, subsidiary protection according to Sec. 4 (1) Asylum Act and determination of a ban on deportation pursuant to Sec. 60 (5) or (7) Residence Act in relation to the total number of decisions in the relevant period. Cf. BAMF (2024c, p. 37).

constitutes the first and only legal basis for return assistance in Germany. The REAG programme (Reintegration and Emigration Program for Asylum-Seekers in Germany) was founded earlier (in 1979) and counts as the first of its kind (IOM 2019). Return assistance programmes mainly targeting protection seekers grew in number and quantity during the late 1990s, while return assistance for labour migrants was not scaled up.

After the end of the Cold War, against the background of new evolving violent conflicts, e.g., in former Yugoslavia, the number of asylum applications from eastern and southern Europe increased substantially, peaking in 1992 with almost 440.000 applications (Oltmer and Hanewinkel 2021). This was one factor that invoked a highly polarized debate on the right to asylum, while at the same time violent attacks on housing and homes for asylum seekers surged (Mediendienst Integration 2024a). In 1993, the German government passed the so-called asylum compromise (Asylkompromiss) to limit asylum application numbers by amending Art. 16 of the German Basic Law. Newly implemented Art. 16a qualified the right to asylum for politically persecuted persons by specifying that the right to asylum would be considered ‘plainly unfounded’ for persons entering Germany via one of the member states of the (then so-called) European Communities “or from another third state in which application of the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms is assured.”⁹ The long-term effects of the amendment to the Basic Law can be seen in German and European refugee law and institutional innovations.¹⁰ Article 16a first brought into force the third country regulation, and later also the regulation on so-called safe countries of origin. The additionally introduced so-called airport regulation (*Flughafenregelung*) meant that asylum applicants from ‘safe third countries’ designated as such could be checked directly at the airport entry from the transit area and be refused.¹¹ At the EU level, many states emulated the Safe Countries of Origin Regulation, which had consequences for asylum law throughout Europe, similar to the Dublin Regulation (1997, 2003).

Subsequently, relevant institutions in Germany developed a strong coercive capacity to implement forced removals – even in the face of contestation – before the latest rise in immigration and asylum applications occurred from 2015 onwards. Whereas Ellermann (2005) argues that this relates to the insulation of the implementing agents from their legislative principals, the activities of the Bund-Länder-Arbeitsgruppe Rückführung (“AG Rück”, engl. ‘Return Working Group’ between federal level and state institutions) evidence the existence of an increasingly coercive infrastructure which has developed steadily since 1993. In 2002, AG Rück commissioned an expert assessment on medical obstacles to forced

⁹ https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_gg/englisch_gg.html

¹⁰ For the latter, cf. the establishment the Bund-Länder-Arbeitsgruppe Rückführung (“AG Rück“, engl. ‘Return Working Group’) as a body at federal and state level upon the initiative of the Conference of Interior Ministers (Innenministerkonferenz, IMK) in 1993. NRW was designated chairing state of the AG Rück upon its foundation; the office is located at the Ministry of the Interior of NRW. Today it is called AG Integrated return management (AG Integriertes Rückkehrmanagement). Cf. below for further contextualization.

¹¹ In another political effect at domestic level, the Asylum Seekers’ Benefits Act (of July 1993) replaced former social welfare payments for needy asylum seekers and tolerated persons with benefits in kind, basic health care and pocket money, putting them in a worse position than other needy persons and significantly reducing the minimum subsistence level.

removals and how fitness for air travel can be ensured through accompanying measures (IMK 2002).¹² Similar strong repercussions for the asylum and return debate in Germany can be felt today from a second commissioned assessment of the AG Rück, conducted in 2011 on the so-called *Vollzugsdefizite* (enforcement gaps) (IMK 2011). Immediately before the arrival of unprecedented numbers of refugees in 2015, the expansion of the safe countries of origin to six Balkan states in 2014-15 increased the number of people who neither had a right of residence nor could undergo vocational training and were subject to a general ban on working (Residence Act §60a, valid from 15 August 2015).

The rapid influx of refugees in 2015-16 generated an increasingly polarized and emotionalised public and political debate (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 16) with an emphasis on so-called stay perspectives based on new regulations for training and employment toleration (*Ausbildungsduldung/ Beschäftigungsduldung*)¹³ on the one hand but that also focused on migrants without a right to remain on the other. Regarding the latter, the official return migration focus concentrated on a humane ‘return management’ and the prioritizing of so-called voluntary (assisted) return (MKJFGFI 2024, p. 8). Upon recommendation of the AG Rück, the NRW state government introduced the so-called integrated return management (concept) in 2016, thus institutionally putting the steering of forced and assisted returns in one hand (Bezirksregierung Münster 2024) through the establishment of a central return coordination (agency) (*Zentrale Rückkehrkoordination, ZRK NRW*) in the ZAB in Bielefeld.¹⁴

In the immediately following parliamentary term at federal level (2017-2021), these have led to an increase in restrictive measures, manifest in several new laws since 2015 (Mielke et al. 2024) as well as some material infrastructure plans such as the establishment of additional detention centres throughout Germany (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 16). The detention

¹² One major conclusion regarding the recruitment of doctors in the context of immigration and asylum proceedings was the recommendation to pool medical competences for fit for fly assessments and institutionalize framework contracts with qualified personnel. In hindsight this paved the way for the extensive reliance on specific medical service providers (cf. below) by ABHs.

¹³ The federal government issued an Integration Law in summer 2016, which resulted in the adjustment of Article 60.2.4 of the Residence Act (AufenthG) providing that a responsible immigration authority may issue a stay permit (toleration; *Duldung*) for the duration of vocational training (*Ausbildungsduldung*; usually three years) if the foreigner is enrolled in a qualified vocational training of a state-recognized or similarly recognized training occupation and there is no reason for exclusion (e.g. safe country of origin). After having completed the training successfully, the person is then generally entitled to a two-year residence permit if they can find employment corresponding to the professional qualification (“3+2”). The “*Beschäftigungsduldung*” (temporary termination of the obligation to leave because of employment) according to § 60d AufenthG is a special form of “*Duldung*” issued (Article 60a para. 2 sentence 3 AufenthG) to persons who have been employed for at least 18 months and secure their livelihood. Relatives (spouse and underage children) of a person with a tolerated stay permit can also receive a tolerated stay permit under certain conditions. Only those who entered Germany for the first time by 31 December 2022 are eligible to apply for a tolerated employment permit. As a rule, it is issued for 30 months. If a person has held a tolerated employment permit for 30 months and continues to meet all requirements, they should be granted a residence permit in accordance with Section 25b AufenthG upon application.

¹⁴ The ZRK NRW was to provide the municipalities with technical and organizational assistance by (1) being responsible for return cases to so-called safe countries of origin (Balkan states, Georgia, Armenia), (2) bundling previous support services concerning flight and transportation management and (3) being a focal point for all questions, including related to assisted return (information, contacts, organization of travel documents, etc.). Cf. Landtag NRW (2016).

infrastructure has also been developed to make better use of the extended possibility for detention pending forced removal. The so-called asylum package I has been in force since 2015, and in 2016, the asylum package II was introduced. Both include restrictive measures in the return and asylum procedure, like accelerated process and forced removals without warning (Mielke et al. 2024). In 2017, the federal government together with the state governments founded the Joint Return Support Centre (*Gemeinsames Zentrum für die Unterstützung der Rückkehr*, ZUR) in Berlin (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 34). This was one of the efforts to centralize the return infrastructure at the national level, in an attempt to make it more efficient.

Similar to this, the states and the federal government have made efforts to respond to earlier detected ‘enforcement gaps’ of returns, aiming to enhance the ‘efficiency’ of related administrative processes to accelerate return processes. Several measures were indicative of this return policy. According to the national coalition agreement of 2017, the accommodation of asylum seekers was to be centralized in the so-called AnKER facilities.¹⁵ In 2020, some 15 AnKER facilities were established, with the purpose to process asylum applications more quickly and facilitate the return of persons without ‘prospect to stay’ (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 34, 35; Hänsel et al. 2019).¹⁶ The state of NRW introduced a three-step strategy known as Asyl-Stufenplan in 2018 to centralize efforts to implement both, assisted returns and forced removals. The aim of this three-step plan was to relieve the municipalities and only allocate recognized refugees and persons with good prospects of staying to the municipalities in NRW, by introducing accelerated asylum procedures and extending the stay in centralized reception centres for those with unclear prospects of remaining in Germany to be able to return persons directly from such centres.

A change in coalition from Christian and Social Democrats to one composed of Social Democrats, the Green and the Liberal Party at the national level after elections in 2021 paved the way to facilitate more pathways for tolerated persons towards opportunities to stay. Most significantly, the Opportunity Right Residence (Chancen-Aufenthaltsrecht) Permit, according to Sec. 104c Residence Act, allows long-term tolerated persons without a right to stay to obtain a residence permit – initially for 18 months before becoming eventually eligible for a residence permit according to Sec. 25a or 25b Residence Act. To be eligible for the opportunity residence right, a person must have resided in Germany for an uninterrupted period of five years as of 31 December 2022¹⁷, must be committed to the free and democratic basic order and must not have been convicted of any intentional criminal offences or have repeatedly misrepresented their identity. Sec. 25a and 25b of the Residence Act give “well integrated” young adults and persons the opportunity to obtain a residence permit. Accordingly, a person is considered to be “well integrated” if they have resided in Germany for four or six years, are committed to the free and democratic basic order, have basic knowledge of the German legal and social system, are able to earn a living for themselves and have basic knowledge of the Germany language

¹⁵ AnKER facilities (arrival, decision and return facilities). The central element of the AnKER concept is the bundling of all functions and responsibilities at one location: from arrival, asylum application and decision to municipal distribution, initial preparatory integration measures and the return procedure of rejected asylum applicants.

¹⁶ For a critique on this artificial construct of ‘stay perspective’, cf. below, at the end of Ch. 5.1.

¹⁷ The Opportunity Right Residence was enshrined in the Residence Act for three years (from December 31, 2022); it can be applied for during this period.

(A2-level). If a person, for legal or factual reasons for which they themselves are not responsible, cannot leave the country and it is not expected that this reason will cease to exist in the foreseeable future according to Sec. 25 (5) Residence Act, a residence permit “may” be issued. If the forced removal has been suspended for at least 18 months, a residence permit “should” be issued. By the end of 2024, Germany-wide over 75,000 persons had applied for the opportunity residence right, however the total number is likely to be significantly higher since only eleven of the 16 states collected data, and not all have figures for the entire year, in NRW 18,724 persons applied (Mediendienst Integration 2024b).

In a parallel trend, the discussion about returning migrants has become linked to the discourse on internal security since at least 2001; it saw an intensification from 2016 onwards after on New Year’s Eve 2015/16 a series of sexual assaults occurred in Cologne, mainly committed by young men from north-African and Arabic countries. This immediately led to an increase in calls for easier returns and forced removals, even before it became clear what had occurred that night (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 19).¹⁸ Ever since 2015, the argument has been raised, that foreigners forfeit their right to protection in Germany if they engage in criminal behaviour; however, the right cannot be forfeited completely only by their own actions (Podolski 2024). Several rounds of new legal initiatives aimed to facilitate the return of so called ‘Gefährder’, persons who pose a threat to security e.g. due to criminal behaviour or Islamist motives, thus enhancing already ongoing measures for ‘effectiveness’ to accelerate forced removals and previous increases in the duration people can be held in detention before forced removal. Several deadly incidents that threatened public security triggered further attention to questions of asylum and forced removals, most pronounced in 2024. An attack by an Afghan man at an anti-Islamic demonstration in Mannheim killed a policeman and injured five others, after he targeted the organiser of the protest on 2 June 2024. Politicians, media and police representatives reacted by demanding the forced removal of criminal offenders and ‘Gefährder’ from Afghanistan and Syria to their countries of origin (Podolski, 2024). Two months later, 28 Afghans, designated as ‘violent criminals’ (*Intensivstraftäter*) were forcibly removed to Afghanistan (LTO 2024a).¹⁹ This was only a few days after a terrorist attack occurred in Solingen, carried out by a Syrian, who was supposed to have left Germany the year before (LTO 2024b).

Only three weeks after the attack, the NRW state government agreed upon a comprehensive security package, which includes measures for stronger surveillance of potential extremists and offenders, improved data exchange between authorities, plans for an additional/ second forced removal detention facility²⁰, and measures against irregular migration (LTO 2024b).

¹⁸ The events of that night were the subject of an inquiry committee (*Untersuchungsausschuss*) of the NRW parliament for months.

¹⁹ This despite the fact that the German government has no diplomatic relations with the Taliban’s Islamic Emirate. Reportedly, Qatar facilitated this transfer upon the German governing coalition’s will and pressure to follow populist calls from right-wing parties and movements in Germany. As a general observation, this incidence evidences how migration law and policy is increasingly mixed up with criminal law, because there is no real explanation from policy makers as to why a forced removal can or should substitute already existing criminal law provisions that are usually enforced in Germany.

²⁰ At the time of finalizing this Paper, it became known that NRW plans to build the additional/ second forced removal detention facility not at Düsseldorf airport but within the jurisdiction of the town of Mönchengladbach; the estimated costs are 300 million EUR, even though the currently used facility Büren is underutilized, with only about 60 per cent of places used (Komitee für Grundrechte 2025).

Civil society organizations and NGOs, however, called for compliance with international legal obligations, such as the non-refoulement principle, and raised concerns about human rights violations (Biehler et al. 2021, p. 20). After renewed attacks against public crowds by foreign nationals with mental health issues and partly legal stay permits, e.g., in Magdeburg at the end of December 2024 and Aschaffenburg and Munich in early 2025, the call for stricter forced removals, in particular of Syrians and Afghans, has grown even louder. At a time of intensive election campaigning, politicians from all parties but the Left (Die Linke) spoke out in unison in favour of the quick implementation of forced removals, even to Afghanistan, thus blending forced removals with punitive measures, even though the criminal and asylum laws include provisions for addressing criminal offences.

3.3 Return migration in Germany and NRW: Trends and figures

NRW has been ‘leading’ the Germany-wide returns statistics²¹ of the 16 federal states for more than two decades. It is noteworthy that, while the number of assisted returns (the German national program is called REAG/GARP)²² was higher than that of forced removals in 2016, the ratio has been reversed from 2017 onwards (cf. Figures 3²³, 4) (Deutscher Bundestag 2019, p. 79). The highest number of forced returns in the German context – even higher than during the so-called refugee crisis in 2015-16 and the subsequent push for returns – occurred during the 1990s, with a peak of 53,043 in 1994. Of the last 25 years, the number was the highest in 2000 with more than 35,000 forced removals. These reflected the longer-term consequences of the introduction of Art. 16a of German Basic Law (GG) in 1993 (cf. 3.2 above) which paved the way for enforcing the safe third country concept and the Dublin-regulation (1997). The so-called asylum compromise has been identified as a contributing factor to the decline in asylum cases (cf. 3.2); even though the numbers of applications were high, only 4.3 per cent were recognised (bpb 2013).

²¹ While forced removals, REAG/GARP-returns and Dublin transfers are systematically recorded and therefore included in the statistics, other types of return, in particular non-assisted, assisted by other programs than REAG/GARP, or so-called spontaneous returns, are not registered and remain unknown. Note that this Working paper uses the term ‘forced removals’ to signify both, forced removals to the origin or a third country outside the EU (called returns [*Rückführungen, Abschiebungen*]) and so-called transfers to the EU-country of first entry according to the Dublin regulation (*Dublin-Überstellungen*).

²² Germany’s assisted return program runs under the name REAG/GARP and covers the return as well as some types of reintegration assistance for returns from all 16 German states. REAG/GARP stands for Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum Seekers in Germany/ Government Assisted Repatriation Programme and has been supplemented by StarthilfePlus since 2017, which consists of additional reintegration support administered in 40 origin countries. Since BAMF took over the operational management of REAG/GARP from IOM at the start of 2024, it is referred to as REAG/GARP2.0.

²³ * Germany: Jan. until Nov. 2024, NRW: Jan. until June 2024; Sources for Figure 3: bpb (2024), Deutscher Bundestag (2007, p. 1; 2008, p. 1; 2009, p. 1, 6; 2010, p. 1, 5; 2011, p. 1, 9; 2012, p. 1, 8, 2013, p. 1, 8; 2014, p. 1, 7, 2024c, p. 2, 13), BMI (2016, p. 139), Kreienbrink (2007, p. 200), ZDFheute (2025).

The lowest point in forced removals was recorded for 2010 with 7,558 cases, followed by a steep increase with annual figures above 10,000 from 2012 until today, even during the COVID-19 pandemic.²⁴ In 2023, Germany forcibly removed 16,430 persons. Over the years, NRW's share in the total number of deportations has been 20 to 26 per cent (22.3 per cent in 2023).²⁵ Assisted returns with REAG/GARP (cf. Figure 4²⁶) first peaked around the turn of the century with 67,953 returns in 2000, which was due to the end of the Balkan wars (BAMF 2024b). This was followed by a sharp decline in numbers of assisted returns – only in 2015 did assisted return numbers increase considerably with 35,514 in 2015 and peak with 54,006 returns in 2016 (cf. Figure 4), which was caused by high arrival numbers in 2014 and 2015. In 2017, more than one in three assisted REAG/GARP-returns from Germany were organised in and departed from NRW (Deutscher Bundestag 2021, p. 40). Mainly due to the COVID-19 pandemic, only 5,657 REAG/GARP-returns occurred in 2020, including 1,461 from NRW (cf. Figure 4).

²⁴ While in the first months, fewer forced removals occurred given that many countries had closed their airspace during the pandemic, forced removals resurged in summer 2020.

²⁵ In comparison, the share of Bavaria, a state which is famous for its strict border policing and migration control, ranges between 13 and 16 percent over the years, in 2023 it amounted to 14.4 percent of the national total (bpb 2024).

²⁶ * First half of 2024. Sources for Figure 4: BAMF (2024b), Deutscher Bundestag (2016, p. 47, 48; 2017, p. 56; 2021, p. 40; 2022, p. 30; 2023, p. 25; 2024b, p. 26; 2024c, p. 20).

Table 2 summarises how many people were obligated to leave Germany and NRW by the reporting date 31 December 2023, and how many held a temporary suspension of forced removal (*Duldung*, §60a-d AufenthG) on the same date.²⁷

Table 2: Types of obligation to leave and suspension of the obligation as of 31 December 2023

	Number of persons obligated to leave (<i>ausreisepflichtig</i>)	Number of persons possessing a temporary suspension of forced return (<i>Duldung</i>) ²⁸	Number of persons with enforceable return obligation (<i>unmittelbar/vollziehbar ausreisepflichtig</i>)
Germany	242,642	193,972	48,670
NRW	59,373 (24.47 per cent)	48,902 (25.21 per cent)	10,741 (22.1 per cent)

In 2023, NRW had the highest number of REAG/GARP assisted returns among the German federal states: 2,495 out of a total of 10,763 in 2023 (Bavaria, which is second on the list, had 1870) (Lich et al. 2024). In 2024, Germany forcibly removed 20,084 persons, NRW 4,400 (2023: 16,430 persons vs. 3,663 in NRW), of these 18,384 returned to their country of origin (until 30 November 2024), 5,827 were so-called Dublin transfers to another EU member state (until 30 November 2024).

²⁷ Cf. MKJFGFI (2024d, p. 9), based on AZR entries.

²⁸ The suspension of forced removal does not affect the obligation to leave the country (§60a.3 AufenthG), and the responsible ABH can revoke a temporary suspension at any time if the reasons preventing forced removal no longer apply.

Every year, an increasing number of forced removals is terminated before completion for different reasons, e.g., refusal of carriage by the airline, cancellation of the request, etc., in the different stages of the forced removal process. The overwhelming majority of terminated forced removals stops before the handover to the Federal Police at the airport and thereof most because of the cancellation of the request or because the transfers from the place of pick-up could not take place (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 19). According to official statistics, 615 forced removals failed in 2021 after handover to the Federal Police (Deutscher Bundestag 2022, p. 20). In 2022 a total of 23,377 forced removals failed, thereof 22,408 before and 929 after the returnee was handed over to the Federal Police (Deutscher Bundestag 2023a, p. 11). In 2023, 24,704 forced removals via air transport failed before handover to the Federal Police (Deutscher Bundestag 2023b, p. 22). Cancelled forced removals during the enforcement process from NRW amounted to 4,341 in 2023 (Deutscher Bundestag 2024a) – far more than the 3,663 enforced removals. In 2024 32,567 forced removals were terminated before the returnee was handed over to the Federal Police country-wide and 1,150 removals (314 of which Dublin-cases) during or after hand-over (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, pp. 17, 19), in NRW the number of enforced removals (4,400) nearly equalled the number of cancelled removals in the same period (Zeit Online 2025). There are no statistics on interruptions of assisted return processes. In principle, migrants have the right to decide against assisted return at any point during the process, be it after the first counselling session or at the airport. Assisted returns are less likely to be contested or resisted (by the migrant as well as others) and less likely to be terminated shortly before or during the physical return. In any case, if migrants are subject to a removal order, this remains unaffected by a decision against assisted return though.

The main origin countries of persons designated to leave Germany in mid-2023 comprised Afghanistan (12.3 per cent of all rejected asylum seekers), Iraq (11.7 per cent), Nigeria (7.9 per cent), and Iran (5.5 per cent) (Mediendienst Integration 2025). The five main destination third countries of forced removals in 2024 Germany-wide were Georgia (1,854 persons), North Macedonia (1,396 persons), Turkey (1,087 persons), Albania (1,074 persons), and Serbia (1,031 persons) (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 2). In NRW, the Western Balkan countries North Macedonia, Albania, and Serbia made up around one third of all forced removals during 2023; other destinations included Georgia, Algeria, Austria, Turkey, and Bosnia and Herzegovina (MKJFGFI 2023c, p. 9). In 2024, Germany-wide 10,225 persons returned with assistance in the framework of the REAG/GARP programme; the five main nationalities were Turkey (3,276), Georgia (1,461), Russian Federation (809), North Macedonia (802), and Iraq (498) (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 22). In NRW, the number of assisted returns (REAG/GARP) reached 2,052 in 2024 (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 23).

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in NRW

The legal basis for forced/ coerced returns is defined in national legislation, such as the Residence Act [AufenthG] and Asylum Act [AsylG]. The forcible removal of a foreigner from Germany who does not have a valid residence title or benefits from a temporary suspension of forced removal (*Duldung*) due to administrative/ internal or external obstacles of forced

removal procedures or is no longer allowed to stay in Germany for other reasons²⁹, is captured by a variety of terms, depending on the user, their positionality, and context. Dublin III-forced removals to another EU member state are officially referred to by state institutions as Dublin transfers (*Dublin-Überstellungen*, DÜ) – critics argue this downplays the coerced nature of the transfer –, returns to third or origin countries are officially called returns (*Rückführungen*) and can be assisted (cf. Section 4.1) or forced. “Assisted return” has increasingly replaced the term “voluntary (assisted) return” (which is – however – also still in use), due to growing emphasis on the non-voluntary nature of many of these returns. For the case of forced returns, the term *Abschiebungen* (English lit. ‘deportations’³⁰) is used; it presupposes that the obligation to leave is enforceable³¹ and involves the physical transportation (‘removal’) of the foreigner from Germany and the steps necessary for preparation (cf. below and Ch. 6).

Regarding the operational side of returns in Germany, the federal states are responsible for enforcing returns (aka the obligation to leave). According to Sec. 71 Residence Act (AufenthG), they are obliged to determine a central office to execute both assisted and forced returns³² and involve the state police. However, in contrast to other states, NRW kept the responsibility for returns with the 81 ABHs and established five ZABs to support the municipal ones, even though the ZAB are add-ons and not part of the administrative hierarchy.³³

In line with the EU return directive, assisted returns are meant to be prioritised over forced removals both in Germany and NRW, “unless this would undermine the purpose of a return procedure”.³⁴ They are less costly to the taxpayer, perceived as more humane, allow some degree of preparation (mostly within a rather limited timeframe), more likely to include

²⁹ Only about 60 per cent of those who are obligated to leave Germany are failed asylum seekers; the other 40 per cent comprise a heterogeneous set of people, e.g., foreign students, divorced spouses who lost their residence status, employees or tourists whose visa has expired (so-called overstay).

³⁰ Authorities also speak of ‘repatriation’ (*Rückführung*) as a synonym for the term deportation. ‘Deportation’ is the term used for removal (*Abschiebung*) in the translation of the German Residence Act (AufenthG). It has the same meaning as ‘removal’ as used in the EU Return Directive. For this Paper, the authors decided to use the term ‘forced removal/s’ to designate *Abschiebung/en*, against the background that ‘forced’ returns is more ambivalent given the critique towards assisted returns to be largely forced as well. It is an explicit aim of this Working Paper to show the entanglement and fluidity between assisted return and forced removal (both understood as a continuum of forced return); therefore, this paper positions itself as contributing to the (anglophone) field of deportation studies by way of expanding the initial narrow focus on forced removals with the attention to the continuum and close interdependency of assisted return and forced removal practices (cf. Bartels 2019, Bartels and Sperling 2023, Kalir 2017).

³¹ Supposing that no external or internal reasons (*Abschiebungshindernisse*) exist that will prevent the planned forced removal.

³² Bavaria, for example, established a State Office for Asylum and Returns (Landesamt für Asyl und Rückführungen, LfAR) in 2018 to bundle state-wide competences in the area of forced and assisted return. Schleswig Holstein has a State Office for Immigration and Refugees (Landesamt für Zuwanderung und Flüchtlinge), including a so-called enforcement department (*Vollzugsdezernat*). The political orientation of both states (conservative anti-immigrant government of Christian Social Union, CSU, in Bavaria vs. coalition government of Christian Democratic Union, CDU, and Green Party [Bündnis 90/ Grüne] in Schleswig Holstein) can be gleaned from the naming of the respective departments.

³³ The total number of ABHs in Germany is 549; of these, the state of Bavaria counts 109 ABHs alone (BR24 2025).

³⁴ EU Return Directive 2008, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0115> (accessed 26 February 2025)

reintegration assistance and result in no or a shorter (compared with forced removal) re-entry ban.³⁵ However, except for 1983/84 (cf. 3.2), Germany has not established a legal basis for return assistance. This has given rise to a diverse landscape of return counselling providers and funding lines with stark differences within and between the federal states. Diversity here relates not only to various combinations of different types of organizations, but encompasses their identities, (counselling) practices, standards, funding and reporting modes. The lack of legally prescribed standards gives rise to ingenuity and allows for significant levels of discretion.

Eligibility for return assistance under the national (REAG/GARP) program – which is the main tool for assisted returns - is not only determined by removal order; applications can also be submitted for migrants who wish to return but are unable to raise the required financial means by themselves. Statistics on assisted returns distinguish returnees by legal status to some extent, but do not indicate whether asylum was rejected at the time of application or not. According to the interviews, the large majority (estimated on average at 85%) are persons who are obliged to leave Germany/ NRW. This report, particularly section 4.1 will focus on this group only. In how far assisted return is prioritised by the implementing actors depends on a variety of factors, such as the institution and the individual actor in charge of the process and relations between return counsellor and ABH/ ZAB, if the counselling is conducted by actors outside of the latter institutions.

When asylum is rejected, applicants receive a letter from BAMF containing the rejection along with information on the time remaining until mandatory departure, their rights to appeal and an invitation to consult return counselling. There are two types of rejection: simple (*einfach*) and plainly unfounded (*offensichtlich unbegründet*). A simple rejection implies 30 days until mandatory departure and access to legal appeals with suspensive effect (*aufschiebende Wirkung*). A rejection decision based on the statement ‘plainly unfounded’ leaves only seven days until departure and if the applicant decides to appeal by using legal remedies, a suspensive effect has to be applied for through a temporary injunction (*Eilrechtsschutzantrag*, emergency judicial relief petition), also within one week (and can be denied).

In 2023, nearly 60 per cent (58.8 per cent) of negative asylum decisions issued by BAMF were appealed in court (bpb 2025), which means that upon receiving the rejection letter, many people prioritise mobilizing legal remedies over return counselling. Applications by people from so-called safe countries of origin are always rejected as plainly unfounded (or, in minimal numbers, accepted), thereby restricting the time and possibility for appeals significantly. When hardship commissions or petition committees discuss a case, this does not have a suspensive effect. Thus, after rejection – unless an appeal is filed that prolongs the residence authorisation (*Aufenthaltsgestattung*) for the time of the court proceedings - a decision against assisted return most likely leads to forced removal, if people do not leave or disappear by themselves. People who have once before received return assistance are generally excluded from REAG/GARP (some federal states have their own more flexible budgets, but NRW does not).

³⁵ Interviews indicate that authorities regularly remind (in the words of ABH-personnel) or threaten (in the words of an affected) designated returnees that assisted return is the better option for them because otherwise they would be subjected to Dublin transfers or forced removals to an origin/ third country. Interviews, 24 September 2024, 16 September 2024.

In the following, the two return migration infrastructures (RMIs) of assisted and forced returns are introduced following the pre-given typology of actors, modes of implementation ('doings') and materials and technologies, preceded by a quick clarification regarding the notion of 'actors' in this context. Our research found strong overlaps of both RMIs in operational practice, including responsible institutions, target groups and places. To demonstrate these interconnections, similarities and differences regarding the procedural steps, the authors present one flow map which gives an overview of both RMIs.

Given the heterogeneous landscape of actors who are part of the return migration infrastructures besides the affected (foreign nationals and persons with migration background involved as returnees), we distinguish between institutions and non-governmental actors for purposes of simplification. Even though institutions comprise mostly governmental authorities and offices, the plain dichotomy of governmental vs. non-governmental actors translated into institutions vs actors (as used by, e.g., Xiang and Lindquist 2014) does not reflect the here introduced differentiation entirely. Instead, the rough distinction between institutions (as sub-category of actors) and non-governmental actors is suggested because it can encompass a) liminal institutions at the interface of state and civil society which either consist of official (state/ government) representatives and civil society representatives (e.g. Forum Flughäfen in NRW) or are (co-)financed by the former (e.g., Flüchtlingsrat NRW) and all non-governmental return counselling bodies in NRW, and b) what could be called watchdog institutions built into the state's structures to allow for monitoring, appeal and reviews of state action (e.g. Hardship Commission and Petition Commission). Moreover, courts of different jurisdictions and court instances (chambers) are understood as institutions but as they are independent, they are not part of the state hierarchy. International organizations are likewise considered institutions, e.g. Frontex; in addition, embassies, consulates and their respective delegations are subsumed under institutions and ascribed institutional mandates. In distinction, actors here comprise civil society actors and organizations, including employees of institutions in their capacity as private citizens who might have and act along worldviews opposed to the dominant institutional perspective on forced or assisted returns. Moreover, profit-oriented private companies and service providers (e.g. facility management, medical services³⁶, security) are understood as non-governmental actors. Moreover, it is important to note that returns are but one of the diverse and partly conflicting tasks that many of the actors (and institutions) are dealing with. Within local-level foreigners offices, for example, forced removals are just one (according to interviews rather minor) field of action they are in charge of (besides asylum, assisted returns and other matters relating to foreigners' presence).

It is important to note that the comparative design of the Working Paper did not foresee a separate analysis of the role of the persons involved as returnees or deportees; this is why the authors did not conduct any interviews with this group. However, wherever possible, insights from secondary sources about – and in other interviews reported experiences with – the agency of individuals from this group, is factored into the below analysis (e.g. cf. the flow map between 4.1 and 4.2). This said, in the following, the RMI-category of 'actors' refers to the role and mandate of institutions, liminal institutions, and non-state actors.

³⁶ On the role of medical personnel in forced returns from Germany, see Deutscher Bundestag (2018, 2018a), Girth (2020).

4.1 Assisted return

This section focuses in a somewhat ideal-typical manner on the process of assisted return as it unfolds after the rejection of an asylum application until departure. It should be noted that according to an experienced return counsellor, only about 10 per cent of assisted return preparations follow an ideal-typical, linear pattern (Notes from event, March 2025), i.e., for 90 per cent disruptions, repetitions and drop-outs are common. Information about and the option for assisted return is provided before and during an asylum application process not only to incentivize the withdrawal or non-submission of the application but also because, after rejection, the time remaining until mandatory departure is very limited. Thus, the assisted return trajectories are more diverse than captured here, but most applicants have reportedly received a rejection of their asylum application prior to applying. Moreover, for assisted return, the types of actors and their relations differ hugely between the German states. Two remarks are essential for the contextualization of this section:

- Assisted return is meant to be offered to migrants when or before they become subject to a removal order. This is why the target group shows significant overlaps with the people who may be forcibly returned. For the subgroup of returnees looked at here, the actors and processes of status determination and contestation (courts, hardship commissions, petition committees, citizens) and civil society actors providing counselling and support during the asylum process are largely the same as presented in section 6 below.
- At the start of 2024, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) took over the management of REAG/GARP from IOM, which had been the implementing agency for more than 40 years. Therefore, the period of data collection is characterized by changes resulting from this transition, mainly with two effects: a) granting German state institutions more control over the process and regulation of assisted returns (e.g. determination of suspended countries) and b) at least temporarily, significant delays in the processing of applications and unavailability of certain services (such as airport assistance, payments of GARP money at airports, returns with medical assistance) over several months. The delays, in particular, increased the differences between the federal states, as some have their own allocated funds that could be used to fill some of the gaps (the return of persons with medical needs or at risk of forced removal, for example). NRW does not have its own return funds and return counselling providers were unable to provide many of the regular services in time. Reportedly, at least two persons were deported from NRW who had applied for assisted return.

Institutions and non-state actors:

The main actors in organizing assisted return in NRW – along with the migrants – are return counselling providers. Return counselling is provided both by municipal and central foreigners authorities (ABHs and ZABs, as institutions) and by a variety of non-state actors ranging from municipal-level representations of the large charities to local churches, specialised associations, NGOs and different units of the municipal administration such as social welfare offices. The total number of return counselling providers in NRW is bizarrely unclear: the website “returning from Germany” lists 422, of which 420 provide counselling and submit applications. IOM (which implements the website) stated in 2023 that in NRW, 262 return counselling providers are listed as application submitting bodies in the

REAG/GARP applications online portal (Lich et al. 2024).³⁷ In practice, it turns out that municipal bodies other than the ABHs listed in the online dataset do not play a substantial role in the counselling infrastructure.

Before 2020, the NRW government had funded the most decentralized non-governmental return counselling landscape in Germany through the state funding programme *Soziale Beratung für Geflüchtete*.³⁸ The declared aim was to provide independent counselling in each district and town. However, with successive cuts to this social counselling program – of which only one leg is return counselling – this system has become harder to maintain. Implementing organisations had to increase their own funds, but the workload and standards often exceed the means (“this turns us into ticket counters”) (Interview, 16 July 2024). The annual (and often rather late) extension of the state funding program in particular makes planning difficult. Personnel fluctuation is reportedly at 50 per cent per year, fragmentation of funds (0.25 positions for return counselling in some places) adds to the challenges, and funding for non-governmental counselling in the state-run accommodation facilities³⁹ was cut entirely as of early 2025. Generally, ZABs conduct counselling in central accommodation facilities (ZUEs); municipal ABHs receive people living in decentral accommodation. Non-governmental providers used to work in both settings until 2024 but with increasingly limited presence in the ZUEs. The division of labour between the regulative and the not explicitly regulative bodies varies from municipality to municipality and ZUE to ZUE. It is largely determined by respective capacities (measured in terms of personnel, specialization, and eligibility to act as application submitting body) and by mutual trust. There is quite a divide between ABH/ ZAB counsellors and non-state providers in the sense that training, networking, information events and channels (online and offline), and to some extent, their understandings of the goal and purpose of their work are different. One respondent declared that “they [ABH/ZABs] are the ones with the measures to terminate residence” (Interview, 16 July 2024) thereby underlining his/ her perspective that non-state return counselling is more independent and trustworthy.⁴⁰ At the same time, for the non-state providers, relations with the responsible ABH/ ZAB for their mentees (designated returnees in counselling contexts are called ‘clients’) are key and described as ‘cooperation in quotation marks’ or ‘modus vivendi rather than collaboration’ (same interview); however, with significant differences between the localities and actors.

There are few providers of return/ reintegration preparation training that people can be referred to (focusing mainly on business and practical skills), however, after an asylum rejection, the remaining time is often too limited for that. For the logistical return preparations, the return counsellor may need to request services, documents or information

³⁷ In comparison, only 90 counselling organizations were registered in the state of Lower Saxony in 2023 (Lich et al. 2024).

³⁸ Unlike in some of the other federal states, funding for return counselling in NRW comes through this state funding program for social counselling for refugees and to some extent from the implementing organisations themselves; almost no other donors, municipal funds or other sources are involved.

³⁹ These so-called *Landeseinrichtungen* include initial reception centers and central accommodation facilities (ZUEs); for the sake of simplicity, we will continue to speak of ZUEs, which are much larger in number and more relevant for facilitated returns after asylum rejection.

⁴⁰ Mixed meetings take place in the context of the ZUR Working Group, at some Integplan trainings and conferences and are sometimes initiated, often by the civil society side, to increase mutual understanding.

from other actors and institutions. BAMF (and in case of EURP BAMF and Frontex) need to process the applications. Embassies/ consulates, doctors or psychologists as well as (where it applies) youth offices (*Jugendamt*) may be involved and meet with the client directly. For many other processes, the counsellor can receive a power of attorney (*Vollmacht*) from the client. Non-governmental counsellors need to reach out to the responsible ABH/ ZAB, in ZUEs also to the district government (*Bezirksregierung*) and management of the ZUE [*Einrichtungsleitung*] regarding documents of the potential returnee, information exchange and – crucially – prevention of forced removal.

In case of a positive decision on the REAG/GARP application, BAMF issues a flight date and books the tickets through the Frontex-owned platform FAR (Frontex Application for Return) or a private service provider. For returnees who are classified as vulnerable, especially due to medical conditions, service providers who are either sub-contracted by the REAG/GARP managing organization (BAMF) or commissioned individually on a case-by-case basis can arrange door-to-door transportation including medical assistance, trained escorts and documents such as fit to fly certificates. Other subcontracted service providers, for example Everest travel (Skylink Holding), organise the handover of cash assistance at the airport – which in NRW is only possible at Düsseldorf airport. Until the end of 2023, airport assistance was bookable together with REAG/GARP, for example for people needing help due to illiteracy. The final decision on who can board an aircraft lies with the airline and passengers can be rejected by the airline personnel regardless of all preparations (e.g. fit to fly), for example based on health or security risks. For this reason, medically trained personnel appointed or subcontracted by the airlines assess forms and reports on the health of a returnee in parallel with the REAG/GARP application process, when this is relevant, to determine if and under what conditions the person can be taken on board. The permission to fly can be revoked by the pilot even after boarding. Federal police are usually present at the airport or point of departure to hand out the passports and to receive the border crossing certificates, which can alternatively be handed to the respective German embassy in the country of origin upon return. Once this proof of departure has been provided, BAMF Data or the responsible ABH/ ZAB will change the entry in the central foreigner's registry accordingly.

Doings:

The main part of 'doings' is a range of activities subsumed under the notion of 'return counselling', which commonly takes place over one or several counselling sessions and other forms of information exchange. Some organisations, for example the Red Cross, do not use the term return counselling and provide "Ausreise- und Perspektivberatung" (departure and prospects counselling) instead. Departure is seen as more appropriate, since the REAG/GARP also supports moving to a third country, provided the applicant can legally enter there. Perhaps more importantly, the choice of terminology also reflects the identity of the organisation providing counselling as either implementing return or assisting in the development of future prospects (which, if legally possible, could also be found in Germany). Practitioners report that beyond the terminology and identity, a strict avoidance of a regulative 'habitus' (for example no uniforms, no security) enhances trust-building and increases demand for assisted return. The counselling starts by providing general information about the implications of the migrants' legal status, the option of assisted return and assessment of legal

alternatives to return.⁴¹ If the person agrees to assisted return, the state of travel documents, needs and eligibility for assistance, potential vulnerabilities and prioritization criteria are assessed and applications for assistance submitted. As this takes time, non-governmental providers must constantly negotiate to delay or prevent forced removal and also regularly update and renew some of the forms included in the application. For this, as well as the issuance of relevant documents and information for the application and the border crossing certificate, they depend on the respective ABH/ ZAB. ABHs/ ZABs, in turn, have the file of the applicant and all personal documents in-house. ZABs can even print laissez-passer documents for certain countries of origin. In a next step, concrete return preparations may require renewing passports or organizing replacement documents, arranging for birth and school certificates to be translated, fit to fly and perhaps other vaccination and health certificates to be issued. A connection with reintegration advisors in the country of return (possibly through an online meeting) may also be established. Post-return conditions and needs regarding accommodation, schooling, medical needs, access to the job market, and security need to be clarified and prepared for. If relevant information about the post-return conditions is unknown or uncertain, many of the return counselling bodies can submit a request for information with ZIRF⁴². Some return counsellors also offer support with transportation to the airport. Post-return contacts and follow-ups occur occasionally and largely depend on the commitment of the individual return counsellor; also monitoring and evaluation is not an in-built part of the assistance.

Due to the diversity of providers, counselling varies from brief explanations on assisted return and implications of its refusal (forced removal) to trust- and need-based advice on how to develop a future perspective within the given legal framework. Different guidelines and operational frameworks have been developed to guide counselling, some only applying to charities, others to all providers, but all not binding.⁴³ While counsellors in non-state organizations frame their work more in terms of helping to develop a perspective and not only to smoothen return, their capacity to achieve this is constrained by limited funding,⁴⁴ short-term contracts and high fluctuation of staff, making the maintenance of high standards and trustful relations a continuous challenge.

Materials and technologies:

There is no law that regulates assisted return in Germany (European Migration Network 2007). The practice is based on a political consensus that assisted return should be prioritized

⁴¹ If legal alternatives or at least options are found, the person may be referred to asylum counselling.

⁴² ZIRF stands for *Zentralstelle für Informationsvermittlung zur Rückkehrförderung* (Central office for the provision of information on return assistance) and is a chargeable research service operated by IOM (~400 Euros per request).

⁴³ Guidelines aiming to set minimal standards and to an extent harmonize approaches across Germany are known to 72-75 per cent of return counsellors according to a recent survey (Lich et al. 2024), while 50 per cent of survey participants have their own organization-specific concepts. For the non-governmental providers, training in the residence and the asylum acts is only obligatory for counsellors without a degree in social work, social pedagogy or an equivalent, but participation in training and regularly organized networking and exchange activities is encouraged.

⁴⁴ For NRW (and as of 2024), the state budget foresees 50 full-time equivalents which are distributed across 81 positions and the budget as well as the contracts are renewed on an annual basis.

over forced removal for being more cost-effective, humane and generally preferred (Schneider and Kreienbrink 2010). REAG/GARP funds come from the EU's Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) with co-funding from BAMF and the German federal states. Funding for the non-state return counsellors in NRW comes almost exclusively from the state budget for non-state counselling of refugees (funding programme *Soziale Beratung von Geflüchteten*) managed by the NRW Ministry for Children, Youth, Family, Equality, Refugees and Integration (MKJFGFI).⁴⁵ Therefore, anonymized information on the non-state counselling sessions is entered into an online-based controlling program called HaFöC, which is overseen by the NRW Audit Office (*Landesrechnungshof*). The ZABs are also funded by the MKJFGFI⁴⁶, however channelled through the respective municipalities, and, as return is the responsibility of the states, the return counsellors in municipal ABHs are co-funded by the NRW state and the municipality. ZABs/ ABHs have their own internal electronical databases including the files of designated returnees, where they can enter information, for example on assisted return, directly.

During the concrete process of preparing for assisted return, the main technologies are forms and online databases. At the start of the counselling process, the applicant needs to sign the declaration on assisted return. If the return counsellor is not from the ABH/ZAB, another form releases the latter of its confidentiality to allow for coordination. Eligibility for REAG/GARP assistance has to be proven through an affidavit of indigence (*Mittellosigkeitsbescheinigung*), not older than three months at the time of decision, and proof of medical needs and other vulnerabilities besides a photocopy of the passport also needs to be submitted along with the application.

Applications for REAG/GARP are to be submitted through the online application module (OAM), which is technically still operated by IOM.⁴⁷ Information exchange between return counsellors and BAMF is mainly channelled through the chat function of the OAM. Since 2024, the OAM has been connected with the Central Registry of Foreigners (Ausländerzentralregister, AZR), thus the respective AZR number is required to submit the application (only the governmental providers can directly access the AZR). An application for EURP is to be submitted through another online platform known as Reintegration Assistance Tool, RIAT 2.0⁴⁸, which requires 2-factor authentication, which means that the body that submits the application needs to own a business cell phone. For the EURP service provider in the origin country to prepare the post-arrival package, the return counsellor must upload the flight dates provided by BAMF into RIAT at least five days prior to departure. For the non-state return counsellors in NRW, there is an NRW-specific intranet with relevant news, discussion fora, tools, advice, events and basic documents. ABHs receive updates and

⁴⁵ The district government of Arnsberg supports the MKJFGFI in some aspects of the operationalization of the funding guidelines as subordinate authority (*nachgeordnete Behörde*), which also acts as the supervisory authority over the ZABs on behalf of the MKJFGFI.

⁴⁶ Return counselling is not among the legal obligations assigned to them through the ZustAVO, so it depends on the initiative and negotiations of the staff, whether a ZAB has personnel exclusively for return counselling or whether this is done in the context of 'return management'. Only Essen and Bielefeld seem to have specifically assigned return counsellors.

⁴⁷ Apparently, not all ZUEs grant internet access to return counsellors, so they may have to do the data management once they are back at their desk.

⁴⁸ Since Frontex has taken it over from ERRIN. See <https://reintegrationfacility.eu/home/riat/>

information from the responsible NRW ministry through a news ticker located on their intranet, but there is little content specifically on return counselling.

If the application for REAG/GARP is accepted, BAMF will issue the approval notification, which contains the ticket booking number. Passports are usually kept by the ABH/ZAB until departure, so non-governmental providers have to apply for them to be handed over. Cash assistance (if applicable) is handed over to the returnees at the airport by a service provider or – if no service provider is available – advanced by the return counselling organization.

Implementation gaps: Legislative sleepiness, overregulation and burden shifting

The failure to come to a binding regulation (not to mention a legal basis) for the provision of return counselling (regarding e.g. the qualification of staff, common standards of the process, implications for forced removals, conditions for financing) has led to the emergence of rather divergent approaches, and discrepancies regarding the funding requirements and possibilities between the federal states and between as well as within state- and non-state providers. In NRW, the transition from IOM to BAMF and implementing agency of REAG/GARP has exacerbated an imbalance between state and non-state providers, as non-state providers were much less able to fill gaps or bridge delays that emerged during the first half of 2024 in the applications processing at the federal level.

Initiatives for a stronger standardization of return counselling are met with some level of resistance by some of the more ambitious actors, mainly because they perceive it as lowering the ethical standards, that they themselves apply. Where regulation has emerged, for example regarding the requirements for assisted return of persons with medical needs (so called MEDA cases), these are perceived as detached from practical realities and largely inhibiting by counsellors.⁴⁹ However, given that return counselling and assisted return hold a lot of potential to implement returns at a lower financial and human cost and less risk of disruptions compared with forced removals, the overall neglect by policy makers at the federal level is rather surprising. Stakeholders express that while their work is in line with policy priorities and crucial towards their fulfilment, it takes place under straining conditions and political disregard. Especially those with long-standing expertise on the topic and direct contact with the ‘clients’ feel that their perspectives are under-reflected in political decision-making.

Box: RMI flow map overlaps in assisted return and forced removal

The RMI flow map highlights the RMI-overlaps between assisted return and forced removal; for this purpose, it has been simplified (technologies are not featured). We find huge coherence regarding the institutions involved, the implementation steps they follow, the usage of technology, as well as the sources of funding. Both return pathways coexist to some degree but a dropout of designated returnees from the assisted return path subjects them legally to the forced removal path. Exposed to the foreseeable removal procedure they adapt and submit given the threat of coercive means or obstruct the process by disappearing or open resistance at any of the marked instances in the removal process.

⁴⁹ These were introduced by IOM after specific funding under REAG/GARP was made available for these cases in 2016. If and in how far BAMF taking over will make a difference in this regard could not be determined, as the data collection took place too early for this.

Major differences in both forced return pathways (assisted return and forced removal) comprise

- the independence of the counsellor from institutions or departments (within the same institution) that deal with forced removals is crucial for providing sincere advice, gaining the trust of 'clients' and helping in weighing the different options designated returnees have
- a rather transparent process in assisted return in close cooperation with the designated returnee/s (cooperation in identity clarification, active involvement in return preparation)
- the legalistic foundation forced return procedures can rely on (even if ambivalent) vs. the absence of any legal foundation for return counselling in the framework of assisted returns.

Common to both governmental and non-governmental implementers is that

- MGKJFI is the superior foreigners authority and allocates the budget, thus the aspiration to fulfill the integration ambition and the aspiration to implement a return offensive at the same time is located outside the Ministry of the Interior as regulative authority
- their institutions work at capacity limit, while the provided resources are not sufficient to live up to their own (normative) standards concerning effectiveness and ethics
- strong overlaps exist regarding the personnel and equipment used for assisted returns vs. forced removals (especially within the ABHs and ZABs).

Unclear roles and processes:

- Frontex plays a central role for implementers – both in organization and funding of forced returns. While this reduces the costs of the federal state (escorts, aircrafts, medical service provider, translators), the costs Germany contributes to the Frontex budget remain unclear.
- IOM is involved in various procedures linked to forced returns; however, IOM's detailed involvement and impact remain to be clarified.

Figure 5: RMI flow map NRW/ Germany

Source: authors' elaboration

4.2 Forced removals

The implementation of forced removals – i.e. after clarification that there are no internal or external legal obstacles to return – concerns different groups of persons: (1) those who are obligated to leave Germany after a rejected asylum application but did not agree to assisted return; (2) those whose residence permit is no longer valid according to Section 50 of the Residence Act⁵⁰; (3) those who have no residence permit or other (temporary) right to stay, e.g. persons without valid documents picked up in public spaces during police controls; (4) whose removal is enforced on grounds of a threat to public security (Articles 58, 58a and 59 Residence Act, AufenthG) and (5) those who have been expelled according to Article 54 AufenthG.⁵¹ According to Rose and Schießl (2025, 211), just over half of those who are formally ‘obligated to leave’ Germany are rejected asylum seekers (58 per cent). The rest are a very heterogeneous group, including overstaying tourists, international students who no longer fulfil the criteria for a residence permit, skilled workers who became unemployed and therefore lost their residence permit, or young people who were born with a tolerated stay permit because their family did not have a residence permit.⁵²

Institutions and non-state actors:

The field of actors is very diversified and fragmented due to the high number of institutions and actors involved (for an overview of the actors only see Figure 6 - in 5.1 below). Key points are:

- As local governments are responsible for the enforcement of returns, the specific situation in NRW, in contrast to other states⁵³, is that NRW kept the responsibility for returns strictly decentralized, i.e., it lies with the 81 ABHs that exist at the local government level in municipalities and counties (sub-districts). Over time, the state established five ZABs to support the ABHs; however, the ZABs are add-ons and not part of the administrative hierarchy. Due to German local government semi-autonomy, local level procedures are decided by the respective local administration and depend on the personnel and resource capacity of the ABHs and their (social and geographical) proximity to one of the newly introduced five ZABs supervised by the respective district governments (*Bezirksregierungen*). ABHs and ZABs interact to prepare forced returns, and many also jointly conduct the actual enforcement (pick-up and transfer to airport or land border).
- At the third tier of government, ABHs oversee returns and integration at the same time since they have become organizationally and administratively part of the NRW

⁵⁰ This regulation also applies to those whose right of residence has expired under special agreements such as the right of residence under the EEC-Turkey Association Agreement (Article 50, section 1 AufenthG).

⁵¹ Article 54 Residence Act (AufenthG) regulates the so-called interest in removal according to Art. 53 AufenthG that defines the circumstances and criteria under which a foreigner can be expelled from Germany: These comprise a threat to public safety and order, membership of terrorist organisations, or a serious criminal offence.

⁵² Besides, there are many other constellations in which a right of residence can be lost or denied in Germany, e.g. after re-entry despite an existing re-entry ban or in cases when an EU citizen has lost the right to freedom of movement. The subsequent sections focus on groups 1 and 2 (as discussed in interviews).

⁵³ The local jurisdiction (roles and mandates) of the foreigners authorities is determined by state laws (e.g. Ordinance on Responsibilities in Aliens Matters [Verordnung über Zuständigkeiten im Ausländerwesen, ZustAVO]) and complemented by regulations in the Police Laws of the states.

ministry dealing with both ‘return’ and integration since 2017 (then the Ministry for Children, Youth, Family, Equality, Displacement and Integration (MKJFGFI)). Before, return enforcement’s regulative mandate (*Ordnungspolitik*) had been subordinated to the state Ministry of the Interior; the merger served as political signal in favor of an integration and stay perspective for migrants. Mainly discretion and the usage of discretionary space by the leadership of the ABH concerned, and individual staff members in the different positions on all levels of the administrative hierarchy, determine how the pertinent tension between integration and return objectives is being dealt with, i.e., whether the goal conflict in terms of practices and outcomes yields integrationist or isolationist policy behaviour.

- The presence of state (NRW) police is only requested when the person to be removed is expected to pose a risk of violence and danger to the removal process; in exceptional cases, the Police Special Unit (SEK) is asked to assist. Otherwise – this is unique for NRW among the German states – state police are not involved.
- Federal Police has a role as border guard and, at the airport, they are also partly seconded to Frontex. Whereas Frontex is often in charge of organizing (Frontex return division), administering and accompanying (Frontex escorts and monitors) collective charters among several EU member states, national charters are accompanied by Federal Police personnel.
- Several types of private, profit-seeking service providers have a role in different stages of the forced return process, e.g. as operators of accommodation facilities, security service providers⁵⁴, medical services providers, translators, locksmiths etc. Embassies, consulates and delegations from countries of origin are involved in the beginning and end of the removal (organisation and realisation).
- Other non-state and civil society actors that scrutinize forced returns or how they are conducted comprise church communities, different types of welfare organizations, activists, lawyers and advocacy organizations, such as the NRW Refugee Council and municipal refugee councils and pro- integration/ migrant-commissions, etc.
- Notably, state institutions have initiated and are funding interface institutions such as the Hardship Commission or the Petitions Committee that might offer pathways to ultimately avoid forced returns on a single-case basis.

‘Doings’:

Even though the forced return infrastructure is designed in a linear model, the reality foresees ruptures (church asylum, citizen asylum, active resistance by the returnee at different junctures in the process of implementation), U-turns (successful petitioning, recognition of hardship case) and loops (where returned people re-enter Germany and apply for asylum or enter on regular employment visa).

The forced return administrative process is split into two phases: the preparation and actual enforcement of removal. Whereas preparation involves identity clarification and logistical preparations including the issuance of passport replacement papers, flight booking, transport organisation as well as medical checks, the enforcement comprises the pick-up from the

⁵⁴ For a discussion on the powers of private security companies in accommodation facilities and necessary limitations, see Engler 2019.

shelter (whether central or municipal accommodation, private residence, hospital, ABH, detention facility), the transfer to the airport, handover to the Federal Police there and a clearance process that again might include a medical check-up up, until boarding. Federal Police and/ or Frontex accompany single and collective charter flights (Federal Police also on scheduled flights where necessary), and these also hand the removed person over to the responsible authorities in the destination location. At all stages of this process, people may resist or a legal emergency appeal, the deterioration of the health condition of the person subjected to removal, the cancellation of a flight by the airline, violent resistance and (threat of) self-harm of the returnee, an activists' protest blocking the road to their airport or at the runway, granting of church or citizen asylum, etc. can cause termination of the process.

Materials and Technologies:

Besides the different places (cf. Table 3 in section 5.3) that represent the sites of the 'doings' (residences, airport, ABH, places of pick-up) (cf. Figure 5), a range of tangible materials are used in the preparation and enforcement process, such as documents (medical certificates, passport replacement papers, protective briefs, emergency appeals, dossiers) but also the protective and operational equipment used by ABHs' staff (helmets, vests, shackles, etc.). Technologies cover data bases (EuroDAC, Central Foreigners Registry [AZR], SYS3.0, IRMA) and technical procedures (OSINT, reading data storage devices).

The following in-depth case study examines the interplay of these institutions and actors, their roles and relations, the doings and procedures, and the materials and technologies to provide deeper insights about the forced return migration infrastructure from NRW/ Germany.

5. Case study: Forced Removal Migration Infrastructure in NRW, Germany

Zooming in from a narrow perspective, the forced RMI-case study is connected to the place where the enforcing actors pick up the returnee. This can be the central accommodation facility, a communal accommodation facility or a private place of residence of the designated returnee, church premises or the premises of the ABHs and detention facilities. In the wider sense of the infrastructure approach, the case study includes the preparatory activities for the forced removal, besides the enforcement as such (cf. flow map/ Figure 5 in Ch. 5).

5.1 Actors involved in the forced removal infrastructure and their role/intention/mandate

a) Institutional roles and mandates in forced return migration infrastructure

State administration: The German federal system produces a complex interplay of multi-level authorities and offices, whereas the primary federal authority – the Federal Ministry of the Interior – is the executive and in charge of crafting new and adapting existing laws related to (forced) returns (Residence Act and Asylum Act) in line with European legislation. The Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF), a higher federal authority, acts as the operational arm of the BMI. It is a multi-tiered authority with branch offices (*Außenstellen*) in

the major migrant reception facilities and other relevant administrative divisions.⁵⁵ The BAMF is the agency responsible for deciding on applications for protection (asylum) and for legal measures and decisions concerning aliens (§5.1 AsylG). Within this remit, the BAMF administers the entire asylum process before deciding on a protection status or rejection (including Dublin cases). Concerning returns, the BAMF is in charge of clarifying whether external obstacles prevent the enforcement of an obligation to leave.⁵⁶

At NRW-state level, the Ministry for Children, Youth, Family, Equality, Displacement and Integration (MKJFGFI) acts as the supreme foreigners authority since 2017⁵⁷, when this mandate was taken from the state Ministry of the Interior in a move to signal a more stay-oriented and less removal-focused approach in the implementation of national legal provisions. The MKJFGFI has additional power to introduce NRW-specific legal provisions (*Erlasse*) that are binding for its sub-authorities. In contrast, the implementation of national and state legal provisions lies with the local-level ABHs, which thus have merely an executive mandate. In-between the local and state level, five district governments (*Bezirksregierungen*: Münster, Düsseldorf, Arnsberg, Detmold, Köln) constitute the so-called higher ABHs. Subordinated to them in the regular hierarchy are intermediate-level sub-district administrations, which act as the immediate superiors to local-level ABHs – in rural areas the sub-district council (*Kreistag*) with an administration (*Landratsamt*) headed by a county commissioner (*Landrat*) and in municipalities city councils headed by a mayor.

As introduced above, the municipal and sub-district ABHs are responsible for returns from NRW; in addition, five central foreigners authorities (ZABs) have been successively established (one in each government district) that are not superior to the local ones and not related to the intermediate level but are supposed to provide centralized support to local ABHs in the preparation and enforcement of deportations. Regional Return Coordination Offices (*Regionale Rückkehrkoordinationsstellen*, RKK) – one subordinated to each district government – were established as parallel institutions by the MKJFGFI in 2017 to support assisted returns and accelerate forced returns of foreigners who committed criminal offences and with deviant social behaviour from the municipalities and the state reception facilities in

⁵⁵ According to §5.3 AsylG (German Asylum Act), the opening of a BAMF branch office is mandatory where a local reception facility accommodates more than 1,000 persons but can also be established—in coordination with the states—in locations with lower numbers and outside of reception centres. In 2023, there were 60 local branch offices of the BAMF. See the Glossary in the Annex for further distinctions in the naming of BAMF branch offices; distinction is made between arrival centres, AnKER centres and decision-making centres. This is partly due to the current government's rejection of the AnKER centre concept introduced by the previous government (2017–21) in 2018. The main idea, however, of bundling the competencies of all relevant agencies for the asylum process in one place, remains, albeit reformulated as 'integrated refugee management' (BAMF 2018).

⁵⁶ According to a recent Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) ruling, the non-enforcement of forced removal orders under §34a AsylG has to be examined by BAMF alone, which has consequences for the lawfulness of the removal threat. Previously, the clarification of possible grounds for non-enforceability of forced removal was divided between BAMF for the applicability of national removal bans and the Foreigners Authority for the so-called other reasons for non-enforcement (*Vollstreckungshindernisse*). This has led to unlawful removal threats for persons with family ties where the best interests of the child have to be taken into account. Cf. CJEU ruling of 15 February 2023, C-484/22: Revocation of the return decision if family ties and the best interest of the children/minor asylum seekers are violated.

⁵⁷ In the previous NRW legislative period (2017-22), the Ministry's title and mandate was narrower: NRW State Ministry for Children, Family, Refugees and Integration (Ministerium für Kinder, Familie, Flüchtlinge und Integration des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen, MKFFI).

the respective administrative district (Regierungsbezirk). This reportedly involves case management procedures with collaborating authorities (cf. section 5.3).

Police: Given the existence of the ZABs and the responsibility of local ABHs for the enforcement of forced removals, the state police are only involved to assist in pick-up and transfers to the airport or state border if the returnee is categorized as ‘dangerous’. In exceptional cases, the federal Special Forces Police (*Sondereinsatzkommando* [SEK]) has been involved in the ‘pick-up’ of designated returnees, e.g., when people are either assessed as particularly dangerous or to panic in the face of imminent deportation and threaten to harm themselves, but also when breaking church asylum or in complex situations at central accommodation facilities when authorities expected collective resistance and/ or violence.⁵⁸ Upon arrival at the departure airport, the Federal Police – which is Germany’s border guard authority – takes over and handles the departure. Depending on the arrangements (unaccompanied return vs accompanied return and responsibility of escort either with Federal Police, Frontex, security personnel of airline, or security personnel of third/ destination states), Federal Police officers either only accompany the ground handling until handover to other security personnel in cases of accompanied returns on board of the aircraft, or Federal Police designated personnel (*Personenbegleiter Luft*, PBL, cf. 5.3 below) accompany the returnees during the entire return flight to oversee also handover to the respective authorities in the destination country.⁵⁹

Frontex: Frontex support and staff is mostly involved in preparing and enforcing forced removals as the counterpart to the ZAB. The Frontex return division’s flight booking system is used to organize seats/ tickets to certain destinations in collective charters departing from airports Germany-wide and including neighbouring EU countries. Frontex staff supervises (escort leaders) and accompanies (escorts, monitors) flights. If necessary, Frontex also organizes medical staff at airports and/ or to accompany the flights. The deployment of Frontex personnel is detailed in several handbooks, codes and guidelines.

Embassies/ consulates and their respective country delegations: Diplomatic representations of origin countries of potential returnees are involved in the preparation of forced returns. They are contacted by local and central foreigners offices – sometimes also by national-level institutions like the BAMF – for identity clarification of persons who are found to be obliged to return. As a rule, identity clarification is the precondition for the issuance of identity papers (passports, laissez passer, etc.). Diplomatic missions either accept returnees based on appointments or authorities organize collective presentations of potential countrymen and -women at the premises of their offices or the diplomatic representations (so-called embassy hearings). Federal-level authorities can also invite country delegations from

⁵⁸ To mention but two of several cases documented by Rose and Schießl (2024), SEK was present at the pick-up of a Yazidi family with several children in Gelsenkirchen to enforce their return to Armenia in August 2022; in December 2022 the Dublin pick-up of an Iraqi man who had threatened to self-harm himself in a previous pick-up attempt by the municipality of Ippenbüren was handled by an SEK-unit.

⁵⁹ A guideline for Federal Police’s mandate and handling of returns of foreign nationals by air – called *Best Rück Luft*, cf. Glossary in the Annex – was compiled and issued for internal usage only in 2016 (Bundespolizei 2016). It became publicly accessible in 2019 after an inquiry at the platform “FragDenStaat” based on the Freedom of Information Act, which grants every person an unconditional legal right to access official information from federal authorities.

countries of origin for such identity clarification hearings. The interest and cooperation of different origin countries in these processes vary.

b) Non-governmental actors' roles and mandates

Civil society organizations: Organized civil society has a strong human rights orientation and comprises different church actors (of various congregations), secular advocacy organizations that work at the federal and the state and municipal level (Committee for Basic Rights and Democracy, ai, Pro Asyl), migrant self-organisations and other NGOs such as Rom e.V. Cologne. Private individuals engage as volunteers in the said organizations but also in municipal/ local integration councils and associations (e.g. "Help for people in deportation detention Büren e.V."). In their self-understanding, they scrutinize how forced removals are enforced; some oppose forced returns outright. Their focus is mostly on single cases of affected/ returnees.

Other non-governmental actors: Various refugee councils at the municipal level, welfare organisations (Caritas NRW, AWO, Diakonie Rheinland-Westfalen-Lippe) and their representatives/ social workers in various places (central and municipal accommodation facilities, detention facility), as well as counselling services (psychosocial centres and counselling offices for victims of human trafficking), offer advice and assistance for potential forced returnees, legal literacy and possibly options to avoid removal. Moreover, welfare organisations and refugee councils are engaged in advocacy at the national level and attempt to influence legislative processes from a human rights perspective. National watchdog organizations like the National Agency for the Prevention of Torture (Nationale Stelle zur Verhütung von Folter) and the German Institute for Human Rights (Deutsches Institut für Menschenrechte) have a role in highlighting irregularities, abuse and deficits in enforcement processes and can provide guidance through their national clout, even though their monitoring activities provide only a snapshot of insights about forced removal procedures based on one-off visits at only long intervals.

Private companies/ service providers: Hired by government institutions, profit-oriented private companies and service providers (e.g. facility management in accommodation facilities, medical service providers called for health checks and present at pick-up, transfer and during flights, security guards in ABHs, detention and accommodation facilities), as a rule, play a facilitating role in the forced return migration infrastructure.

Other non-state actors: Lawyers, pilots and flight attendants can play an ambiguous role in the forced return enforcement process. Depending on their capabilities, their assessment of the situation and mindset, they can either facilitate or prevent forced removals in particular cases. (Civil society) activists practice resistance in private or as a collective, e.g., by offering shelter ('citizen asylum') to persons designated for or at risk of forced removal or by protesting against forced removal charter flights through collective action (demonstrations and roadblocks), e.g., on motorways leading to airports or directly on the runways.

c) Role and mandate of interface/ liminal institutions

Interfaces initiated by and organizationally associated with the state of NRW: As a state parliamentary committee, the petitions committee (*Petitionsausschuss*)⁶⁰ can review state authorities' decisions on forced removals – mainly concerning the presence of so-called internal obstacles to forced removal (*inlandsbezogene Abschiebehindernisse*). Therefore, it can organize case hearings and, on the basis of special rights giving it access to all authorities and administrations under state control, it can inspect files, request information and order on-site visits to check and, if necessary, propose the correction of administrative (not a court's) decisions within the purview of existing legal possibilities (Residence Act). In particular, it can encourage the responsible ABH, including the BAMF, to reconsider a case within the scope of its discretionary powers and to recommend measures.⁶¹ The hardship commission (*Härtefallkommission*)⁶², which goes beyond such a mandate, can be called upon by those who do not have a right of residence under the Residence Act but for whom urgent humanitarian or urgent personal reasons apply as a basis for continued residence and who thus request the creation of a new legal basis to avoid forced removal. Therefore, the petitions committee refers some cases to the hardship commission. However, the referral in both institutions does not have suspensive effects, and both can only recommend or (legally more strongly) request that the local ABH responsible for the individual case/s revise its decision within its own discretionary space and offer a perspective to stay.⁶³ Petitions referring to Art. 25a and 25a Residence Act (AufenthG) seeking residence in cases of well-integrated juveniles and young adults on the one hand and of permanent integration on the other are regularly successful. The committee's investigation often finds options the ABH could additionally consider (missing documents such as a submitted payslip, a more positive language assessment, etc.) and recommends corresponding case revisions (interview, 12 November 2024). The ABHs react differently, and there have been cases where they have moved ahead with a forced removal, even though a case was either being reviewed by the petition committee or the hardship

⁶⁰ A petitions committee in Germany is a parliamentary committee or a committee in local representative bodies, such as the Bundestag, state parliament or local council, which deals with petitions from citizens who feel they have been treated unfairly by a public authority or state body. While it is not absolutely necessary for a parliament to set up a petitions committee to deal with petitions, the petitions committee of the NRW state parliament has a long history and enjoys the most extensive competencies among all state petition committees, since Article 41a in the state constitution significantly expanded the rights of the petitions committee in April 1969. This was the consequence of the so-called Klingelpütz affair, a scandal about abuse in a Cologne prison, which parliament was unable to investigate sufficiently as it did not have access to the prison. Since then, the petitions committee has had similar rights to a committee of enquiry. Importantly, the prevention of forced removals is only a small aspect of the work of the petition committee (cf. <https://www.landtag.nrw.de/home/petitionen/der-petitionsausschuss.html>; Interview, 12 November 2024).

⁶¹ For a consideration of a 'case' in the petitions committee, persons threatened with forced removal must present their case (initiative-driven). Recommendations made by the petitions committee have no legally binding effect but are still frequently followed. Submitting a petition to the committee does not guarantee that the forced removal will be suspended while a solution is found, but it is often handled this way (Flüchtlingsrat NRW 2023, p. 31).

⁶² Set up by the state government based on the Hardship Commission Regulation of 2005, it includes ten members from the Ministry, local ABHs, churches, civil society and medics. Decisions to formulate hardship requests (*Härtefallersuchen*) are solely based on file/ written records. Dublin cases are not eligible. The hardship commission does not publish an annual report about its performance and effectiveness.

⁶³ Cf. Voigt (2016) for a critical reflection of the construct of 'stay perspective' (*Bleibeperspektive*) arguing that contrary to what is conveyed in the public debate, it entails the denial of participation opportunities for certain groups of people and thus endangers if not prevents the achievement of legal and permanent residence.

commission.⁶⁴ A third interface body in this category is the *Advisory Board Deportation Detention (Beirat Abschiebungshaft)*. Established in 2015 with the State Law on the Execution of Deportation Detention in NRW (§ 33 Fn 2 Abschiebungshaftvollzugsgesetz Nordrhein-Westfalen, AHaftVollzG NRW), the Advisory Board Deportation Detention is directly subordinated to the MKJFGFI and tasked to monitor the conditions and care for detainees awaiting forced removal and see how these can be improved.⁶⁵

Interfaces (co)financed by MKJFGFI: In an interesting constellation, there are several interface bodies that are not institutionalized or established by law but that also fulfil the role of advising the MKJFGFI and other institutions on human rights violations and due diligence during forced removal procedures. First, the Forum Flughäfen in NRW (FFiNW) was established in 2020 as a stakeholder exchange forum to regularly discuss issues related to forced removals at NRW airports. Its members include representatives of the MKJFGFI, welfare and civil society organisations, the responsible police directorates at the airports in Düsseldorf⁶⁶ and Bonn/ Cologne, as well as the forced removal observation (*Abschiebungsbeobachtung*) of the Diakonie RWL; the latter body has an advisory role and authors an annual report informing the public about different aspects relating to forced removals from NRW airports. Second, the *Refugee Council NRW* (Flüchtlingsrat NRW) uses lobbying, information work and public relations to advocate for mainly people with a precarious residence status whose asylum application has been rejected or whose residence permit has been withdrawn. As a publicly funded human rights organization (an association under private law), it receives partial funding from the MKJFGFI but acts independently.

Courts: The first instance administrative courts (*Verwaltungsgerichte*) play a key role in reviewing BAMF rejection decisions and can offer legal remedies.⁶⁷ Detention decisions are

⁶⁴ According to Graebisch and Borstel (2021, p. 90), hardship commission applications are only permissible before the initiation of measures for forced removal (to terminate the stay).

⁶⁵ The board members are appointed by the ministry and include members of all parliamentary factions, representatives of civil society organisations, welfare associations and the NRW refugee council. According to the law, detainees have the right to contact the advisory board directly to invite advocacy on their behalf.

⁶⁶ Düsseldorf airport has the second-highest number of forced removal flights in Germany, after Frankfurt. Cf. Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 97.

⁶⁷ For details on the first to third instances of Administrative Courts and their role, see section 5.9 on Procedural Safeguards in Mielke et al. 2024, p. 33f. Within the scope of research for this *Working Paper*, the role of courts and judges could not be investigated in depth. However, it is noteworthy, that their role is increasingly debated ambiguously. On the one hand, judges and courts will be suspected of being partial if their ruling suspends the forced removal of, e.g., Islamists and/ or ‘Gefährder’ due to the detrimental situation in the country of origin; on the other, there are increasing indications of a right-wing political upheaval and right-wing extremist anomalies in the area of jurisdiction due to a growing number of professional lawyers and honorary judges who are members of the AfD or are close to other right-wing/ extremist currents. The author of a book titled ‘Right-wing judges’ (‘Rechte Richter’, cf. Wagner 2021) described the new quality of politically opinionated rulings in an interview: “A judge from the Zittau district court writes in a ruling that Chancellor Merkel ‘seems to have endangered public peace more than a Facebook comment accused of incitement to hatred’ as a result of the open borders in 2015/16. Administrative judges in Gera refer to ‘unruly’ asylum seekers or ‘so-called’ church asylum in their rulings. In a ruling by the Gießen Administrative Court, a judge took the view that the NPD slogan ‘Migration kills’ was an ‘empirically provable fact’.” Cf. taz 2021.

subject to a judicial order by the district courts (*Amtsgerichte*, the first instance of ordinary jurisdiction).⁶⁸

⁶⁸ Droste and Nitschke (2022) use the case of ten persons designated to forced removal as an example to show how the *Amtsgerichte* (courts of ordinary jurisdiction) generally follow the proposal of the ABH ordering the detention, and thus ‘adopt(ing) the perspective of the latter’ (p. 146). The hearing is very short, and the detainee is usually not asked to explain him/herself and to contribute facts on the basis of which the decision for or against detention is made; instead, according to Droste and Nitschke’s research, the decision seems to be ‘pre-determined’. The apparent lack of serious consideration of the foreigner’s perspective raises pertinent questions about the role of the courts of ordinary jurisdiction and their judicial independence (see also pp. 156f).

Figure 6: Overview of institutions and actors in forced removals from NRW⁶⁹

⁶⁹ Source: authors' compilation.

5.2 Implementation/ “doings” of RMI connected to places of forced pick-up for removal

The implementation dimension of the forced return migration infrastructure is analysed below. It covers two stages of implementation applicable to pick up from any of the possible places⁷⁰: (1) the preparation (5.2.1 a-b) and (2) the actual enforcement (Vollzug) of removal (5.2.1 c-e).

5.2.1 Actions by different actors

The preparation of forced removal involves two processes: For one, identity clarification and the issuance of travel documents (passport replacement paper/s [Passersatzpapier/e, PEP]) and two, the logistical preparation and organisation of the enforcement procedure.

a) Identity clarification

Research has shown that it is very common for the identity of persons who have been through asylum application and rejection processes as well as court and other procedures, who have lost their residence status in Germany for other reasons, or who are stopped by the police in public places without status to be unknown to the authorities. To enforce the law requiring them to leave Germany, the ABHs need to know where to return them (except for Dublin cases). Therefore, ABHs apply a standard procedure depending on the case and presumed origin of the migrant to be returned.⁷¹ If the designated returnee is a rejected asylum seeker, the BAMF provides the ABH with the hearing protocols and decision documentation. It can also use so-called open source intelligence (OSINT) and investigate the social media sites and accounts the person may have (used), invite the person for an interview, and possibly confiscate and search their mobile phone.⁷² A following or parallel measure is often the organisation of face-to-face interviews – with several persons or individuals – with representatives of the possible country of origin from embassies or consulates. For these, a ZAB may invite embassy staff and present them with these cases, and often, several foreigners authorities from Germany are present at such occasions with the persons whose identity has not been clarified and who are suspected to be from the respective country of origin. In a variation, the local ABH schedules an appointment for the person concerned with the nearest consulate or embassy and requests them to attend the personal hearing. According to an

⁷⁰ These include central accommodation facilities, communal/ municipal accommodation, private residences, premises of church asylum, the deportation detention facility Büren and ABHs premises. The literature also documents removal from hospitals and psychiatric clinics (Suerhoff and Engelmann 2021, Girth 2020); however, the authors did not come across such cases during interviews and for this reason these are not included.

⁷¹ Designated returnees are legally obliged to cooperate in clarifying their identity (Sect. 82 AufenthG). This encompasses that they personally appear in appointments with the competent authority and the representations or authorised officials of the state of which they are presumed to be nationals of and provide the information required to clarify their identity.

⁷² The ‘reading out’ of data carriers (*Datenträgerauslesung*) was described by some ABH representatives as measure of last resort. Authorized are only persons with a juridical qualification (comparable to judges). Usually, due to lack of the up-to-date technology, the data carriers are sent to the ZAB Essen which is specialized in reading data carriers. The local ABH receives only identity-relevant information from the data office in return, not the entire content (reasons being among others privacy and data protection). Cf. Interview local ABH, 25 September 2024. In a recent legal development, persons can be sought by current arrest warning (*Fahndung*) for identity clarification. Cf. Notes, 27 June 2024.

interview (25 September 2024), the local ABH offers the person in question transport to the embassy or consulate; at least one time the person has to be able to go there by themselves. If this does not happen, the ABH obliges the person a next time to attend and picks them up, with no choice to withdraw or reject the hearing. Since 27 February 2024, according to § 82 para. 4 s. 2 AufenthG, the so-called embassy hearings can be enforced by force as an administrative act ('Order' to take so-called preparatory measures for identity-clarification). The costs for such hearings are to be paid by the designated returnee in accordance with Section 66 AufenthG. According to the Administrative Court of Schleswig Holstein (VG Schleswig-Holstein 2021), 'It is not objectionable if three law enforcement officers are deployed to accompany a person to an embassy hearing of the assumed home country. This also applies if the person concerned has not behaved aggressively or violently in the past but has merely announced that he or she will not voluntarily apply for a passport and has not appeared at the previous appointments.' After the hearing, a written confirmation or non-confirmation of the person's probable nationality or affiliation is sent to the responsible ABH. If embassy or consulate staff believe that the person is a national or has lived in their country, an investigation in the place of origin is initiated. The spectrum of measures is broad and ranges from fingerprint verification in existing national databases (Pakistan) to localized search for birth certificate copies undertaken by subcontracted lawyers through the German embassy in the respective country (e.g. in India).⁷³ If there is no confirmation, other means of identity clarification are pursued further, e.g. phone data reading or the obligation to attend another hearing of an alternative country if respective conclusions have evolved in the meantime (embassy staff might drop hints about the presented persons' origin if they cannot confirm their own competence/ jurisdiction).

Depending on the origin country, once the nationality and identity are confirmed and proven by legal documents (birth certificate, national identity card, etc.), the competent authority in the origin country (of return destination) would be able to issue passport replacement papers (*Passersatzpapiere*, PEP). However, the issuance of PEP is not an automatism, and many countries choose not to issue them. For example, while Albania and Serbia were said to be quick in issuing papers, Pakistan is reliable once they find a fingerprint entry in their national database, and Armenia is said to be cooperative, while Guinean authorities were described as uncooperative in the past.⁷⁴ According to interview data, Guinea is one of the countries NRW ABHs struggle with in the process of identity clarification and PEP-issuance; however, Guinea is reportedly accepting embassy presentations of criminals for identity clarification now; still, the issuing of PEP is not an automatism. In contrast to the interview information, the Federal government responded in a minor inquiry of the parliamentary group Die Linke on Embassy hearings for the provisioning of passport replacement papers regarding Guinea that a country delegation from Guinea had been invited to Germany in September 2024 for two weeks to aid ZAB Essen during seven days to identify suspected nationals from Guinea and issue PEP. The delegation also stayed for the same purpose one day in Bremen. Several research partners used the metaphor of a game, where some players do not cooperate or play at all, or even football, where one team cannot always win. Thus, institutional representatives assessed the non-issuance of passport replacement papers for international travel (and as such required for the

⁷³ Cf. Notes, 27 June 2024.

⁷⁴ Cf. Deutscher Bundestag 2024d, p. 4.

forceful removal by the authorities) to be one of the greatest challenges in forced return enforcement. In some cases, it was said to take years. This has implications for forced removal detention as it does not make sense to detain people if it is foreseeable that the ABH will not be able to obtain replacement passport documents for a person within a period of three months.

b) Logistical preparation and organization of enforcement

When the documents are complete or likely to be received within an expected time frame, the ABH initiates in a first step a range of logistical measures to prepare the actual enforcement (*Vollzug*) of removal. According to one representative of a local ABH, “It is the task/responsibility of the ABH to conduct a removal measure in a way that it works” [„*Aufgabe der Ausländerbehörde ist, eine Abschiebemaßnahme so zu gestalten und auch vorher so abzusichern, dass sie funktioniert.*“ (Interview, 25 September 2024)]. Depending on the exhaustion of means any ABH employs within its own discretion in line with its either more integrationist or return orientation (‘attitudinal culture’), a range of measures can be initiated to ensure the person/s who are legally obliged to leave Germany, will be accessible at the day of pick-up for deportation to accomplish practical enforcement.

Thus, the ABH can apply for forced removal detention of a returnee in legally justifiable cases, i.e., if it can plausibly argue that the person would otherwise abscond. Evidence suggests that half of those detained prior to deportation are found to be detained unlawfully after legal investigations.⁷⁵ In a variation of detainment, called ‘desk removals’, migrants are, e.g., summoned to the social welfare office in order to increase the likelihood that they will sleep in the accommodation on that day, and are then either detained (first) or immediately taken to be removed on the same day.⁷⁶ ABHs also prepare for the case of legal representation/ defense of the designated returnee/s upon pick-up and during the pre-departure (by plane) procedure. In many cases the ABH deposits a so-called *Schutzschrift* (lit.: protective brief) with the responsible court so that if a lawyer complains about his client’s unlawful treatment and looming removal etc., the written response is already present in the court reasoning why the deportation should be carried out now and how this is legal and justified. The lawyer’s emergency appeal on behalf of the client in such cases thus remains without effect (very much to the disadvantage of the persons designated to leave Germany. Viewed from a slightly different angle of the need to legitimate practices that even the ABHs might feel lie in the grey area of law, their anticipation of juridical opposition in the form of an emergency appeal (*Eilantrag*) and thereupon preventive measures (by issuing a *Schutzschrift*) secures legitimacy for the individual forced removal measure by the court’s decision based on and following the *Schutzschrift*.

⁷⁵ Cf. Mielke et al. (2024, Section 5.10 [Detention], p. 39), Interview 23 July 2024, Abschiebungsreporting 2023, Hilfe für Menschen in Abschiebehaft Büren e.V. 2018.

⁷⁶ In such pick-up scenarios, the affected have no opportunity to pack and take personal belongings (e.g., books, school materials, glasses, medication) with them. Cf. Deutscher Bundestag (2024a, p. 45). In NRW, no official ‘*Erlass*’ (state edict) exists that proscribes the enforcement of desk removals; however, in other federal states, e.g., Brandenburg, a letter from the respective responsible state ministry suggests desk removals as one of several measures to enhance forced removals and make the process more efficient (Ministerium des Innern und für Kommunales Brandenburg 2024).

Otherwise, it is reportedly common that a few days before the removal operation is planned, representatives of the ABH engage staff and the caretaker (*Hausmeister*) of the (central or communal) accommodation facility the 'scheduled' forced returnee/s live to get to know the site, how and where the person or family is housed. Based on the site visit, the enforcement section of the ABH or the colleague/s in charge reportedly prepares a detailed plan which might go as far as getting key access to the site or even the unit of residence of the designated returnee/s. Again, in a variation of this measure, local ABHs contact the management of the facility-administering organization in order to learn whether or not the person/s in question are present and around, whether and/ or when they would usually take meals in the facility⁷⁷, and use this information for assessing other measures, e.g., detention to prevent absconding or the check of other possible places the person in question might be staying at as possible sites for pick-up and forced removal. There is also a level of secrecy, as the information about planned removal measures is not permitted to be shared with the social welfare provider (social workers) and the security service in advance, at least in the central accommodation facilities.⁷⁸ Critics deem the described detailed planning of the pick-up operation (*Zugriff*) an encroachment on basic rights (*Grundrechteingriff*) and thus at least questionable because organizational intelligence about people's residence situations falls into a grey area of law(fulness) (*rechtlich im Graubereich*).⁷⁹

In a subsequent step, practical enforcement preparation entails the logistical planning of the departure, including the booking of flights, transport, and receipt⁸⁰ on the one hand, and route and time planning, risk assessment, and personnel deployment planning for the pick-up and transportation to the airport, on the other hand. All NRW ABHs (decentralized and ZABs) depend for their logistics arrangements for pick-up (regarding route, timing and personnel deployment) on the flight scheduling organized by ZAB Bielefeld's Central Directory for Deportations by Air (Zentralstelle Flugabschiebungen, ZFA). Thus, as part of their planning process, local ABHs⁸¹ issue a formal request to the ZFA to return a certain person or family (*Rückführungersuchen*), including thereby special remarks about the designated returnee/s such as security-relevant incidences (police record, propensity for violence, suicide risk). ZFA

⁷⁷ For the cases when the ZABs are in charge of organising the enforcement of removals – as a rule from the central accommodation facilities (ZUEs) in their respective district – the responsible ZAB unit contacts the head of the ZUE, who is also a representative of the district government, directly in order to know whether the 'target person' is regularly present in the ZUE, i.e., actually resides there or only comes occasionally for the receipt of pocket money or similar (Notes, 27 June 2024).

⁷⁸ Cf. MKFFI 2021a for the NRW-Ministry's secrecy provisions for forced removals from central accommodation facilities. Among other content, the document suggests several measures to prevent that potential forced returnees might draw conclusions about an imminent forced removal, e.g., the returnees are not informed about the preparation of lunch packages, and the pocket money should be paid out in full to avoid suspicion, even if the forced removal of a resident is planned before the next payment date.

⁷⁹ As does the searching of private rooms by ABH staff in distinction to entering the (private) accommodation (section), cf. below.

⁸⁰ Especially mentioned in case of Dublin transfers. For these, specialized units in ABHs (e.g., Dortmund Desk 32c) are common and correspond to national- and international-level units, e.g., the BAMF Dublin centre and Dublin units EU member states.

⁸¹ In some cases, local ABHs might also request their district ZAB for logistical assistance/ to request ZFA and take care of the logistical process on their behalf.

organizes any flights in coordination with the Frontex>Returns Division and books for collective and individual charters as well as regular airline flight tickets. According to Frontex, "Germany is also the most active user of both Frontex charter and scheduled flights mechanisms. Most of the returnees from Germany supported by Frontex are returned by charter flights, but the share of third country nationals returned by scheduled flights has been growing considerably."⁸² Two weeks prior to the planned deportation flight, Federal Police is informed. Local ABHs usually request their district ZAB for practical support during enforcement if they themselves face personnel shortages. In cases where the pick-up situation is less predictable from the perspective of the ABH, it can and does request support from the state police, e.g., if a person is known to respond violently, has a criminal or violent record or is deemed a 'Gefährder'. However, the presence of state police during enforcement operations is the exception in NRW and is usually not foreseen (cf. above). A new development is the establishment of a so-called centralised (state) transport directory ('Landestransportkommando') at the ZAB Cologne, which is responsible for handling the transfer to the airport. Reportedly, the ZFA data about flight departures are transmitted to this directory, and a local ABH can request its respective district ZAB to take care of the transfer after ABH staff has been present during pick-up (*Zugriff*).

The route and timing of the transfer are planned according to the given departure times of the flights arranged by the ZFA, which in turn schedules the flights based on conditions set by the destination countries. Reportedly, many destination countries require⁸³ a time window for arrivals between early morning and no later than two pm, which often leads to pick-ups during night time (90 per cent).⁸⁴ For example, Bangladesh is said to accept charter arrivals only between midnight and 2am, while various African countries reject charter flights completely given the risk of public discontent. Individual subdistrict authorities have restricted timings for the pick-up of families, for example, not before 6am. However, depending on the forced return destination, this might collide with the framework requirements and thus lead to a situation where forced returns are not enforceable (interview, local foreigners authority, 25 September 2024). According to a foreigners office representative, since the enforcement of forced removal should be as stress-free as possible for the returnee/s and no one is allowed to be detained for longer than the time needed for pick-up and transfer and roughly two hours at

⁸² Written email reply of Frontex upon interview request, 29 July 2024.

⁸³ In Germany, the competent state authorities (in NRW: MKJFGFI) as well as BAMF issue information about destination countries' conditions for returns, which include the permissible timings. In the context of the political discussion in NRW (and beyond) whether the Solingen assassin (attack at Solingen town fair claiming three lives on 23 August 2024) whose initial Dublin removal to Bulgaria had failed, could not have been transferred a second time immediately after, the credibility of these information came under scrutiny. In one of the first sessions of the newly installed NRW state parliamentary inquiry committee (Parlamentarischer Untersuchungsausschuss) on the Solingen event, a document of the Bulgarian authorities (Transfer form of the Bulgarian State Agency for Refugees) was cited that suggested a 'preference' (not mandatory condition) of receiving forced returnees in the timeframe: "*We prefer the transfer to take place at Sofia Airport any working day except Friday between 9:00 AM and 2:00 PM.*", parallel with the request to notify the Bulgarian State Agency for Refugees seven working days in advance for any Dublin transfer (Ullrich 2025). Subsequently, the political opposition parties blamed the state government for interpreting the timings as conditional suggesting lack of political will to carry out forced removals, in a variation going as far as to suggest the purposeful use of discretionary space to avoid removals (Landtagsfraktion FDP 2025), and in other interpretations the responsible ministry just failed organizationally (public policy failure).

⁸⁴ Cf. Notes, 27 June 2024.

the airport before departure⁸⁵, ABH and ZAB representatives stated that the time frame for arrival set by destination countries was the main factor for night time pick-ups in Germany. They are broadly perceived as inhumane because as a rule they are not announced in advance, and those who are picked up are taken completely by surprise.⁸⁶ Thus, it is no surprise that a) affected people react irritated, surprised and resist if they can; and b) that local ABH personnel enters unpredictable situations that staff should be prepared for to de-escalate ideally (cf. below for pick up-procedures). When families are picked up, female ABH/ ZAB staff is mandatory to accompany them to the airport.

A third pre-enforcement action is the organization of medical check-ups, so called fit-for-fly confirmations for the person/s subjected to forced removal. These are issued by contracted medical service providers and can be booked online by any ABH.⁸⁷ The services these physicians offer range from check-ups and the issuing of needed paperwork to the presence of a medical escort during pick-up, transfer and flight, to arrangements for pick up by a medical service provider in the country of return. Whereas previously, it used to be common practice to stop forced removals if a person was seriously ill, this is no longer possible since the introduction of §60.7 Residence Act (AufenthG), which includes the presumption that a person is fit to travel; if not, this presumption must be rebutted.⁸⁸ This means that if an ABH organises a medical fit for fly-checkup for a returnee whose asylum application has been rejected, medical emergencies or other health-related risks are often no longer an obstacle for forced removal. Instead, an escort is mandatory in such cases, and the BAMF approves the escort as the lead authority for Dublin cases. A member of the hardship commission shared, “We have cases with medical constellations, where someone is in a wheelchair, is deaf and dumb, a very recent case, cognitively completely inaccessible, in need of care 24 hours a day, cannot provide themselves with hygiene or food; however, they are fit to travel within the meaning of this regulation because they can be transported with an escort, with medical assistance, in a wheelchair and can be unloaded from the aircraft at their destination. Full stop. That cannot be the case. That really can't be the case, especially if there are also general

⁸⁵ Longer fixation of people would otherwise amount to forcible confinement/ detention and require legal justification and approval/ issuing of a detention order by the district court (*Amtsgericht*). It must be preceded by a failed removal attempt.

⁸⁶ Cf. below for pick up-procedures.

⁸⁷ An important player in this field in NRW with a wide spectrum of solutions for public sector authorities and aggressive courting of medical personnel is [Behördenarzt.de](https://www.behördenarzt.de). According to its website “Behördenarzt.de is the right contact for all medical issues in the public sector. With our network of over 1,500 doctors and the experience gained from over 2,500 projects and expertise, we can cover almost any type of assignment.” Besides, there are several other medical service providers offering all-round carefree packages (Cf. Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 135), often via framework contracts or on honorarium basis.

⁸⁸ A rebuttal can only be done by presenting medical certificates that fulfil very specific usually insurmountable requirements that normal practicing doctors can hardly provide, even if they submit several pages of medical assessments. In the view of some observers, this excludes an entire medical specialists-group (psycho-social therapists) from recognizing and assessing migrants' mental health situations – which they see fits the primary interest of the lawmaker in creating a smooth forced removal machinery undisturbed by interventions based on concerns for fundamental and human rights. Protests by Chambers of psychotherapists and even the General Medical Council/ Chamber of medical professionals (*Ärztammer*) remain unheard (interview, 8 May 2024).

conditions, such as family members here in Germany who are also prepared to look after the person” (interview, 24 July 2024).

A fourth pre-enforcement action concerns the organisation of the airport handover to the Federal Police. In the case of unaccompanied travel of designated returnees, the responsible ABH or ZAB has to send a Letter of notification to the responsible Federal Police airport office or an additional letter of request about a planned forced removal two weeks in advance of the planned flight. Moreover, the Federal Police guideline requires submitting a risk analysis on designated returnees, taking into account possible health needs, the risk of violence, etc. (cf. Bundespolizei 2016, p. 9). These types of notifications serve as prerequisites for the Federal Police to start their own internal organization (e.g., deployment of personnel) and communication with the airline (if applicable), with counterpart authorities in transit and destination countries and, for non-Dublin returns, with the German embassy in the return country (Bundespolizei 2016, pp. 16, 17).

The practical enforcement of forced removals as such (*Vollzug*) can be divided into three stages if completed: (c) pick up and transfer to the airport⁸⁹, (d) the handling and clearance process at the airport and flight to the destination country, and (e) the arrival in the destination country and handover to the respective authorities. The designated returnee/s may resist and interrupt the foreseen linear process in each of these three stages. As a result, the return process is stopped early and enters the statistics as ‘not enforced’. The different options of resistance are listed below as they occur in the respective steps of the ‘forced return logic’.

c) Pick-up and transfer to the place of departure/ airport

Except for the cases where pick-up and transfer take place from the deportation detention facility in Büren by the ZAB⁹⁰, all other constellations involve a combined presence of local and central foreigners authorities’ staff, optional translators (arranged by the ZFA), and possibly security and medical personnel. According to Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 45), more than a quarter of all forcibly removed persons from NRW in 2022 and 2023 were removed after forced removal detention. So-called ‘desk removals’ from the premises of the ABH may involve subcontracted security guard personnel (who await the designated returnee in an office ‘standing behind the door’), otherwise local personnel are in the lead. In central and municipal accommodation centres, searches for a person in question might set in on a more or less legal basis (given the distinction between entering and searching private premises). As result of the recent Repatriation Improvement Law (entered into force in February 2024), §58.5-2 AufenthaltG was altered to allow the authorities to enter premises other than the room of the designated returnee as well as ‘shared premises’ in collective accommodation premises. However, searches require a court approval and search warrant. While families are reportedly usually present upon pick-up, 50 per cent of those supposed to be Dublin-transferred to

⁸⁹ Forced removals by land are also common. However, due to shortage of space and since approximately four out of five forced removals are conducted by air (cf. Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 73), the former are not included here as separate cases. Part of the security package with which the NRW government reacted upon the attack by a rejected Syrian asylum seeker in Solingen in August 2024, is the decision to establish a new/ second forced removal detention facility in Mönchengladbach with a capacity for 140 detainees, both female and male (Komitee für Grundrechte 2025).

⁹⁰ This can include the (forced removal) detention facility in Ingelheim (in the neighbouring state Rhineland-Palatinate), where female designated returnees from NRW are detained.

another EU-member state are likely not to be present. In private, church-based and collective accommodations, doors might have to be broken or a locksmith service brought in to enter the premises by force. In all cases and sites where a returnee is met, their mobile phone is usually confiscated in one of the first steps before the persons are asked to dress and pack the most needed items. This is done under time pressure; there are several reports of forced dressing, of basic items such as glasses or necessary medication being forgotten and not replaced. There are also conflicting reports about the extent to which designated returnees are informed of their rights and of what is going to happen from pick-up onwards. When met with resistance, enforcing staff often use restraints to control the situation and minimize the risk to themselves, including to enforcement staff.

In the process, family separation seems to be common and sometimes deliberate despite the fact that the EU Return Directive, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Checklist NRW (cf. Annex 1), issued by the state of NRW in 2016 (Ministerium für Inneres und Kommunales 2016), clearly discourage immigration authorities to separate families. As Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 188) summarise, “binding standards are still lacking. In some cases, families with children are separated by the forced removal process; in other cases, immigration authorities arrest one parent and have them detained pending forced removal, while the other parent remains with the underage children.”

In cases where ABHs have requested assistance of ZAB personnel, the latter accompany the designated returnee/s to the airport and hand them – and separately the returnees’ documents – over to the Federal Police. The ABHs’ staff informs the Federal Police about possible occurrences during the transfer, e.g., an illness or submitted emergency appeals. Depending on the situation, additional security (state police) or a translator and/ or medic is also present up to this point.

d) Clearance process at the airport

At the airport⁹¹, the designated forced returnees and their baggage are searched (Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 96) and then accompanied through the usual check-in and security screening procedures in a separate terminal. Their mobile phones, handed over to the Federal Police by the submitting ABH staff, are now switched off and stowed in the luggage of the persons concerned. Again, translators and medical staff but also observers to the return process might be present and act according to their mandate and tasks, e.g. often fit-for-fly certificates are still issued at the airport. Depending on the returnees’ financial situation, the Federal Police either pays them earnest money (*Handgeld*)⁹² to enable immediate expenses after their arrival, or people are asked to hand over substantial amounts of money they might have with them to pay for their return enforcement costs (so-called *Abnahme von Sicherheitsleistungen*, lit. acceptance of security services, according to §66.5-1,2 and §67.1 AufenthG) (Diakonie

⁹¹ Where not indicated otherwise, this section relies in particular on observations of the forced removal observers documented in their annual reports (Diakonie 2020-2024). The observations of Diakonie-staff are restricted to ground handling activities.

⁹² Cf. the latest earnest money edict of the state of NRW (Handgelderlass NRW), issued on 11 December 2024, valid from 1 January 2025 (MKJFGFI 2024e). Accordingly, NRW decided in 2024 to pay hand money to forced returnees upon departure, usually an amount of 50 EUR, in exceptional cases 70 EUR. Criteria for non-eligibility are, e.g., if there is evidence that the returnees have funds in the country of destination, e.g. because they have transferred funds there or if a previous forced removal was completed less than five years ago (MKJFGFI 2024e, p. 2).

2024, p. 22; Oulios 2016, p. 261). Conflicts due to anger and resistance and corresponding use of restraints by the Federal Police arise typically because the returnees were not informed about the security deposit necessity or the actual destination of deportation (interview, 7 May 2024). Returnees are not supposed to stay at the airport for longer than two to three hours, and according to the German *Grundgesetz* (Basic Law), the designated returnees must not be restrained in any way or put in cells to be detained, even for a short period. This would require a detention order backed by a court and a hearing with a judge after release. According to one informed interviewee, a high degree of intransparency exists regarding the occurrence of de facto detention of designated forced returnees at NRW and other airports. Having obtained witnesses reports from forcibly removed people who returned to Germany afterwards, the respondent filed a criminal complaint against the Federal Police at Düsseldorf Airport in 2016 in a response to which the Federal Police stated that anyone could leave, and nobody would be detained at the airport (interview, 23 July 2024).

If the flight is unaccompanied, the Federal Police officers bring the person to the door of the aircraft and hand the personal ID documents to the crew members, who return them to their owners upon arrival in the destination country.

If a forced removal is stopped due to a successful emergency appeal, if the person is found unfit to fly, if the flight is cancelled for some reason, or if the pilot and or crew on scheduled flights assess that s/he poses a danger to other passengers and a security risk for the flight, the representatives of the ABHs are responsible for returning the person back to the residence. However, cases have been reported where people were left stranded because ABH-staff had left prematurely (Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 96-97).

e) Journey by air to destination country, arrival and handover to authorities

According to Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 97), between 30 and 60 per cent of all forced removals annually are unaccompanied cases; in 2024, there were 9,743 cases (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025, p. 15). In 2024, airline security personnel accompanied the forced removal of 468 persons (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025, p. 16), most to North Macedonia (114), Romania (95) and Kosovo (77), but also to Iraq (43); security personnel of the respective destination country assisted in 2,019 forced removals, with Georgia (1,358), Algeria (410) and Moldova (181) topping the list. If the flight is accompanied by Frontex or Federal Police personnel, these wear civilian clothes on scheduled flights. In 2024, 13,243 Federal Police officers and 570 state police or state authority representatives escorted 7,607 forced returnees (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 16). As a rule, forced removal escorts sit with the returnees in the back rows of the aircraft; a blanket might cover possible fixation so that other passengers do not notice it (Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 99).

Legally⁹³, only when the person concerned has been handed over to the authorities of the country of destination, that is when the arriving returnee has left the transit zone of the airport of arrival and entered the sovereign territory of the country of destination, is a forced removal deemed to have successfully taken place. This requirement theoretically allows for the opportunity to reverse the forced removal carried out via collective charter flights during the

⁹³ According to two rulings by the Higher Administrative Court of North Rhine-Westphalia, of 15 August 2018 (Az.: 17 B 1029/18) and 12 January 2017 (Az.: 18 B 1157/16).

transfer by air. Therefore, the accompanying personnel are required to check during transit stops and straight after landing in the country of destination whether a notification (*Eilrechtsschutzverfahren*) of an administrative court decision ordering the termination of the measure has been received by the means of communication carried on board (MKJFGFI 2023b).⁹⁴

Returnees in need of medical assistance ought to be handed over to qualified personnel and unaccompanied minors to family members or entrusted legal guardians upon arrival. The available grey literature on these topics documents numerous cases where, in particular, the aspect of medical care was not met as foreseen.

In cases where accompanied return operations via regular airline flights are stopped en route due to returnee's 'unruliness' (*Renitenz*), manifested in violence, (partial) self-harm or other serious health conditions (unfit to fly) or if the authorities in the destination country refuse to receive the returnee upon arrival (*Einreiseuntersagung*), the returnee is accompanied back to the departure airport in Germany.⁹⁵

5.2.2 How do they facilitate or contest returns (How effective are they?)

The previous overviews of actors and their 'doings' are incomplete without an analysis of their respective role concepts in relation to the 'accomplishment' or prevention of forced removals. The in-depth study of this particular dimension of the forced removal infrastructure in NRW suggests that rather than a binary of facilitation vs. contestation, there is a continuum, where institutions have a rather fixed position, but actors of these institutions can occupy different positions along the continuum. In theory, on the one end, institutions, actors and actions are eager to remove people forcibly, investing time, energy and vast amounts of resources into the so-perceived 'necessary processes' of preparation and enforcement. On the other, some fundamentally question the entire return regime, the idea of state-induced returns (Koch 2013), i.e. both assisted and forced removals, and the normative underpinnings of the society as a whole. While these are idealized categorical positionings, the empirical insight gained during data analysis rather suggests that actors' roles are positioned on a stretch of a continuum between the two poles, which means that a clear distinction is not always straightforward. This spectrum is also mirrored by designated returnees who may comply with facilitated forced removal by cooperating or they may oppose and resist return by various means.

Clearly on the facilitating side (of the continuum stretch of analysis for the purpose of this paper, cf. Figure 7) are the institutional actors (state administration with subordinate

⁹⁴ For an example of how the information chain about effective termination orders has not been working or rather not been adhered to, and which justifying arguments the involved state authorities brought forward to explain the incident, see *Abschiebungsreporting 2023*. In this case, a man from Viersen/ NRW was deported to Kinshasa/ DRC on a collective Frontex charter flight from Brussels via Larnaka (Cyprus). Importantly, according to the National Agency for the Prevention of Torture, a so-called 'Last Call'-procedure that ensures that the head of escorts is informed about the status of the legal proceedings during the flight until the moment of handover requires that the potential court order will be respected and implemented (Nationale Stelle zur Verhütung von Folter 2024, p. 47).

⁹⁵ According to Federal Police guideline *Best Rück Luft* (Bundespolizei 2016, p. 32), the Federal Police airport office must inform the ABH/ ZAB in detail about why the return operation was stopped; alluding alone to 'unruliness' of a forced returnee is not sufficient.

authorities⁹⁶, Federal Police, Frontex) who are part of a strict administrative-political hierarchy with a continuously optimized interplay of coordination concerning their mandates and roles for both preparation and enforcement of forced removals. Intensified centralization tendencies over the last decade that were codified in the so-called Asyl-Stufenplan (Land NRW 2018) have added new interfaces and new institutions (ZABs, RKKs, ZFA, etc.) that reflect the political will to ‘facilitate better’ – i.e. more effectively.⁹⁷

Figure 7 visualizes the relevant section of the continuum, illustrating that while facilitation seems to be quite clear, contestation can mean different things. For example, as shown here, contestation can express a desire to change the means and process without questioning the reason and purpose of forced returns, which means that forced returns are considered necessary while being carried out in a more human manner. Contestation can also take the form of pro-active scrutiny, rejection of and resistance to forced returns. With rare exceptions, the ‘contesting’ actors and actions involved in forced removals in NRW do not question forced removals as such but only how they are being conducted. They find the process problematic because it involves human rights violations and ‘drama’, especially when families are affected. Thus, most of the civil society and non-governmental organizations plus the interface institutions (FFiNW, Refugee Council NRW, Advisory Board Forced Removal Detention, airport forced removal observers) and many individual actors fall into this category. The petitions committee of the state parliament with its mandate to correct possible errors when applying regulatory law (*Ordnungsrecht*) – in this case the Residence Act (AufenthG) – or the hardship commission, which, from an integration lens, aspires to see the broader context and situation of a person or family obliged to leave Germany, also fit into this category because they act within the logic of the larger framework of return migration infrastructure. When articulated, criticism is directed at the legislative and implementing authorities at federal and state level for changes to individual regulations or to correct case decisions; a broader, more fundamental and political scrutiny is not voiced and the need for it might not be felt.

⁹⁶ These include the facility managing operators in central and municipal/ decentralized accommodation facilities.

⁹⁷ ZFA Bielefeld and RKKs are a case in point as they report existing capacities in collective charters to the ABHs pointing out possible deportees to match flights. According to Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 89), a systematic preselection is desired by the municipal ABHs – together with the involved authorities they compile so-called priority lists (*Prioritätenlisten*) of forced returnees. The criteria are not entirely clear or transparent; however, Dublin-transfers, due to the limited time frame before the sovereignty clause is invoked, and so-called *Gefährder* are high on the list.

Figure 7: *Continuum of attitudinal practices in forced removals - from facilitation to resistance*

Those who reject and aim to prevent coerced returns by different means are intellectuals, different types of activists⁹⁸ and, among the latter, individual members of institutions and organizations (of the other two categories) that do not fundamentally criticise the idea or involved institutions, the preparation and enforcement of forced returns. Depending on the experiential background of these individuals, they consciously/ deliberately or more impulsively challenge the set-up of the constitutional order which, in their view, produces injustice by default, i.e., through legalistic measures (interview, 22 May 2024). They employ conceptual discussions and activist practices to support and assist migrants to prevent them from being subjected to returns, e.g. support activities of migrant self-organizations (counselling and guidance) or citizen asylum. In this category of contestation, effectiveness is not a value or category given that resistance aims at structural changes and a systematic overhaul of the entire coerced return regime. The limited reach of actors in this category is hampered by the fact that many critical minds focus on individual cases and case-based violations of fundamental rights alone, which they believe can be corrected through policy changes. They therefore appeal to state institutions to alleviate hardship, etc., which might lead to a stronger consideration of integration perspectives in ‘return management’ (*Rückkehrmanagement*)⁹⁹ procedures, but they do not necessarily go as far as to reflect on the

⁹⁸ Cf. Korvensyrjä (2024) for a study on West African-origin ‘diaspora’ activists’ engagement in Germany.

⁹⁹ ‘Return management’ has become an increasingly prominent concept used by German authorities dealing with different aspects of asylum and foreigners law from national to local level; however, there is no unified understanding or standard definition. In a common negative connotation, return management is officials’ ‘German’ for deportations and “integrated return management” is a rather not clear, all-encompassing generic term (interview, 19 July 2024). A neutral smallest common denominator seems to be approaching the issue of returns from a holistic view at foreigners’ presence in Germany and the intention to do justice to the vast spectrum of expectations (skilled immigration needs, international protection, residence stay right realization) and legal requirements (connected to domestic security, regulative law, clan criminality, etc.). As one head of ABH who conceptualized this concept for his own authority (in a major city of NRW) recounted: “The initial idea in 2018 was that we extend the scope of our purview beyond mere assisted return counselling separate from regulative policies and forced returns to enable a forward-looking stance with a stronger focus on immigrants’ right to stay, but at the

criminalizing and racist underpinnings of the return regime, which, for instance, categorises persons as ‘obliged to leave’ in the inherent logic of German immigration law, or which is constantly being tightened in line with the system's inherent logic of seeking effectiveness in law enforcement.¹⁰⁰ The boundaries between the second and third actor category are sometimes fluid where people engage as volunteers in defence of human rights and search for an alternative but without finding it and thus remain in the group that seeks to (at least) impact current forced removal procedures in a way that makes them more humane, even if their abolition is or seems out of reach.

Assisted return is perceived as a more humane alternative to forced removal and the positioning of actors involved in its implementation always includes forced removals as a reference frame (mainly as a worse alternative that is to be avoided). Despite this common denominator, there is a wide range of attitudes and related actions among the actors involved. On the one hand, there is, for example, the statement that forced removals are “nothing to be ashamed of”, because every person affected by them has been offered (and refused to accept) assisted return beforehand (notes from event, May 2024). The ‘necessity of return’ is not questioned in this line of argument, and the option of assisted return also serves to legitimize forced removals. More commonly – and reflecting a kind of middle ground – actors emphasize that assisted return is not only more humane but also more effective than forced removal. By involving the migrant in the planning of their return and by not using (direct) force or secrecy, assisted return is much less likely to be hampered by resistance or protests; it is also more cost-effective. Proponents of this argumentation may object against the violence of forced removal, but not necessarily the rationale behind removal orders; in fact, they offer a more effective means of implementation. In addition, the legal representations of origin countries (embassies, consulates) tend to pose fewer obstacles to assisted return. Absconding prior to departure does happen, but rarely, and no cases of self-harm or resistance have been reported during the implementation of assisted returns in NRW.

It is in this context that actors from charities and other non-governmental organisations face the most challenging balancing act between their own ideals and realities: They see themselves as advocates of refugee rights (and their organisations often voice explicit criticism of the means and methods that produce deportability/ returnability) at a different level. They engage

same time maintaining the regulative aspect. This led us to a situation where I today tell new colleagues during onboarding, ‘You have to be almost a bit schizophrenic to work in return management here, because you have to look with one eye towards the obligation to leave the country and enforcement, but with the other, please, towards the realisation of prospects to stay, etc. And, if possible, always at the same time.’ He described this as a surplus load for ABH staff. Looking back at the process of broadening the scope in return management as an independent administrative subject area since 2020, he added, “We have not always been able to realise this. So, the reality is not always what the planning is, because sometimes (...) staff shortages, Covid, Ukraine, everything that has befallen us has sometimes thwarted the idea of real management a bit and you are then very quickly back in reaction mode as a foreigners authority and look at how you somehow, I say, survive to some extent in everyday life” (interview, 22 July 2024).

¹⁰⁰ One interviewee told us, “... that always leads to cases where you sit there and think, it can't be true. That's why, when I give seminars on immigration law, my first sentence is usually, ‘Ladies and gentlemen, we're talking about immigration law, please leave your common sense at the cloakroom.’ If you get involved in the topic, if you get involved in the work, you actually have to deal with this dichotomy between common sense and the relatively ideologized immigration law on the other side” (interview, 25 April 2024).

in return counselling (sometimes after controversial internal debates) because they are convinced that people in difficult situations (such as a pending return) should be supported and not left alone. They also believe that information (e.g., about the timing and process of return) and transparency (about the reasons for refusal), more humane treatment during and upon return, reintegration assistance and remigration possibilities are (small) improvements (within a less than ideal system) that are worth fighting for. Or, in short, that assisted return is the lesser evil compared to forced removal or protracted irregularity. They often problematize the fact that within some state institutions forced and assisted returns are managed by the same actors (cf. Figure 5). As one interviewee put it: “I can't go to the people [...] and slap the order on the table and say, well, now you have to leave the country, otherwise you will be forcibly removed, but then, at another moment, I say, well, now I'm going to help you and advise you” (interview 19 July 2024).¹⁰¹ At the same time, for all migrants who are under a removal order, they depend on the good-will and trust of the responsible foreigners offices (ABHs or ZABs), which they would lose if they were seen to be delaying or preventing returns. The only two scenarios where this is possible are at the very beginning of the counselling, when legal alternatives to return should be assessed (which, according to the interviews, some actors take more seriously than others) and when a person attends return counselling without having been registered or rejected as an asylum seeker. In such cases, counselling NGOs do not share any information unless the person actually decides in favour of assisted return.¹⁰²

Two interesting aspects are worth mentioning that blur the ideal type categorization in Figure 7. First, as mentioned above, institutional mandates and the attitudes of subordinates (civil servants, public officials, staff and employees of government institutions and their subordinate authorities) do not necessarily (need to) correspond. This explains the existence of different ‘cultures’ that might dominate local and central foreigners authorities: Interviews have shown that some embody the regulatory provisions in their pure form and deny any room for interpretation with the result that they prove to be eager enforcers of the laws on improving forced removals based on the attitude that “the law must be enforced.”¹⁰³ They also feel supported by the narrative that municipalities are overburdened and that returns are a valid solution to this ‘problem’. Heads of institutions and administrations, as well as street-level bureaucrats, characterize and shape this dominant ‘culture’ through everyday practices. In contrast, other ABHs, mayors or county commissioners (*Bürgermeister, Landräte*) ‘believe’ in an integrationist approach and try all available options to offer migrants an integration path. While this is most relevant before a person or family is found to be obligated to leave and this to be enforceable (*vollziehbar ausreisepflichtig*), the attitudinal culture also plays a role in the planning and enforcement process – simply put, measures are enforced more humanely.

¹⁰¹ German original: “Ich kann ja nicht zu den Menschen [...] gehen und denen die Belehrung auf den Tisch hauen und sagen, gut, jetzt sind Sie ausreisepflichtig, sonst werden Sie abgeschoben, aber im anderen Moment sage ich dann, ja gut, ich helfe Ihnen jetzt und berate Sie” (interview, 19 July 2024).

¹⁰² Migrants who are not subject to a removal order can leave the process of assisted return at any time without consequences, even at the airport, but may then not be able to apply again.

¹⁰³ This emphasis on static law neglects the constant increased tightening of the regulatory framework and thus – as Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 30) rightly pointed out – the constructivist dimension of the law as product of symbolic policymaking with the aim to demonstrate the state’s ability to enforce the rule of law.

However, this shows that individual agency can have a tremendous impact when used as a space for negotiation regarding residence and asylum act applications. Another example is the development of assisted return counselling in the ZABs of NRW since 2021; it was driven by individual staff members working in return management (and thus also in assisted return, but without this being separated from forced return in any way). After realizing that this setting undermined the trust of potential returnees and did not allow the potential of assisted return to be exploited, they began to lobby at various levels (from their own superiors to the MKJFGFI) for this to be separated administratively and supported with additional funding.¹⁰⁴

Second, while the entire identity clarification process aims to establish deportability, it can be and is regularly thwarted by the non-cooperation of the countries of origin or destination when they do not issue passport replacement papers (PEP) for travel. The extent to which this non-cooperation results from ignorance or is an act of conscious rejection of the deportation regime, is beyond the scope of this paper (cf. 5.2.1.b).

5.3 Materials and technologies used in the forced removal infrastructure

An important prerequisite for the application and use of materials and technologies is the legal framework which provides for forced removals: the Asylum Act (AsylG) and the Residence Act (AufenthG) at the national level, complemented by state-level edicts (*Erlasse*) and regulations established at the sub-state level of municipalities and counties. Moreover, international bilateral readmission and migration agreements, plus regulations at the EU-level add to the spectrum of provisions that shape the application of certain objects for surveillance and the structure of databases and administrative processes spanning from local to supranational level.

This section distinguishes between places, technologies and materials in the five processes of preparation and enforcement of coerced returns identified above.¹⁰⁵ The findings are summarised in the following table.

Table 3: *Usage of materials and technologies*¹⁰⁶

	Places	Materials	Technologies
<i>Relevant throughout 1)-3)</i>		<i>Foreigners authorities' preselection lists of priority returnees</i>	<i>Checklist NRW (Ministerium für Inneres und Kommunales, 2016)</i>
PREPARATION			

¹⁰⁴ In 2024, the MKJFGFI was convinced by this approach and decided to fund two positions per ZAB only for assisted return (not yet fully implemented by the end of data collection). At the same time, however, the funding for non-governmental return counselling in the central accommodation facilities (ZUEs) was cut.

¹⁰⁵ The distinction between materials and technologies is not clear cut where documents are concerned because they might constitute objects as such in the instance when they need to be checked for existence/ provided or shown, but the documents' content might concern broader administrative processes the person is subjected to, and this in itself is more of a technology than an object.

¹⁰⁶ A brief description of specific technologies is compiled in Annex 1. Please note that the listing of places-materials- technologies in the same line (reading it from left to right) does not suggest a connection between those.

1) identity clarification	Embassies, consulates, ZABs	Excerpts of migrants' personal BAMF file ¹⁰⁷	Central Foreigners Registry (AZR), EuroDAC
		Mobile phones	OSINT
		Country of origin information (websites, data banks)	SYS 3.0, IRMA
2) logistical organization	ZUE, municipal accommodation facility	Passport Passport replacement paper (PEP)	<i>Rückführungersuchen</i> (foreigners authority to ZFA) via APS (AusreisePlanungStatistik)-System
		Fit for fly-certificate	Presence-surveillance system in accommodation facilities
		Letter of notification (in case of unaccompanied travel of returnee), or additional Letter of request about planned forced removal to responsible Federal Police airport office ¹⁰⁸	
		Protective brief (<i>Schutzschrift</i>)	Petition/ hardship application
		Other medical reports (e.g., psycho-social assessment)	Readmission case management, e.g., RCMS with Pakistan
ENFORCEMENT			
3) pick-up and transfer	Church premises	Different types of buses (up to 35/ 15 persons) with separating grid	Search warrant (case-specific)
	Central or municipal accommodation	Fixation materials: special helmets with spit protection, uniforms with	Emergency/ Summary appeal (<i>Eilverfahren</i>)

¹⁰⁷ According to one interviewee engaged in legal counselling, four different files (*Akten*) can be distinguished: a court file, the foreigners file, the enforcement file, and the medical file. Depending on the individual case, a designated returnee thus has at least two and up to four files (Interview, 23 July 2024).

¹⁰⁸ The submission period for notices of unaccompanied returns are at least three days in advance, vs. that for accompanied forced removals, which is two weeks in advance. Besides, the Federal Police guideline requires the submission of risk analysis about designated returnees (considering health needs, risk of violence, etc.) together with the notification and request letters (cf. Bundespolizei 2016, p. 9).

	facility, private residence	gloves, biteblock with fixation	
	Foreigners authority offices	Medication	Protective brief (<i>Schutzschrift</i>)
		Taser ¹⁰⁹	
	Forced removal or ordinary detention facility ¹¹⁰	Headsets and personal protective equipment of foreigners authorities' personnel: ballistic vests, protective gloves with cut protection	
		Operational equipment of foreigners authorities' staff: handcuffs (steel), disposable handcuffs and associated cutting tools, irritant spray device incl. first aid spray, ankle cuffs (steel)	
		Confiscated mobile phones	
<i>Relevant for 4)-7)</i>			<i>Federal Police Guideline 'Best Rück Luft' (Bundespolizei, 2016)¹¹¹</i>
4) clearance at airport and flight	Airport premises	Cash (retained or paid as <i>Handgeld</i>)	Fit for fly-certificate
	'Module F' at Düsseldorf airport	Returnee and documents handover report (from ZAB/ ABH/ state police to Federal Police), Form BPOL 1 90 003	Transmitted emergency appeal and deportation stop order during flight/ at transit stop/ upon arrival
	Inspection site	Food packages	Videorecording (exceptional) ¹¹²

¹⁰⁹ Rahman et al. (2023, p. 92) recount from an interview with a counsellor, "We have over twenty [...] witness statements that Tasers are used during forced removals, which is not actually permitted."

¹¹⁰ Note that so-called *Gefährder* are detained in ordinary detention facilities, whereas other males are detained in NRW's forced removal detention facility Büren. *Gefährder* removal as a special case is beyond the scope of this paper.

¹¹¹ The references to the various forms and documents relevant in stages four to seven, 4)-7), hints at the 'centrality of paperwork to statecraft' as analysed by Lindberg and Borrelli (2019) for the 'Swedish deportation regime'. Further, it speaks to Walters' recent article where he develops the concept of custodial chains (that combine subjects and paperwork) as tools in the process of charter flight removals; cf. Walters 2024.

¹¹² When expecting extreme violence from a returnee, Federal Police officers can use videorecording from the moment of takeover of the returnee from the pick-up authorities to the moment of boarding, up to seating in the aircraft (Bundespolizei 2016, pp. 30, 31). The usage of videorecording must be in line with Act on the Federal Police (BPolG) (Bundesministerium der Justiz, 1994) and is to be documented.

		Aircraft (scheduled flight, collective charter, individual charter)	
		Returnee handover report to airline personnel or destination state personnel (Form BPOL 1 90 018, Personenübergabeprotokoll)	
		PBL/ Federal Police equipment during regular airline flight & Frontex-equipment during charter flights: spit protection bonnet, plastic handcuffs, restraint belt/ body-cuff, mittens	
5) early termination of return procedure		Form BPOL 1 90 003 'unaccomplished return' Report about unsuccessful termination (BPOL 1 90 020)	
6) arrival and handover	Airport premises outside the transit zone area	Passport or passport replacement paper (PEP)	
		'Statement' document (BPOL 1 90 014) and Accompanying letter (BPOL 1 90 019) ¹¹³ in case of airline flights	
		'Process Report' about Charter flights ¹¹⁴	
7) follow-up processing		Forced removal documentation via form BPOL 1 90 003 Completion report (BPOL 1 90 020)	

¹¹³ Both documents have to be carried by the accompanying Federal Police escort leader and handed over to the counterpart authority in the destination country upon demand ('in case the foreign border office requires a declaration of the reason for forced return'), cf. Bundespolizei 2016, p. 29.

¹¹⁴ To be compiled by the Federal Police airport office for each charter measure departing at the particular airport, for required content details of the reports cf. Bundespolizei 2016, p. 34.

All types of interviewees articulated dissatisfaction with the existing state-level edicts (*Erlasslage*). Often, the rules and procedures are not transparent to outsiders, and less so to designated returnees. It needs no mentioning that such a situation inhibits adequate support to prevent and contest forced removals.

To give just one example: The NRW state decision to entrust the local ABHs with the enforcement of forced removals instead of the state police requires their personnel to have and (know how to) use personal protective and operational equipment to handle pick up- and transfer situations. Ideally, this mandate would also result in and require adequate training for ABH staff to deal with such extreme situations. While police personnel are systematically equipped with the necessary skills during their professional training and career, ordinary officials of ABHs lack such skills, and training activities are reportedly not offered to the extent needed. At the level of flight escorts, Frontex offers training programmes in various return dimensions (legal, operational, human rights aspects of return operations) also for EU member states' staff. Germany has established a personnel pool of air escorts (*Personenbegleiter:innen Luft*, PBL) among members of the Federal Police over recent years who qualify by completion of a special three-week training course. According to Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 85), 2,000 such PBL had been trained at the end of 2022; different media reports speak of the same number of PBL for 2024 (cf. von Boetticher, 2024), stating that this is a fourfold increase since 2015. The training was professionalized after a Sudanese returnee died during a return flight as result of police violence in 1999. Two to four PBL-officers accompany one returnee as a so-called escort team during a flight. In the words of one PBL: "Two colleagues secure one side of the person, the third is primarily responsible for communicating with the person and secures the person from behind" (von Boetticher, 2024a). A fourth colleague is added in the case of particularly strong resistance. The teaching and use of hands-on techniques PBL rely on to control the returnee's limbs so that the other person has no opportunity to use their own muscle power against the PBL does not fit either the material or technology category (von Boetticher, 2024a). It is also worth noting that the use of any PBL relies on the principle of voluntariness; this means that Federal Police officers with a PBL qualification accompany forced return flights not as principal activity or full-time job but occupy regular posts as officers where they have to be replaced by colleagues when on PBL-duty.¹¹⁵

Another dimension of 'technologies' relates to administrative processes that are hard to locate in the triad of places, objects/ materials and technologies but limit the intended effectiveness of NRW authorities. They are indirectly related to the diplomacy of readmission and return agreements, international airline conventions, and the legal and administrative framework underlying the forced return infrastructure. The RMI-analysis found at least five examples of such administrative processes:

- Requests from partner authorities' (of other/ third state, country of origin) for assistance in locating and returning a person and, vice versa, requests from NRW for

¹¹⁵ To accompany forced removals by air, PBL are formally assigned on business trips abroad, which the responsible Federal Police airport office has to apply for at the Federal Police Headquarters (Bundespolizeipräsidium) with perusal of the police duty station of the travelling PBL officer eight days in advance. Any subsequent authorisation to travel abroad includes the instruction to wear one's own civilian clothes (Bundespolizei 2016, p. 16).

support in these matters. Collaboration with the other country's authorities and (even if indirect) access to existing databases plays a role here.

- Rules set by countries of origin/ destination (e.g. concerning the accepted time of arrival, list of non-days on which no return flights are accepted);
- Observance of airline rules that, e.g., limit the number of forced returnees per scheduled flight;
- Advice on the growing complexity of relevant legal regulations in Germany's multi-level governance structure;
- Guidelines and codes of conduct for accompanying personnel during air deportations, e.g., Frontex Code of Conduct, Frontex-Reader, Best Rück Luft guideline of the Federal Police.

In addition, when discussing technology, interviewees with a working background in local government authorities claimed to be put in a very much down to earth approach with a need to improvise (*hemdsärmelig*), especially regarding digitalisation. One respondent pointed out that to date the federal system in Germany and the local autonomy in dealing with and implementing federal and state provisions have prevented the introduction of a nationwide specialised procedure (*Fachverfahren*) that every foreigners authority could work with. Instead, "every foreigners authority works with different specialised procedures" (interview, 22 July 2024) that are hardly compatible with each other, even in the same administrative district. Reasons for the lack of unified standards lie in the different resource allocation to municipalities and districts and the situational lack of digital infrastructure by default because it has not been considered and provided for in policy regulations. NRW seems to be trying to counteract the fragmentation and incompatibility of many local authorities' procedures by establishing new tools and exchange technologies with the newly introduced centralized institutions (ZABs, RKKs, etc.). For example, according to an MKFFI decree of 2021, the RKK can match planned charter measures with designated returnees from the area of responsibility of various ABHs in a common database (called 'AusreisePlanungStatistik', APS) and make suggestions for the inclusion of these persons in the upcoming charter flight to the ABHs suggesting the booking with ZFA, as well as report matches in parallel directly to ZFA (MKFFI, 2021, 2021b). While this will help to streamline and increase the efficiency of the immigration bureaucracy, which several interviewees expressed a desire for, it can also limit the agency of foreigners offices' staff.

5.4 Relationships of actors, materials and technologies in NRW's forced return migration infrastructure

5.4.1 Collaborations/ networks of facilitating and contesting actors

As analysed above (cf.5.2.2), the actors involved in NRW's forced removal infrastructure can be placed on a continuum between facilitation of and opposition to forced returns. The multi-level vertical collaborations and networks involving the different institutions of the state administration have been outlined in 5.2.1, and parallel existing institutions founded in the course of centralization efforts (to achieve higher effectiveness) have been pointed out. Beyond the state of NRW, these facilitating actors network with counterparts in or representatives of origin and destination countries as well as Frontex and federal institutions in Germany. Their work with subordinate agencies such as facility-management companies and private sector medical providers has shown how statecraft creates surveillance to establish deportability and

increase numbers for greater effectiveness of the forced removal regime. In the following, horizontal networks and collaborations between facilitating institutions and those actors who seek to ensure that forced removals comply with human rights are analysed as ‘bridging formats’. The second sub-section (ii.) provides a brief analysis of collaborations between the third category of actors on the continuum (cf. 5.2.2) who oppose forced removals and actively resist returns by offering support to those threatened with forced removal. In these collaborations, the involved activists and others form a network of social infrastructure.

a) Bridging formats

At the interface between the institutions that facilitate forced removals and those who seek to make forced returns more compliant with human rights, the analysis discovered several types of exchange activity, five of which are summarised in the following Table 4.

Table 4: *Bridging collaborations between state institutions and actors in favour of forced removal*

Activity type	Specific formats	Joint materials and databases
Different formats of Round Tables (RT): at municipal- and NRW-level	Municipal RT on human trafficking NRW-RT on forced removals Dialogue conference (<i>Dialogtagung</i>) Conference with state authorities (<i>Behördentagung</i>) Conference with BAMF (<i>BAMF-Tagung</i>)	Agendas, ‘tabling problems’ and issues
Informal agreement between churches and BAMF/ MKJFGFI about church asylum	Dossier procedure	Dossiers of church asylum seekers
Institutional watchdog interfaces ¹¹⁶	Forced removal monitoring at Düsseldorf airport with Forum Flughäfen in NRW (FFiNW) Advisory Board Forced Removal Detention Municipal integration councils Municipal advisory commission on immigration-related issues (local hardship commission)	Annual reports of Diakonie (2019-2024) Forum discussions Case management Consensus paper on ‘Stay perspectives’ (Unna) Local hardship commission case file sharing
Advocacy activities	Briefings with parliamentarians and parties in	Exchange of informed evidence about migrants’ situations and

¹¹⁶ Hardship commission and petitions committee of the NRW state parliament are not included here, because the members are mostly institutional or institutionally appointed representatives.

	state and federal parliament (closed-door) Networking among and referencing towards migrant support organisations in NRW and Germany	basic rights restrictions in current deportation regime Exchange of information, (re)sources, mutual referral
Cooperation between foreigners authorities and social councillors/ representatives of welfare organisations	Informal information sharing and pro-migrant solution-oriented case processing based on long-term established working and trust relations Co-optation of return counsellors in foreigners authorities and accommodation facilities	Case-file sharing

Interview partners from both camps of actors discussed in this section saw the establishment¹¹⁷ of formats such as the Round Tables and institutional watchdog interfaces as a positive development. At the sub-state level, some municipalities and counties have developed formats to bring together individuals concerned with human rights violations during forced removals with local government offices and have established different forums for exchange and consultation. In this context, ABHs are urged from above to establish and maintain intensive networks with civil society actors outside the local administration to increase external transparency and understanding of their actions and decisions.

b) People as infrastructure

Among the actors who actively oppose and resist the forced return of migrants, it is noticeable that they cannot rely on comparable financial and material resources and are usually hardly organised in the form of institutions; coordination among them is quite a challenge. This reflects the power relations in the prevailing forced removal regime in Germany. As a result, resistance only occasionally manifests itself publicly. The potential for micro-resistance lies in undermining existing practices by (un)doing them with a pro-‘immigrant’ and pro-‘integration’ stance, e.g. in legal counselling but also in conceptual work that seeks to change criminalizing and racializing discourses (e.g., about deservingness) and knowledge production about migration, its processes and effects.¹¹⁸

At the same time, those in the ‘opponent category of forced removals’ are often closer to those affected and obligated to leave than representatives of the two other categories identified in section 5.2-b. Activists and opponents of forced removals rely on horizontal social ties, social

¹¹⁷ Established in connection with the turn towards the so-called integrated return management (paradigm) in NRW in 2016 and centralization efforts in the field of forced removals introduced with the Asyl-Stufenplan 2018 (cf. 3.2).

¹¹⁸ According to Korvensyrjä (2018, p. 27), criminalizing racism “operates as a general suspicion against migrants and as state violence that leaves non-EU migrants in particular precarious and without rights and even drives them into premature death”.

mobilization for funding, intricate collaboration and temporary but productive encounters with migrants in need of support based on ideas of solidarity, thus creating a care infrastructure ‘of people’.¹¹⁹ They are concerned by the increasing and prolific racism of the increasingly extreme centre¹²⁰ of society in Germany and the dehumanisation of migrants through policymaking and the accompanying discourses.¹²¹

A few concrete examples will illustrate this: The already mentioned **church asylum** is a somewhat autonomous practice to avoid forced removals and to ensure that the asylum process is carried out in Germany. In recent years, it has gained in importance as a last resort to avoid forced removals (especially for Dublin-transfers) e.g., in view of the changes that have made it possible to forcibly remove people with serious illnesses and the overall more restrictive enforcement of coerced removals. Only maximum ten per cent of all church asylum cases are non-Dublin cases, mainly because the duration in Dublin cases is more predictable with the regular transfer period of six months (18 months in the worst case, cf. BAMF 2022a) that have to be endured before the asylum case is transferred to German authorities. Other church asylums might last years. The longest one interviewee referred to was about 13 to 14 years, which strains local support communities’ resources to high degree (interview, 22 May 2024). Whereas some 15 years ago, there were 20 or 30 church asylums in NRW, there were about 500 in 2023 and 160 by mid-2024.¹²² While official church representatives do not oppose forced removals per se but reject the allegations by some government representatives that granting church asylum would amount to civil disobedience and therefore not be acceptable, individual church community members often deviate from this line and rhetoric. The latter see nothing wrong with civil disobedience and claim that it is necessary if state and government actions can be corrected in this way; in fact, they see it as necessary and part of their humanitarian responsibility.

The two main ‘churches’ (Catholic and Protestant congregations) in Germany had come to an agreement with the BAMF in 2015¹²³ about the protection of individuals designated for Dublin

¹¹⁹ The notion alludes to Simone’s findings from urban peripheries worldwide about temporary encounters and horizontal ties constituting “a critical *infrastructure* for the endurance of a territory, a people, a community” (Simone 2021, p. 1343). Simone also observed that the upkeep of marginalized people’s networks is highly labour intensive (Simone 2004). For a recent recourse to the notion of ‘people as infrastructure’ in migration studies, see the special issue introduction of Müller and Tuitjer (2023).

¹²⁰ This diagnosis roots in the observation that the number of supporters of right-wing extremist attitudes in Germany has been steadily increasing. The most recent bi-annual report conducted by FES (2023) found that that parts of the centre of society are distancing themselves from democracy or have lost confidence in the functioning of institutions; related to (im)migration, 16 per cent have a negative attitude towards foreigners and 34 per cent believe that refugees only come to Germany to take advantage of the social system (Zick et al. 2023).

¹²¹ Interviews, 22 May 2024; 26, 31 July 2024; Conference Notes, 25 October 2024.

¹²² Interviews, 22 May 2024, 24 July 2024, 1 August 2024.

¹²³ In 2015, the BAMF had threatened to extend the time limits in Dublin cases to 18 months for church asylum, which appeared to be a huge burden for many church actors. Following negotiations and the conclusion of the non-binding procedural agreement on 24 February 2015, a department for the examination of hardship cases was set up in the BAMF bureaucratizing the entire procedure with obligatory dossiers that had to be submitted. Initially hosted by the quality control unit, this department moved to the Dublin section in 2016. With this move, the recognition rate fell drastically from about 80 per cent of recognised hardship cases that lead to the invocation of sovereignty clause/ transfer of their asylum procedure to Germany (*Selbsteintrittsrecht*) to about two and most recently 0.5 per cent. This meant that they would have to stay in church asylum until the end of the designated

transfers in church asylum via a dossier procedure. It is not a robust legal instrument but more of a tradition that is recognised by the BAMF and the authorities in Germany. That is why a person who is in church asylum is not considered to have absconded under the Dublin Regulation, because the authorities are informed of their whereabouts. In theory, since the person is not considered to be evading forced removal in legal terms, the forcible removal is possible at any time. This is important for the Dublin Regulation in that the transfer period is not stopped, and the aim of church asylum is to let it run out because then the asylum case is taken over by and conducted in Germany (BAMF 2022a).

However, church asylum only works if there is a sufficient support coalition of volunteers in the church community, administrative assistance by the churches' lawyers and higher bodies, and a support network beyond the church community in the wider municipality. The people involved have to organise and finance the entire stay of the church asylum seekers themselves, e.g., shelter, food, medical treatment, etc., and rely largely on personal networks. Some parishes in NRW have been providing church asylum for many years, sometimes on a large scale, with at least ten people in church asylum at any one time, and sometimes as many as 35 people at the same time.¹²⁴

In other cases of proactive opposition to forced removals, activists **provide advice** ('First Aid Deportation') and **organise protests**¹²⁵, e.g., at airports at the time of scheduled forced removal flights¹²⁶ (cf. Figure 8) or – although not reported in NRW – by blocking roads to and runways at airports, e.g. in Berlin. In many cases, individual cases are defended by different constellations of support coalitions, consisting, for example, of employers, friends, lawyers, local press, schools, refugee rights organizations and welfare organizations. The collaboration of activists with like-minded lawyers has been productive and, in several cases has helped forcibly returned families and individuals to return to Germany within months. These actions, however, do not address the structural impasses of the forced removal regime, nor does the nevertheless important work of counselling and advice, e.g. by migrant (self-)organizations. Social media and internet platforms play an important role in the distribution of (often self-compiled) information material, e.g., lists of supporting institutions and information about rights and processes in the German asylum and return regime, but also for mobilising donations to continue voluntary work for migrants or support their stay. To be 'successful' and

transfer period and hope that during this period, the authorities will respect the church premises and refrain from breaking church asylum as agreed in a so-called 'clearing agreement' in 1995, which was confirmed to be respected at least for the duration of the dossier procedure in 2016 and 2023 (in NRW through state edicts: MKJFGFI, 2023; Ministerium für Inneres und Kommunales des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen, 2017). However, several cases and an increasing number have been recorded where ABHs demanded the dissolution of the church asylum after the dossier was rejected and sought to forcibly remove the person. Critics do not approve of this agreement and view it as a government technique to 'domesticate' and control church asylum.

¹²⁴ It is the only church asylum case in the respective district jurisdiction of this church, with 35 asylum seekers at one time. It costs 150,000 EUR a year. Reportedly, neighbouring parishes contribute to the funding and refrain from providing church asylum in their own church premises.

¹²⁵ In a latest incident, though also not in NRW, different civil society organisations (Refugee Council Lower Saxony, Seebrücke, Netzwerk gegen Abschiebung) protested against the forced removal of 47 Iraqi nationals from Hanover airport (Lower Saxony) on 17 February 2025. The returnees came from 11 federal states. Cf. Frankfurter Rundschau 2025.

¹²⁶ Cf. as trackable on this platform: <https://noborderassembly.blackblogs.org/deportation-alarm/#tracking>

prevent forced removals, the opponents have to mobilize utilitarian narratives about shortages of skilled workers in Germany and the emphasis on a stay and integration perspective. Thereby they allude to already existing legal provisions (temporary termination of the obligation to leave because of vocational training or employment, cf. FN 13) that can be employed within the scope of assessment each foreigners office theoretically has at its disposal. Similarly, but at a different level, **strategic litigation efforts** aim to obtain legal precedent rulings to specify and change laws and have a more transformative influence by strengthening migrants' rights according to existing international law and provisions.

Figure 8: *Information-sharing*

5.4.2 Tensions/ oppositions of actors

The identification of three categories of actors on the continuum between facilitation of and resistance to forced returns (cf. 5.2.2) incorporates an inherent goal discrepancy between the involved actors. It is most pronounced between those eager to implement the law 'in its pure form' vs. those seeing the law as part of the problem and scrutinizing or challenging it. This conflict unfolds against the backdrop of extreme political pressure and entails several dimensions, the three most relevant of which are elaborated in the following sections. Importantly, the legalistic attitude in Germany is strong, i.e., in a constitutional state such as Germany, government authorities usually identify with the principle of legality and public authorities self-define through sticking to strict implementation of the law, for which each step requires a legal substantiation.

Besides, the discrepancy in objectives between non-state actors has already been pointed out in section 5.2-b above. The tension here revolves around the different degree of opposition to forced returns. Put simply, there are two camps of objectors: one is generally in favour of forced removals as a means of enforcing the law but wants them to be conducted in a humane manner. The other camp rejects forced removals and sees the law as part of a problematic power assemblage that excludes migrants and denies fundamental rights to people it

categorises as not belonging. In doing so, the law constructs people as ‘others’ and deportable through the crafting of racializing and criminalizing legal provisions.

- a) Conflict of interest between regulation and control vs. immigration and integration

With the change of federal government in 2021 and subsequent legal integration-oriented provisions, **Germany’s foreigners authorities were mandated more clearly to become ‘Welcoming authorities’** (*Willkommensbehörde/n*)¹²⁷, one major characteristic of which was to help foreign nationals to secure residence status by actively pointing out ways to achieve this and making appropriate decisions at the authority’s discretion. This expectation created an inherent contradiction because **at the same time states and – on their behalf – ABHs across the country were also mandated to increase forced removal numbers**, following the inherent logic of the populist narrative of an enforcement gap.¹²⁸ As one interviewee representing an ABH put it, “Overall the legal situation (*Gesetzeslage*) is very ambivalent. [We end up in a situation where on] Mondays we deport, Tuesdays we welcome new refugees, Wednesdays we assign citizenships, Thursdays we conduct our information evening/ Round Table and Friday we file decisions about asylum applications (*Erteilungstag*). The strategy of the government is not really clear” (interview, 25 September 2024).

However, this conflict of interest is not only an inherent tension within single ABHs (where return is only one of many policy implementation fields), but also among ABHs, leading to different decision outcomes in one jurisdiction compared to another within the same state. While some – depending on the outlook/attitude (*Haltung*) of the administrative head – work in line with an integration-oriented policy, others see themselves as strict law enforcers of restrictive policy priorities. This has several consequences for how they do (not) use their

¹²⁷ The idea and terminology of foreigners authorities becoming ‘welcoming authorities’ date back to 2012 and were actively pushed by the BAMF from 2013-15 through a pilot programme involving ten foreigners authorities in Germany (among them Cologne and Essen in NRW) with the aim of becoming more service oriented and thus supporting a welcome culture that facilitates integration on the one hand and Germany’s competitiveness in the international recruitment of skilled workers on the other (cf., e.g., Walther 2013). The initial programme focused predominantly on the internal reorganization of the ABHs and preceded the large-scale immigration from 2014 onwards, which led to a further expansion of the concepts of welcoming culture and welcoming authority. However, these did not develop further because they were not being actively replicated and both concepts were only substantiated when pro-integration legal regulations came into force. Interviewees from ABHs linked renewed strong demand from above to become welcoming authorities with the change of the federal government in 2021. In the words of an ABH-representative who spoke about unlearning and re-orientation among his staff, “So I can also tell a member of my staff who has perhaps been here for 20 years – these colleagues exist, by the way –, who has learnt up to 2018, 2019 ‘Protect this country, the regulatory character is the highest’. Horst Seehofer [the Minister of the Interior 2018-21] is celebrating the fact that 70 people are being deported for his 70th birthday.* And then, only a few years later, Nancy Faeser [Minister of the Interior 2021-25] comes along and says in an interview that ‘immigration authorities must become welcome authorities’. And she says that on a Friday and it is to be implemented by Monday. Of course we can’t do that. We need a bit of guidance for what we do. We try hard and the legislator doesn’t necessarily help us” (interview, 22 July 2024). *The statement simplified the fact that it was Seehofer’s 69th birthday that he linked to the forced removal of 69 Afghans via charter on the same day during a press conference in 2018 where he presented his ministry’s ‘Masterplan Migration’ (Der Spiegel 2018).

¹²⁸ One report formulates poignantly that personnel of ABH have since to live (with) a cognitive dissonance (Schlee et al. 2023, p. 41).

discretionary powers of interpretation and action with regard to the legal provisions concerning forced removals of persons designated as obliged to leave Germany.

The **contrasting attitudinal orientations (*Haltung*/ ‘cultures’) are tangible** when, for example, the requests (*Härtefallersuchen*) of the hardship commission are not complied with by the ABHs concerned or when they demand the dissolution of church asylums after rejecting the dossier of the person, although the MKJFGFI recommends toleration. At the time of research, three church asylum cases were pending in one NRW district, and the responsible ZAB threatened to evict the people whose dossiers/ hardship applications had been rejected by the BAMF. They argued that they were legally obliged to enforce the BAMF’s decision and that the churches were not respecting the agreement by continuing to grant church asylum.¹²⁹ Given this unprecedented level of escalation, one interviewee stated: “I fear that this could lead to a dam breaking, that the four other central ZABs, or the municipal ABHs, could jump on this bandwagon and adapt the same understanding of the law or the same interpretation of their own room for manoeuvre. And then, of course, we would have a very big problem” (interview, 22 May 2024).

Another effect of this conflict of interests can be seen in the contradiction between the omnipresent narrative that all state institutions and in particular the ABHs are completely overburdened¹³⁰ and the seemingly unreasonable efforts (investment of resources like time, energy, personnel, money) that they make to track down and forcibly remove people, without regard to hardship, such as in church asylum cases or in the case of people who are seriously ill. The principle reflected in this enormous resource-demanding efforts to accomplish returns – whether assisted or enforced removals – shows that **the principle of proportionality is suspended and replaced by the principle ‘whatever it takes’ or ‘at any cost’**. Importantly, the whole effort has to do with the fact that the authorities (at several administrative levels) are trying to **adjust to the unpredictability resulting from the uncertainty about the possible reactions/actions of the designated returnees**. Therefore, several backup systems must be maintained¹³¹, which are activated in case of need (e.g. resistance), comprising, e.g., the need for specially trained personnel at the ABHs and further, the Federal Police. This perceived need for adjustment due to uncertainty motivates also the increasing reliance on central return management for both assisted and forced removals. As a result, resources are prioritized wrong and instead of sought-for-effectiveness, **the entire return machinery becomes more ineffective** – not least because these backup mechanisms seek to impact the designated returnees in the first place instead of steering return migration via, e.g., migration diplomacy measures.

¹²⁹ According to rumours, a new, unpublished state edict (as of mid-December 2024) on the handling of church asylum cases will only oblige the ABH to deport a church asylum seeker if the BAMF directly requests it. This could lead to any ZAB or local ABH to challenge the state in court, as this involves a politically motivated violation of existing law from their point of view (which can be captured as noted in a different context, ‘We are working on the basis of valid law’ [*Wir bewegen uns auf dem Boden des Rechts*]). Interview, 25 September 2024.

¹³⁰ In a similar narrative, the state police and Federal Police are overburdened given, e.g. the new border guarding provisions and the above-mentioned fact that those qualified as air escorts do this outside the purview of their ‘terrestrial’ police duty (cf. Decker 2023).

¹³¹ We owe this hint at backup systems to compensate for uncertainties due to designated returnees’ actions to Norbert Cyrus, one of the scholarly reviewers of an early draft of this Working Paper.

b) Tension between legal provisions and implementation: The theory-practice gap

The tension between legal provisions and their practical enforcement or implementation cuts right across regulation and openness is, i.e., many interviewees hinted at a gap between the theory and practice of forced returns. This is also related to the **unclear political positioning of state and government actors**, the partial lack of complete information on state edicts and the lack of transparency on how implementation is enforced. Documentation is rarely fully provided. The impression gained from the interviews and the study of secondary literature is that in many cases, the legal framework is not fully adhered to, so that infringements of fundamental rights and human rights violations may not be detected and addressed because either details or entire incidents are underreported – or not reported at all. Sub-state administrative institutions such as the local ABHs are mandated to implement laws and edicts they sometimes perceive to exist entirely for symbolic policymaking where the state or federal ministry just wants to demonstrate voters its ability to act. However, they see that there is no clear legal backing for the resulting measures. At the same time, they do **not feel included in feedback loops and have no voice in advising on better policies** that would address operational challenges on the ground. In the third quarter of 2024, a major source of frustration for ABH return divisions was the legislating politicians calling for more forced removals while the same politicians joined the scandalizing tenor of critics in single forced removal cases in their own voting districts if opportune. Representatives of ABHs expressed in interviews that they were in the unfortunate position of having to enforce the decisions taken by ‘others’ elsewhere without being able to influence them. In another example, tensions were felt when families with children were picked up at night for forced removal, which usually leads to public outcry. In this case, the local county administrator (*Landrat*) scrutinized the ABH in his jurisdiction and asked them to stop this practice or to organise pick-up between 6 am to 6 pm; but the ABH argued that they had to act according to the timeframes of the destination countries or otherwise the administrative and logistical effort would be disproportionate.¹³² In the words of the ABH representative, “That’s why we face huge problems in doing justice to all of them. And so, in some cases, **forced removals may not be feasible** in case of doubt” (interview, 25 September 2024).

Interface institutions such as the Airport Forum NRW (FFiN) and as an element of this, the forced removal observers at Düsseldorf airport have been established as sources and platforms to discuss implementation gaps and bring basic points to the attention of the wider public, e.g., through the published annual reports (Diakonie 2019-24)¹³³, and to inform policymaking. Although the publications are selective and a product of compromises among all stakeholders in FFiN, including representatives of the Federal Police and the MKJFGFI, the deliberations and findings provide a solid basis for **reviewing some of the guiding frameworks for**

¹³² Using the example of a Dublin deportation (‘transfers’) to Italy, if enforced outside the timeframe 6pm-6am, it would have to be changed to a transfer by land via Austria and include a range of organizational and logistical challenges, e.g., including handing over the children to the local youth welfare office at overnight stay locations, parents’ temporary confinement and its organization, the employment of additional administrative and security personnel.

¹³³ The forced removal observers of Diakonie in NRW publish coordinated reports (*abgestimmte Berichte*), meaning that all members of FFiN have agreed to the rationale and content of reporting on an annual basis.

the enforcement of forced removals, such as the Checklist NRW. However, no changes have been made to it since 2016 (interviews, 7 May 2024, 1 August 2024).

c) Tension between state institutions and supporters of migrants

The ambivalent role of government institutions was also evident when interviewees discussed incidences where **critics of the current forced removal regime and its often racialized and criminalized discourse were also subjected to criminalizing discourse**.¹³⁴ The term anti-deportation industry (*Anti-Abschiebeindustrie*) became a famous dictum (and the so-called ‘non-word’ of the year 2018) after the leader of the parliamentary group of the Bavarian conservative Christian Social Union (CSU) borrowed it from Hungary’s President Viktor Orbán to introduce it into the German political debate in 2018. His aim was to defame people who provide legal support to rejected asylum seekers and who review forced removals through legal channels as a way of standing up for human rights and the dignified treatment of refugees. The dictum implies that committed people sabotage the efforts of the rule of law and jeopardise public safety because they also defend criminals and earn a lot of money with this kind of legal representation. As one politician from the sister party CDU (Christian Democratic Union) elaborated, “There is a broad phalanx [suggesting a coherent bloc of people], starting with politicians from the Greens and the Left, social workers, aid organisations and lawyers, who try to extend the right to asylum very far and in some cases do not accept its limits when they try to prevent the enforcement of forced removal orders” (Prange de Oliveira 2018). While this example demonstrates how the political discourse in Germany has been shifting to the right in terms of language and content for several years now, there is evidence that the idea of an industry that makes money from the existence of refugees and their ‘administration’ in Germany might rather fit the operators of accommodation facilities (Fischer et al., 2024; Uebelacker & Spinrath, 2024), medical service providers (Funk, 2019) and security companies (Oulios 2016, p. 284).

Within state institutions and/ or between them and subordinate bodies or organisations sponsored by public institutions, tensions over perceived and actual position(alitie)s in support of refugees or migrants designated returnees or ‘clients’ are palpable in the field of return counselling. Return counsellors in non-governmental organizations have to defend their work against scrutiny from the foreigners authorities and state institutions on the one hand and the scepticism of civil society representatives on the other. This situation was captured in an earlier interview with a Bavarian return counsellor; however, it is revealing with regard to the (in-)ability to influence or possibly prevent an ordered return and reflects what several other respondents from NRW reported, too. The interviewee stated, “From their point of view [the foreigners authorities], we were always the ones cuddling up to the refugees, and from the point of view of the refugee councils, it was ‘they are the extended arm of the foreigners authorities, the pigs’ (that’s how they say it here). But we have managed to be recognised by both of them today; they know we do our job well; we don’t wind up anyone. But, Mrs X, I also tell you that we live from compromises, not just me, all return counsellors. I can’t get anyone a residence permit. If I beg for more time, then

¹³⁴ See also Korvensyrjä (2024a) for an analysis how protest and solidarity among migrants related to Dublin removals has been criminalized in southern Germany.

it's a matter of a few weeks, maybe months, but not for long, you can push it but you can't push it too far, you have to remain honest" (interview, 16 July 2021).

In the past, representative civil society organisations have, for example, launched a flyer campaign aimed at Federal Police officers who accompany forced removals by air as escorts, appealing directly to their personal conscience, saying among other things: "**Do not be willing executors of a merciless forced removal machinery!** As Federal Police officers, you are expected to implement the consequences of a repressive asylum policy that fails to respect human rights. Participation in forced removals 'air escorts' is voluntary for Federal Police officers. This means that everyone is free to decide whether to volunteer for this humanly bitter and stressful task" (Komitee für Grundrechte, n.d., p. 2). According to one media report, more extreme forms of opposition against air escort officers were recorded when wheel nuts on service vehicles were loosened in protest against forced removals. Moreover, Federal Police officers involved in forced removals have been visited and threatened at their private homes by family members of removed persons (van Boetticher, 2024a). The latter incidents exemplify antagonistic escalation where protests have turned into personal attacks and threats against government officials by affected migrants and their supporters – in a development that is unlikely to reduce societal tensions.

Another major source of tension is the **lack of transparency of state institutions'** which non-state actors complain about in several spheres of interaction. This relates mainly to the **withholding of information** in different contexts. In church asylum cases, for example, the BAMF does not inform the person granted asylum on church premises about the termination of the time limit for their Dublin transfer – which would mean the invocation of the sovereignty clause and the rightful stay in Germany for the time being as the asylum application could be submitted here now – or its possible extension (from six to 18 months). Instead, the BAMF expects the person to inquire about it personally and does not allow a third party to do so, citing reasons of data protection and data security, even though the information does not have to be passed on to the third person but the asylum seeker. As a result, there is a risk that church asylum cases are artificially prolonged by months sometimes due to non-communication by the BAMF. Informed observers see this as a strategy to systematically delay the procedure and to cause additional hardship for the migrant and their support community (interview, 22 May 2024).

In cases where enquiries, e.g. about the best interests of the child in the enforcement of forced removals, are directed at local municipal administrations, they often tend to **hide behind walls of responsibility diffusion**, meaning that they claim to not be competent to answer a certain request because something has moved outside their jurisdiction. However, they are also unable to say who could give answers instead (interview, 2 July 2024). Conversely, municipal and county administrations may publish excessive information on single forced removal cases when it is in their interest, e.g. to justify a certain harsh measure. This was reportedly the case after an investigation in a NRW county council into an unlawful forced removal of a violent offender (*Intensivstraftäter*), which was not suspended in the process but terminated in the destination country. The official document released online by the authority – and publicly available for several days – did not only contain the personal data of the forcibly removed person but also all the details of his criminal record in an attempt to justify the enforcement despite the lack of the court decision. This was undoubtedly a clear violation of fundamental rights and data protection standards.

Another type of example relates to the **neglect of data collection, documentation, and potential learning from statistical analysis**, e.g. in the NRW forced removal detention facility in Büren. Reportedly, the lack of documentation of, for example, the number of suicide attempts or self-harm during the stay gives the impression that there is no related problem and prevents general external monitoring. There is also reportedly no record of the number of individuals placed in solitary confinement and the length of time they spend there, and investigative journalists are not allowed to speak to the detainees. A request by an NGO to systematically compile the relevant figures from different administrative files based on the Freedom of Information Act (*Informationsfreiheitsgesetz*¹³⁵) was answered with the notice that the fulfilment of the research request would require a fee of 18,000 EUR. In a parallel development, the MKJFGFI did not fulfil its obligation to have the Forced Removal Detention Enforcement Act (*Abschiebungshaftvollzugsgesetz*)¹³⁶ evaluated by the end of 2022, which could have helped to identify areas for improvement.

FragDenStaat¹³⁷ has become an invaluable tool for sceptics and critics of the forced removal infrastructure to demand transparency from government institutions, e.g. by requesting the publication of government edicts, assessments, official guidelines used by authorities, and documentation. Here are just three examples: Besides the already mentioned publication of the Best-Rück-Luft guideline (“Provisions on the forced removal of foreign nationals by air”) of the Federal Police (Bundespolizei, 2016), an investigation was launched into the MKJFGFI’s plans for a second forced removal detention facility, in particular about the possible location, justification and funding requirements (FragDenStaat, 2022). Finally, the *Bundestag* was forced to publish a classified document entitled ‘Medical (forced) treatment during forced removals’ in 2019 (FragDenStaat, 2019). Moreover, the **parliamentary inquiries on immigration and return matters put forward by the party Die Linke (The Left)** in the German Parliament since 2006 have proven to be a significant source of transparency and knowledge production about German asylum politics. The detailed data published at the request of this party have been used by lawyers, refugee councils, media, scholars and even the Federal Constitutional Court and the Federal Audit Office (Tränhardt, 2024) to introduce different angles to public discourses on enforcement gaps, etc., and to defend the interests of asylum seekers, immigrants and designated returnees in the various contexts.

The analysis of the tensions and contradictions between the actors and institutions involved shows that the forced removal infrastructure with its inherent programmatic contradictions (welcoming and removing at the same time) is highly political and can be easily instrumentalized by institutions and other actors for their own ends and short-term assertiveness. However, in the longer term, the frictions that have been unleashed can be seen in the performativity of regulatory institutions that aim to demonstrate their capacity for

¹³⁵ Cf. BMI (2005), Ministerium des Innern des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen (2001) (NRW-Ministry of the Interior).

¹³⁶ According to §59.4 AhaftVolzG NRW, a report about the effects of the law was to be submitted to state parliament until 31 December 2022. Cf. Ministerium für Inneres und Kommunales des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen (2015).

¹³⁷ The project operates an internet platform designed to enable anyone to exercise their right of access to official information. Requests can be made to German (and recently also European) authorities on the basis of various (state, national) freedom of information laws, cf. <https://fragdenstaat.de/>

enforcement, in the significance of non-doing/s (not using the discretionary powers to avoid forced removals where this would have been possible, e.g. in church asylum cases or following the recommendations of the hardship commission; non-transparency) and the de facto abandonment of ABHs by the regulatory authorities in the implementation of ambivalent legislation concerning forced returns risks further discontent, frustration and an increase in polarization with clear negative effects on German societal cohesion. ABHs and migrant supporters from civil society, as well as designated returnees themselves suffer from withheld information and non-transparent processes. ABHs are stuck between a rock and a hard place with the dual mandate described above as an expression of a conflict of interest, which corresponds to and partly translates into tensions between legal provisions and implementation (theory practice gap). Moreover, the ambivalent regulations and individual attitudes communicated by the institutions (e.g. politicians defaming supporters of immigrants) evoke a picture of a fragmented institutional and ideological landscape which is more of a moving target than a fixed pole that could be subjected to and be receptive of scrutiny by the pro-integrationist actors of the second and third categories (cf. Figure 7). It is worth noting that this has led to mistrust between some of the key stakeholders and, in some cases, to significant fluctuations in personnel (especially also in assisted return¹³⁸) and resignations, i.e. job changes.

5.4.3 Financial flows between institutions, actors and networks¹³⁹

The different types of institutions and actors (cf. 6.1) are partly connected through funding, in particular the first and second actor categories (facilitators and humane removal protagonists). This could be interpreted as another manifestation of the peculiar dissonance underlying the NRW immigration authorities' logic with its emphasis on increased returns and integration at the same time. Then again, one could argue that it follows its own inherent logic based on racializing and criminalizing selectivity, which is created and embodied by the current immigration and return migration infrastructure set-up.

All the costs associated with forced removals are born by the state of NRW. This applies, first, to the financing of the various entities of the state administration and state police (where necessary), translators, commissioned assessments (health¹⁴⁰, language), and embassy/consulate hearings. The latter are partly co-financed by Frontex (Deutscher Bundestag, 2024d). The budget for return migration is part of the overall budget of the MKJFGFI; however, costs incurred by actions of the state police and SEK-forces are borne by the NRW-Ministry of the Interior. Expenditure has increased annually. While NRW allocated 16 million EUR for the ZABs in 2017, the amount nearly tripled to 46.96 million EUR in the MKJFGFI's

¹³⁸ The 'starving' of non-governmental refugee return counselling (besides other counselling programmes) effected through cuts to the financial volume of the programme (2021) and its annual and ever more delayed release limits continuities, risks a permanent loss of expertise, and reduces the possibility to overcome distrust, not to mention the lack of decentralized services that can be offered at local level. Instead, it was decided to expand governmental return counselling at ZAB-level.

¹³⁹ Activities, databases and material flows foreseen by the WP-structure to be analysed in this section, have been covered above in 5.4-a-i/ ii.

¹⁴⁰ Physicians' fees for involvement and 'escort' of a forced removal amounted to 90 EUR/ hour in 2014 in the state of Berlin, in case the forced removal operation had to be cancelled on short notice, the doctor received a lump sum of 800 EUR (cf. Funk 2019).

financial plan 2023 (Abschiebungsreporting NRW, 2023). In addition, the financial plan foresees 17.8 million EUR for forced removals and removal support in 2023 and 12.4 million EUR for the funding of ‘voluntary’ return (MKJFGFI, 2022, pp. 48, 49).¹⁴¹

Due to the dual focus on integration and return, the MKJFGFI also funds many of the non-governmental, civil society actors that are involved in counselling and advocacy work as well as activities to make forced return procedures more humane. The large welfare agencies, the Refugee Council and a diverse range of counselling centres (specialising in victims of human trafficking, psycho-social counselling or legal counselling) also receive public money.¹⁴² However, they try, more or less successfully, to diversify their funding sources and rely on a spectrum of donations, e.g. from Germany-wide lobby organisations such as ProAsyl.

For assisted return, the largest contribution by the state NRW is maintaining the counselling infrastructure (details see above). Non-state return counselling providers apply for funding from the social counselling programme for displaced persons run by the MKJFGFI, which has become increasingly difficult in recent years. In 2024, the Ministry shifted its funding strategy, giving less support to the non-state actors and more to the ZAB providers of assisted return, especially with a view to assisted returns from state-run shelters such as ZUEs. Unlike in some other German states, funding sources for non-state return counselling in NRW are not (yet) diversified and dependency on the state programme is high. Sometimes, local institutions such as municipal social welfare offices or district governments carry certain costs, such as necessary travel within Germany or medical assistance during assisted return. The bulk of costs for return and reintegration assistance is covered by federal and other NRW-external sources: costs for REAG/GARP are covered by AMIF with co-funding from the federal and some state budgets (including NRW), costs for EURP by Frontex. Along with other German states, NRW contributes co-funding to some preparatory measures for assisted return and reintegration projects (operated by GIZ) in Kosovo and Albania. In the annual financial plan of the MKJFGFI, funds allocated to support return projects total 3.56 million EUR in 2023 (Landtag NRW 2024, p. 1).¹⁴³ These are intended to cover the costs of supporting projects for assisted returns (3.51 million EUR)¹⁴⁴ as well as 53,000 EUR for the Diakonisches Werk of the Protestant Church in the Rhineland (Diakonie RWL e.V.) for monitoring forced removals (Abschiebungsbeobachtung im Forum Flughäfen).

¹⁴¹ For the ten main countries of destination, the federal government has covered travel costs and medical costs for persons returning ‘voluntarily’, i.e., assisted, in 2023, amounting to 1.7 million EUR; federal costs for financial support of returnees for the ten main countries of destination amounted to 1.6 million EUR (Deutscher Bundestag 2024, p. 2). Background note: Five per cent of the REAG/GARP programme costs are financed by federal and five per cent by state funds, the remaining 90 per cent are covered by the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF).

¹⁴² For example, the annual budget for 2023 and 2024 included 418,100 EUR in support of the office of the NRW Refugee Council and a complaints officer at the forced removal detention centre in Büren. Cf. Budget Title 684 40, <https://www.haushalt.fm.nrw.de/daten/hh2024.ges/daten/pdf/2024/hh07/kap090.pdf>, p. 136.

¹⁴³ Federal budget expenditures for (assisted) return preparation measures amounted to 3.98 million EUR between 2020 and 2024 (Deutscher Bundestag 2024, p. 7).

¹⁴⁴ Funded projects and organisations encompassed: REAG/GARP run by IOM, REAG/GARP 2.0 by BAMF, URA Kosovo by BAMF, Brückenkomponente Albanien/ BAMF, ZIRF-Counselling/ IOM, IntegPlan VIII/ Micado Migration gGmbH, and IntegPlan Einzelfallförderung/ Micado Migration gGmbH (Landtag NRW 2024, p. 2).

Interface bodies rely on mixed funding sources. For example, the petitions committee of the state parliament (financed by the latter), the hardship commission (under the MKJFGFI and financed by it), the Forum Airports in NRW (including the forced removal observers at Düsseldorf airport mentioned in the previous paragraph) and the Advisory Board Forced Removal Detention are co-financed by the three protestant churches in NRW.¹⁴⁵ The latter also provide funding for the various activities of their welfare organisation wings (Diakonie branches), co-finance, e.g., the Refugee Council NRW and the project Abschiebungsreporting NRW as an important lobbying organisation against forced returns. In contrast, the provision of church asylum is not institutionally funded by the Churches of either denomination; church asylum is organized and financed by the members of the local parish alone. The church administration only offers legal advice and provides for a lawyer, if necessary.¹⁴⁶

The costs incurred by the various agencies of the NRW state administrations for preparation, pick-up and airport transfer are borne by the state of NRW. Once the person is handed over at the airport, responsibility passes to the Federal Police (Federal Ministry of the Interior) and the federal budget. Collective charter flights are funded, organized and accompanied by Frontex, whereas the Federal Police accompanies forced removals via scheduled flight or national charter.¹⁴⁷ The costs incurred to cover special expenditures for Federal Police air escorts' international travel amounted to 6.5 million EUR in 2023; the corresponding budget allocation for 2024 foresaw 7.25 million EUR (Pöls & Schulze 2024)¹⁴⁸, the costs incurred amounted to 7.44 million EUR (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p. 17).

In non-Dublin cases, where forced returnees have cash, it is confiscated as a cash security payment/ security deposit (*Sicherheitsleistung*) to compensate for the forced removal costs. Reportedly, two per cent of all who were forcibly removed were charged some amount because they were found to carry more than the immediate subsistence need with them.¹⁴⁹ The costs charged include any previous detention in custody pending forced removal¹⁵⁰, the personnel

¹⁴⁵ The catholic church as an institution finances counselling centres etc. through its welfare organization Caritas (interview, 24 July 2024).

¹⁴⁶ Local church communities, can, of course request assistance from semi-public charities including the church-financed ones Diakonie and Caritas. However, these do not offer the coverage of shelter, living, medical cost etc. but might advise on logistical support and referral to other support infrastructure.

¹⁴⁷ Frontex relies on a pool of EU Member states' security and police forces qualified for the different tasks in the enforcement process of forced removals, such as escorts, escort leaders, monitors. Thus, Frontex personnel on collective charters might include Federal Police personnel seconded to Frontex for the mission, albeit, according to one interviewee, Germany does only have few ('three to four') members of the Federal Police who are in the Frontex Monitors Pool (Interview, 7 May 2024).

¹⁴⁸ These costs cover extra-payments for assignments abroad; they are paid on top of the regular salary.

¹⁴⁹ As individuals and families who are forcibly removed usually have no cash reserves, at the time of writing, they are provided with cash (so-called *Handgeld*) to cover their immediate needs during the journey and upon arrival. Cf. above, FN 90. Although the costs incurred by the forced returnee are legally provided for in Sect. 66 of the Residence Act (AufenthG), it seems to be at the discretion of the border guards whether or not to charge them, and if so, with what amount. The costs of forced removal remain relevant if a forcibly removed person applies for re-entry visa at a later date. The authority responsible for the previous forced removal will then issue a notification of the total costs incurred, which must be paid for re-entry. Cf. Rose & Schießl 2024, p. 100.

¹⁵⁰ According to one informed interviewee, the daily rate charged for forced removal detention is 241 EUR (interview, 23 July 2024).

costs of the enforcement authorities involved, any fees for a passport replacement document, possible costs for doctors or even for the locksmith service that the authorities used to gain access to their home, plus the costs for the flight. A ticket for a scheduled flight to the Western Balkans, for example, could cost 300 EUR, whereas a collective charter flight could cost up to 500,000 EUR including all involved expenses.¹⁵¹ As Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 100) point out: “This often results in a sum of many thousands or even tens of thousands of Euros for a single forced removal.” A special type of charter for a maximum of four returnees seems to be particularly expensive; in the course of 2024, three such charter flights were organized from German airports (not including NRW) which forcibly returned a total of five persons, accompanied by 20 Federal Police officers. The cost of only the aircraft was 102,085 EUR for a flight to Lebanon, 33,085 EUR to Slovakia, and 137,585 to Kenya (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025, p. 15). Then again, a most recent charter flight from NRW, which returned four Syrian and three Afghan men to Bulgaria (Dublin-Transfer) in a regular but empty aircraft with a capacity of 220 passengers, is said to have cost around 200,000 EUR.¹⁵²

5.4.4 Implementation gaps between different actors’ agendas and actions

Implementation gaps relate to (a) the practical enforcement of forced removals, given the limited monitoring and structural overburdening of foreigners authorities, (b) the preconditions in the NRW context where minimum standards are lacking on the one hand and overly restrictive regulations exist on the other, paralleled by a lack of sincerity, impartiality and transparency, and an outsourcing of responsibility, and (c) the federal level frameworks as a norm-setting context (‘the bigger picture’) where we observe legislative hyperactivity without effect, which partly collides with the autonomy of local government.

a) Gaps in practical enforcement

Monitoring. The above analysis revealed several shortcomings in the practical enforcement of the entire return process, from the moment of pick-up to the handover in the destination country. One example of this is the full enforcement of the forced removal despite the existence of a court-sanctioned emergency appeal requiring the stopping of the removal and reverse

¹⁵¹ Rose and Schießl (2024, p. 98) document the costs borne by Frontex for two collective charter flights (for forced removals from six to eight German states) from NRW and one from Leipzig, ranging from 104,080 EUR to Albania and Kosovo, to 278,000 EUR to Ghana and 445,000 EUR from Leipzig to Pakistan. However, these costs only covered the aircraft. For a realistic cost calculation, the personnel costs of between 55 and 75 Federal Police officers in these concrete cases (accompanying 21 to 61 deportees) must be added. According to a foreigners authority representative, the most expensive forced removal of an individual he had ever witnessed (albeit years ago), was to Brazil at a cost of 18,000 EUR (interview, 25 September 2024). By contrast, in 2023, the city of Wuppertal organised a single charter for one person from Mauritania, a converted Christian with no criminal record, at a cost of 114,085 EUR (Rose & Schießl 2024, pp. 158-160). For a collection of other media reports on charters ranging from 30,000 EUR up to almost 200,000 EUR, see Pöls & Schulze 2024.

¹⁵² This information was mentioned in a news agency report on a debate in the NRW state parliament on a forced removal flight from NRW on 11 February 2025, that is shortly before the German federal elections on 23 February, where opposition politicians (AfD, FDP) scandalised the return as pre-election PR-show while representatives of the state coalition and Social Democrats defended the forced removal measure, emphasizing that it showed the state’s ability to act. Moreover, it was reported that, as a new development since the Solingen-attack in August 2024 (committed by an assailant who should have been forcibly removed to Bulgaria), charter flights to Bulgaria have become possible since November 2024; however reportedly limited to two charter options per month with a maximum of ten people (regardless of the size of the aircraft), cf. Zeit Online 2025.

return of the forced returnee to Germany. So far, monitoring has only taken place at the airport Düsseldorf – and even here only sporadically and selectively (mainly in charter flight cases) instead of being carried out in a standardised manner in all cases of forced removals. The other measures, i.e., pick-up, transfer, air transport¹⁵³, and handover in the place of destination are not monitored, which means that there is no documentation of occurrences that could violate or have already violated the fundamental rights of forced returnees. Moreover, the airport observers are limited in their observations and analysis beyond the mere documentation of what they see happening during the handling procedure at the airport, e.g. they have no access to the files of the forced returnees and are not mandated to intervene in the course of the procedure at all. This undermines the legal protection (*Rechtsschutz*) of the forced returnees as they are usually not in a position to have a decision or procedure reviewed by legal experts or the court, e.g., in case of family separation or any other errors in the process. As forced returnees are ‘gone’ once they have been handed over to the authorities of the destination state and sometimes even before, if the court-ordered forced removal suspension is ignored by the escorting personnel in individual cases, an alternative to counter the incapacitation of designated returnees would be to provide a mandatory lawyer (*Pflichtanwalt*) for the practical enforcement process (interview, 2 July 2024). Other gaps were identified in the lack of special officers or permanent contacts for vulnerable groups at the airports (as well as in Dublin-offices and authorities), in particular for minors, people who are ill, victims of human trafficking and women. The non-announcement of Dublin returns is problematic for these groups as they are taken by surprise and are less able to defend their rights.

Overburdened foreigners authorities (ABHs): The peculiar nature of the NRW regulation that the entire enforcement of returns is the responsibility of the local ABHs/ ZABs has several consequences for the enforcement process as such: First of all, the ABHs are overstretched due to a lack of qualified personnel, and there is no coherent standard for the training of officers. This leads to a situation where staff are not properly trained but are responsible for picking people up from shelters and taking them to the airport. Moreover, due to overwork, ABH staff tend to prioritise certain groups of people for forced removals over others, which means that ‘*Gefährder*’ are prioritised over families, and Dublin cases with a strict removal deadline or otherwise the invocation of sovereignty clause are considered more urgent than other returns to third countries or the origin country. All of this is said to be happening without a clear legal backing from the higher authorities (district governments and state/ MKJFGFI) and without having the time and staff to keep track of the constantly changing legal regulations governing forced returns. As a result, representatives of ABHs stated that they try to muddle through (“*man schlängelt sich so durch*”), recognising at the same time that this is sub-optimal and culpable (“*das ist auch wieder sträflich*”). This is another manifestation of how the dilemma of doing justice to integration and return at the same time, is playing out in the ABHs’ everyday working routines.

Given the lack of adequate (including legal) orientation, guidance and sufficient resources (both financial, training and staff-wise) to implement this dual mandate, the muddling incorporates responses and actions that lead to (deliberate or unintentional) violations of

¹⁵³ In collective charters, Frontex monitors are present; however, they only report to Frontex and do not share their insights with member-state institutions such as the Forum Airports in NRW (FFiN). Interview, 7 May 2024.

regulations and clearly constitute deviant behaviour, thus taking forms of what Robert Merton (1938) conceptualized as anomie.¹⁵⁴ Interestingly, Merton identified innovation as one of the main responses to the experienced gap between set objectives and available means, an empirical phenomenon we also found in this research – manifest in institutional modifications (establishment of and division of labour between ZABs), bureaucratic innovations (new forms, dossier-types, etc.), and particularly different techniques and surveillance approaches to establish deportability (in and around the accommodation facilities).

b) Implementation gaps related to NRW's forced removal regime

Lack of minimum standards vs. overly restrictive regulations: Related to the previous point, a major gap felt by the non-governmental actors is the absence of minimum standards set by the state (MKJFGFI) concerning different stages of enforcement: In particular with regard to forced removal detention, best interests of the child, family separation, the handling of persons who are ill, and the provision of professional translators also in the case of single forced removals. Similarly, the facilitating side, mainly the ABHs themselves, complained about the lack of clear legal provisions, ambivalent regulations and statements, and the non-preparedness and unwillingness of the state authorities to take on responsibility, to steer, be transparent, and provide strong guidance for the practitioners. As one representative of a municipal ABH put it, "... this vague approach and this unwillingness to commit and wanting to serve the right-wing fringe a little more so that we can perhaps pick up a few more votes or the left-wing fringe, so that we get some more votes there, that won't help us. I hope that politicians will understand this as soon as possible because only then will they make us more capable of acting, and only then will the public realise that we are not engaged in non-transparent nonsense here but that we are dealing with the sensible application of the law" (interview, 22 July 2024).

One interviewee described immigration law as a pawn of sensitivities (*Spielball der Befindlichkeiten*) (25 September 2024). In a case where a Yezidi woman was to be forcibly removed by a municipal ABH and the staff, because of their own doubts, asked the district government and the MKJFGFI what their position was, they received no answer – one day before a federal ban on forced removals for Yezidis was enacted¹⁵⁵ (interview, 25 September 2024). Then again, sceptics argue that certain minimum standards are counterproductive, e.g., where the provisions and requirements for health assessments have been set in such a way that psycho-social therapists and other specialists are excluded from the pool of experts and cannot intervene in the interests of people who are seriously ill. This is perceived as a strategic tool by the state to ensure deportability.

Lack of sincerity, impartiality and transparency: Instead, opacity prevails – from the top-down exchange of information between state administrative bodies to the inability to share case files due to the different technical equipment each ABH uses. The pending evaluation of the law on forced removal detention enforcement since 2022 is another indicator

¹⁵⁴ For this important hint about Merton's concept of anomie, we thank Norbert Cyrus, one of the scholarly reviewers of the draft version of this *Working Paper*.

¹⁵⁵ The unclear position of German government representatives in the case of Yezidis was cited by representatives of ABHs and civil society actors as an example of ambivalent, dishonest politics. While Germany only recognised the genocide against Yezidis in early 2023, it did not refrain from deciding to forcibly remove Yezidis a few months later.

that the MKJFGFI seeks to avoid scrutiny and documentation of measures as a basis for discussion, reflection and institutional learning. According to informed observers, it would be a healthy process to start a discussion in Germany about which control and coercive measures the government intends to enforce and why it considers such interventions in people's fundamental rights as legitimate. So far, the problems have not been addressed openly, there is no clarity about options and, consequently, no concept of alternative perspectives. Calls by state and party representatives to increase forced returns and close the so-called enforcement gap (Scheel 2024) are populist rhetoric, as this would violate binding international conventions to which Germany is a party, not least the principle of non-refoulement. However, making unrealistic promises and then failing to follow through will lead to disappointment among the public in the extreme centre and right-wing circles. Their dissatisfaction is increasingly directed at courts and judges who are suspected of being partial, in particular when for example a marked Islamist and/ or 'Gefährder' successfully appeals to the court to suspend his forced removal based on the detrimental situation in the country of origin. As one interviewee stated, the overall constellation of dishonest politics and symbolic discussions risks eroding the rights-based order in Germany and strengthening right-wing elements of the population (interview, 8 May 2024).

Outsourcing of responsibility after arrival in destination country: Too little is known about the conditions in the destination countries – how they affect the life of forced and assisted returnees – some of which are also not acceptable in EU member states (Dublin transfers). For example, Germany has stopped Dublin transfers to Italy and Greece, while France is being discussed as the next non-destination. Nevertheless, there are hardly any authoritative studies that analyse what happens after return.¹⁵⁶ The attitude of the German and NRW authorities to cooperate with 'partner' countries and to trust that conditions in these countries do not need independent evaluation seems to follow the logic of 'no documentation, no problem, no need for control, no responsibility'.

c) Implementation gaps related to federal-level frameworks

Legislative hyperactivity without impact: The absence of a clear immigration law is the most pronounced gap between the federal legislative mandate and the implementation obligation of the 81 local ABHs in NRW. This is all the more serious as Germany is a constitutional state and its public authorities derive their identity from a highly legalistic attitude. However, the criticism of the existing legislation is two-fold: First, legislation is drafted by legal experts of the Federal Ministry of the Interior in Berlin, and largely without the input and control of experts and practitioners. As a result, according to ABH representatives, the recent laws to improve the enforcement of forced removal remain ineffective, fail to achieve their purpose and do not fit the reality on the ground. For example, pick-up staff from ABHs are now entitled to search more than one room and even the entire shelter for a forced returnee, which is reportedly not practical in the case of few people and never done in reality. Second, the provisions of the Residence Act (AufenthG) have become so complex – with too many special cases and exceptions included in the legal texts – that ordinary people are no longer in a position to understand the regulations, let alone those who

¹⁵⁶ A few case study-based analyses for experiences after assisted return exist though, e.g., Kothe et al. 2024, Mielke 2023, Rudolf 2022, Schmitz-Pranghe 2023, Sahin-Mencütek 2023, and Vollmer 2023; for experiences after forced removal see, e.g., Alpes 2019, Kleist 2016, and Peutz 2010.

are subject to them. Moreover, the placeholders of immigration law – the Asylum Act and the Residence Act (AsylG, AufenthG) – are overly abstract, inflexible and bureaucratic, which dehumanizes migrants, turning them into numbers, objects and statistics rather than individuals with (dis)abilities and needs.

Local government autonomy: Federal laws are supplemented at the state level with legal regulations on how to deal with and interpret federal law – adding another layer of bureaucracy as manifested in the ZABs in NRW, which represent a parallel structure that aims to increase centralization, albeit with unclear effects. In addition, the third tier of government, the sub-state municipal/ district self-government (*kommunale Selbstverwaltung*) mandates each county and municipality to decide on its own procedures for practical implementation. This explains the variety of the ABHs in terms of their structure, staffing, capacities, self-understanding and attitudes – ranging from a strict legalistic enforcement of removals to an integrationist perspective. As one interviewee put it: “German migration law is a prisoner of federalism” (interview, 25 September 2024). The high number of actors and institutions, especially those set up at the interface between the federal states and the national level, including numerous working groups, commission assessments and reports that lead to decisions that are neither made transparent nor clarified and publicly available, result in a decision deadlock (Behnke, 2020) and an ‘efficiency’ deadlock that the local level cannot resolve but is constantly criticised for.

Taken together, the implementation gaps are numerous, and it is not technologies that are ought to be discussed to solve the implementation challenges. Instead, they result from the search for solutions in ever more institutional innovations and legal adaptations with endless exceptions and new detailing of case possibilities, leading to an administrative-bureaucratic deadlock and inefficiency. Gaps in monitoring and the outsourcing of responsibility for returnees by handover at departure/ arrival in the destination country pose high risks from a rights protection perspective but are largely ignored. The reasons for this are speculative but it is likely that a mixture – consisting at least of a lack of political will and a lack of capacity in the face of bureaucratic and decision-making deadlocks on the one hand and an overload of staff and mandates on the other – explain the current situation. The realisation that the two manifestations of lacking capacities are linked and not just correlate is potentially an important first indicator on the way to a necessary infrastructural involution, i.e. the dismantling of regulatory immigration law (AufenthG, AsylG) of provisions that are no longer coherent with and counteract visions of integration. The selective but far-reaching abolition and concretisation of immigration law would ideally provide the legal backing the implementers in the ABHs are calling for.

6. Conclusion

This report has provided an overview of the return migration infrastructures (RMIs) in the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), Germany. It has presented in-depth analyses of the institutions, actors, their undertakings, relations and related materialities, places and technologies for assisted return and forced removals, with an extended focus on the latter. In addition, the RMI flow map has highlighted existing overlaps between the infrastructural components of assisted return and forced removal, pointing to a large-scale coherence and entanglements of the institutions involved, their implementation steps (preparation and enforcement), the use of technology, as well as funding sources. Both return pathways coexist

to a certain extent, but if returnees designated for the assisted return path drop out of it, they are legally obliged to follow the forced removal path. While both ‘tracks’ are designed to follow a linear logic, the reality of return trajectories includes discontinuities (e.g. active resistance of returnees at different points in the return process), U-turns (successful petitioning, recognition of hardship cases) and loops (where returnees re-enter Germany to re-apply for asylum or with or without regular work visas).

In the federal structure of Germany, return governance spans all three tiers of government: national, (federal) state and local (in municipalities and districts), although the local-level ABHs are mainly responsible for implementation. The report shows that the actors involved in return migration governance are highly diverse and, indeed, increasingly fragmented. The landscape of actors includes the state administration, the police, Frontex, embassies/consulates and their respective country delegations, civil society organisations, other non-state actors, such as private companies, service providers, interfaces initiated by and organisationally linked to the state of NRW or the relevant ministry and courts. There are many actors with different mandates, roles and types of relationships, as well as the temporal presence of some of them depending on the occasion.

In this regime of complex interplay of multi-level authorities and offices with partly overlapping mandates, coordination, implementation and cooperation become challenging tasks. At the state level of NRW, actors enter into collaboration and networks at various vertical levels involving the different institutions of the state administration. Nevertheless, in the course of centralisation efforts, parallel institutions have been established to increase the number and effectiveness of returns – particularly in connection with the chimera of a diagnosed enforcement gap, which captures the differential between those who are legally obliged to leave and those actually subjected to return. The conceptual flaw of this delusion is that only a fraction of those obliged to leave are actually obliged to leave immediately, as it is presumed that they do not face any internal or external obstacles to return; the majority are temporarily tolerated for reasons of protection but are usually caught up in chain tolerations and thus remain removable. Recently established regularisation mechanisms are more important and more effective in practice in reducing the stock of people without a right to stay.

Several findings stand out when looking at the linkages between actors, practices (‘doings’), places, materialities, equipment, technologies and financial flows: The disproportionate effort in pooling human and financial resources, multi-level administrative processes and coordination (with countries of origin, Frontex, national and state institutions) in the course of preparing and implementing returns. This goes hand in hand with ‘creativity’ and ‘innovations’ that are manifest in techniques such as different surveillance approaches to establish deportability. The structuring of identity clarification processes and the logistical preparation of the return enforcement procedure into separate, highly specialised administrative components, underpinned by individual state edicts and legal provisions, has contributed to a situation in which the migrants concerned figure as dehumanised objects or numbers in bureaucratic processes. However, whether the dehumanisation of the migrants is the effect or rather the cause and catalyst for these processes is a matter of debate and further research. Migrants are managed within the purview of bureaucratic frameworks that serve to implement national policy objectives that are not even clear. The administrative habitus generates the metaphor of winning or losing ‘a game’ in cases where a designated returnee could be ‘identified’ despite their non-cooperation, thus creating a precondition for

deportability, even if it may take years to reach this point. The conclusion of the institutional actors involved is not to rethink the forced removal regime but to call for an increase in the efficiency of internal administrative procedures, a reduction in bureaucracy and the concretisation and coherence of legal frameworks on the one hand and the facilitation of information exchange and collaboration with authorities in countries of origin on the other.

Nevertheless, the discretionary powers of individual caseworkers and directors of foreigners authorities, municipalities or county councils (*Landräte*) have a huge potential for creating a dominating 'culture' of local and central foreigners authorities that tend either towards a strict anti-immigrant enforcement of the law (Residence Act) by interpreting it in line with its recent amendments of the Repatriation Improvement Act/s, or towards using their discretionary powers to work towards integration and offer designated returnees stay perspectives. It is striking to observe the extent to which the internal 'culture' of an entire ABH changes with a new director who 'believes' in one or the other orientation, whether they are more inclined towards a forced-removal-at-any-cost perspective or an integrationist perspective, and also how administrations, as well as the street-level bureaucrats, will follow suit in their everyday practices and assessments.

There are numerous implementation gaps in the practical enforcement of forced return (monitoring, overburdening of the ABH) with regard to the preconditions in the NRW context (lack of minimum standards, lack of transparency, outsourcing of responsibility to the origin country upon return) and with regard to the national context (e.g. legislative hyperactivity without effect). To some extent, they result from a legalistic and bureaucratic search for solutions in ever more institutional innovations and legal adaptations. However, gaps in monitoring and outsourcing responsibility for returnees when handing them over on departure/ arrival in the destination country risk violating their fundamental rights. These have so far been largely ignored due to a lack of political will and capacity to assess conditions in destination countries according to the same rule of law criteria as those applied across Germany. This calls for an extension of the RMI concept to include transnational analysis.

Significantly, while the RMI framework is heuristically insightful and allows for a more holistic view of state-induced return trajectories without focusing primarily on the designated returnee, but rather on the structuring machinery of the more or less smooth and de facto mostly non-linear processes, the underlying regulatory framework is the explanatory variable for how the RMI is structured and what outcomes it actually produces. The NRW case shows that describing actors, 'doings', technologies and the relationships between them is not enough to fully understand the return infrastructures, as in the preparation and enforcement of forced removals. Both stages are embedded in and reflect a prevalent 'ideological regime' consisting of a set of concepts, worldviews and the norms they generate (welcoming vs. removal authorities), which are underpinned by legal regulations that guide the 'doings' within the NRW return governance regime. In line with previous research (cf. Mattern 2018, Lin et al. 2017, Borrelli 2023), a key finding of this study is that the 'ideological underpinning' of the forced return infrastructure is not only highly relevant for understanding the logic, functioning and evolution of forced return migration infrastructures – in particular how they have unfolded in a continuous and highly dynamic manner in Germany and NRW since 2015 – but is a fundamental element of any (F)RMI (analysis).

The study also reveals that instead of a simple binary choice between facilitation and contestation of returns, there is a continuum. While institutions tend to have a relatively fixed

stance, the individuals involved in these institutions may occupy various positions along this continuum. At one end are institutions, individuals and actions that actively seek to forcibly remove people, devoting considerable time, energy and resources to what they perceive to be necessary processes of preparation and enforcement. At the other end are those who fundamentally question the return regime, challenging not only the practice of forced removals but also the underlying societal norms – structural racism – that support these practices. With rare exceptions, many ‘contesting’ actors and actions involved in forced removals do not question forced removals but only how they are carried out. They find the process problematic because it involves human rights violations and ‘drama’, especially when families are affected. The empirical findings of this analysis suggest that the roles of the actors can be placed along a spectrum between these two poles. It is, therefore, not always easy to make a clear distinction between pro- and anti-return protagonists.

Ambivalence also characterises the role of designated returnees (who may collaborate or resist at different points in time), the occurrence of strategic non-doings (opaqueness, lack of monitoring), and the role and self-understanding of return counsellors in assisted returns. The diversity of actors and related approaches, objectives and conditions that aim to channel at least some of the mandatory returns through the instrument of assisted ‘voluntary’ returns without an explicit legal basis on which to rely is another expression of tension.

In the context of an overwhelming emphasis in German political and public debates on the perceived need for more/ faster/ more effective returns, assisted return has remained largely invisible. Some providers would like to promote the benefits of assisted return more widely. At the same time, there is a widespread sentiment that more publicity will mean more scrutiny and, inevitably, controversy over the provision of assistance. Therefore, the reasons given for remaining “under the radar” are that the field has evolved as a patchwork of practices and approaches without a real legal basis and that current developments in the German debate on return seem to provide growing support for “tough” measures regardless of their financial cost or lack of effectiveness (not to mention the human cost). In the context of recent developments at the federal level (the call for more forced removals) and in NRW (increasing financial precarity for non-state actors), stakeholders were sceptical about the future of assisted return in general or of the continued meaningful role of non-state actors in it.

Overall, a convincing positioning of return assistance in the current political context is fraught with difficulties due to the conflicting objectives and tensions that characterise migration governance as outlined in this *Working Paper*. At an individual level, most return counsellors draw mainly on their intrinsic motivation to assist those ‘clients’ who genuinely want to return and can be assisted, as well as others whom they have helped to make obligatory return less threatening. There were also more examples of individuals showing ‘bottom-up’ initiative, taking advantage of their scope for proactive engagement that assisted return entails. Overall, however, return counselling derives its legitimacy more from its ability to implement obligatory returns more effectively than others. As the way forward is concerned, there has been a notable shift in financial support from non-state counsellors to central foreigners authorities (*Zentrale Ausländerbehörden*, ZAB) particularly in NRW. While the former have the advantage of providing decentralised and low-threshold counselling, their reach and the trust placed in them is greater. The minority of ZABs in NRW have recently separated forced removal and assisted return, physically, in terms of staff, displayed ‘habitus’ and dress code, thereby imitating the NGO model to some extent. At the same time, they have more control over the process, e.g., they “own” their clients’ files and are thus more effective in preventing

and delaying imminent forced removals. Just as in the case of forced removals, there is a clear trend in assisted return for state institutions to take more control of the process, both at the federal level – signified by the BAMF taking over REAG/GARP implementation from IOM – and at the NRW level with the shift in counselling. This, however, results in increasing insecurity on the part of the NGOs because their funding is at risk.

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8. Annex: Glossary

APS

The APS (Departure Planning Statistics) system optimises and makes the necessary adaptations in return management via two modules available on the ZAIPort platform, i.e. statistics and planning. According to MKFFI (2021b), the statistics module enables the ABHs to continuously monitor departure developments and ‘to derive appropriate action steps on this basis’, e.g., the provision of state support. The statistics module is reported to have eliminated the need for written enquiries about completed returns. The planning module is intended to help mobilise state support resources for more effective, demand-driven use of priority and collective charter measures. Therefore, ABHs are obliged to enter information on actual possibilities of departures.

AZR

With the Central Register of Foreigners (AZR), the Federal Office of Administration provides the central information hub for foreigners and asylum law for the authorities entrusted with implementing the relevant regulations. In addition, the transfer of data to other public and - to a limited extent - non-public bodies is also permitted. The information and data stored in the AZR includes highly sensitive and personal data, even the asylum hearing documentation with most personalized details. The authorities with access to the AZR include the Social Welfare Office and the job centre but not the non-governmental return counselling services. AZR data are linked to a wide range of policy-relevant activities, from asylum law to border crossings, e.g. at airports. The BAMF has been the register authority since 30 July 2004.

Best Rück Luft

The “Bestimmung über die Rückführung ausländischer Staatsbürger auf dem Luftweg” (Provision on the repatriation of foreign nationals by air) contains rules according to which the Federal Police organize the execution of forced removals by air. The guideline came into effect in 2016 (Bundespolizei, 2016) but was only published in 2019 following a request under the Freedom of Information Act. It first defines the main terms in the context of forced removals, then it includes provisions for the preparation, execution and debriefing of the forced removal. There are also detailed provisions on the organisation of charter measures. The guiding principle of forced removals by air according to the “Best Rück Luft” is: “No forced removals at any price”.

Checklist NRW

The checklist for the preparation, implementation and documentation of the forced removal measures by air (“Checkliste zur Vorbereitung, Durchführung und Dokumentation von Rückführungsmaßnahmen auf dem Luftweg” (Ministerium für Inneres und Kommunales [NRW] 2016) provides a detailed step by step list of the preparation, implementation of the deportation and transport to the airport, with the handover to the Federal Police. It is supposed to be filled in for every forced return process by air, including the name and date of birth of the returnee. During the preparation for forced removals special needs of returning families or minors are included, as well as special circumstances in case of illness or pregnancy. In the second phase (implementation) a distinction is made between pick-up from an accommodation or from detention.

Eurodac

The European system for the comparison of fingerprints of asylum applicants (Eurodac) is designed to support the implementation of the Dublin-III Regulation, as

each member state is required to take the fingerprints of all asylum applicants over the age of 14 and of those apprehended while trying to cross a border irregularly, and to transmit the data within 72 hours to Eurodac. The system can also be consulted when a third-country national is found to be illegally present in a member state, to determine whether the individual has previously applied for asylum or was apprehended when trying to enter the EU illegally.

FAR

The web-based Frontex-Assisted Returns (“FAR”) modules of the Integrated Return Management Application (IRMA) serves as a platform/ database between EU member states and Frontex to organize return operations, including voluntary returns and forced removals by charter and scheduled flights or by other means of transport, requesting the standing corps under FRESO (Frontex Return Escort and Support Officers) profile and monitors from the Frontex pool of forced return monitors, as well as communication about financial aspects. Advertised benefits include that FAR significantly reduces email exchange with member states, paperwork, and manual filing of various forms by automating multiple processes and procedures, assuring higher transparency by keeping track of activities and automated deletion of personal data as required by the EU Return Regulation.

IRMA

In line with Art. 48 (1) (d) Regulation (EU) 2019/1896 on the European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations, Frontex operates an IT platform called the ‘Integrated Return Management Application’ (IRMA). IRMA is a web-based platform where member states, Frontex and the European Commission exchange strategic and operational information on return-related activities. IRMA provides a secure exchange platform for return practitioners and policy makers at national and European level, allows the proper coordination of return-related needs, activities and return operations by member states, and allows data collection, reporting and analysis on return in Frontex and the member states with the stated aim to increase the efficiency of returns. (Source: Frontex written reply to emailed questions, 29 July 2024).

OSINT

OSINT (Open Source Intelligence) comprises information collected by authorities and intelligence services from freely available, open sources for intelligence-gathering. These sources include social media profiles and professional networks, news and websites. With the help of appropriate analysis tools, usable insights are gained from the various pieces of information. Open Source Intelligence is not limited to the Internet, but can also use freely accessible mass media such as magazines, daily newspapers, radio and television as sources. Reported benefits of OSINT are low cost, easy access and low risk detection because the information is accessed via public infrastructures and technologies.

PEP

A passport replacement paper (*Passersatzpapier*) is an identity document which, alone or in conjunction with a visa or residence permit, entitles the holder to travel across borders and fulfils some, but not all, of the functions of a passport (Sec. 3 (1) Residence Act). Sec. 3 Residence Ordinance (AufenthV) lists non-German documents that are suitable for a passport replacement paper, e.g. travel documents for stateless persons and refugees or passes for members of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe etc. In Sec. 4 (1) Residence Ordinance (AufenthV), passport replacement papers issued by German authorities are listed, including, e.g. travel document for foreigners, emergency travel documents or travel documents for refugees, etc. A toleration (*Duldung*) is not considered a passport replacement paper.

RCMS

The Electronic Readmission Case Management System (e-RCMS) is a web-based, secure and user-friendly IT platform that facilitates the return and readmission process as defined in readmission cooperation frameworks (applied so far with Pakistan, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, for which the RCMSs were developed between 2017 and 2020). The e-RCMS facilitates the exchange of information necessary for identity verification, including returnee personal data, identity documents, biometric data, as well as the exchange of information relevant to transfer, such as flight details, between the actors involved in the return and readmission process. Moreover, the system also allows for direct, real-time communication between competent authorities concerning readmission applications. The RCMS is part of a project called EURCAP – building capacity for return management – under the Directorate General Migration and Home Affairs of the European Commission (DG HOME) and implemented by IOM. Users are the ABHs/ ZABs.

SIS 3.0

The Schengen Information System is a large-scale database supporting external border control and law enforcement cooperation between member countries of the Schengen Agreement. The SIS consists of a central system (central SIS) with a technical support function and a uniform nation interface, a national system (N.SIS) in each country to communicate with the central SIS, including at least one national or shared backup N.SIS and a communication infrastructure. The Regulation (EU) 2018/1860 (SIS 3.0) aims to strengthen the enforcement and effectiveness of the EU's return policy, e.g. through the facilitation of information exchange on non-EU nationals subject to return decisions. SIS 3.0 requires national authorities to enter alerts as soon as a return decision is taken and established categories of data – since 2023, fingerprints, palm prints, fingerprint traces and palm print traces are used for biometric queries via the automated fingerprint identification system in the SIS – to be included in the alert. Moreover, member states enter alerts to refuse entry and residence to persons who are in the EU illegally and against whom an entry ban has been imposed in accordance with the Return Directive.

ZAB

NRW has established five central foreigners authorities (*Zentrale Ausländerbehörde/n*) in Cologne, Bielefeld, Essen, Coesfeld and Unna – one in each state district – to support efforts of the local foreigners authorities in assisted return and forced removal. The ZABs act as foreigners authorities in their own districts subordinated to the district government and, as such, are responsible for forced removal and assisted returns of people in attached central accommodation facilities (ZUEs). Some of the ZAB also have an additional responsibility for the whole state (Sec. 15a Ordinance of responsibility for foreigners), e.g., ZAB Essen is responsible for the forced removal of foreigners who are considered a public safety threat (*Gefährder*) and data carrier analysis, ZAB Unna is in the lead for PEP issuance, ZAB Cologne for transport/ transfer arrangements.

ZFA

ZAB Bielefeld hosts the central office for forced removals by air (*Zentralstelle Flugabschiebungen, ZFA*), in charge of the organization of forced removals in NRW by charter- or scheduled flights. ZFA determines airline, route and flight dates and books the flights via a contract travel agency. The ZFA also ensures that agreements with the country of origin are adhered to and that flight escorts are provided by security or medical personnel, if necessary (e.g. Federal Police air escorts if 'security-relevant

findings' exist about a designated returnee). If standards cannot be met, the ZFA must cancel the forced removal.

ZUE

The central accommodation facility (*Zentrale Unterbringungseinrichtung*) is a collective accommodation of the state. Asylum seekers are housed in a ZUE after having been in an initial reception centre. The ZUEs are the responsibility of the respective district government. Private commercial or non-profit care service providers are commissioned to provide accommodation and care for those seeking protection. People seeking protection remain in the ZUEs until they are assigned to decentral accommodation or until they (are) return(ed). Some ZUEs have a special purpose. The central accommodation facilities in Bonn-Bad Godesberg, Hamm, Ibbenbüren, Möhnesee, Ratingen-Tiefenbroich and Viersen are currently used as so-called "priority facilities". Accommodation in priority facilities serves to ensure more efficient implementation of forced removals directly from the state facilities.

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